

Report on the
Implementation of
the Section 75
Equality and Good
Relations Duties
by Public Authorities
Based on Public
Authority Annual
Progress Reports

Equality Commission

FOR NORTHERN IRELAND

1 April 2005 - 31 March 2006

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Accuracy of information contained in this report

This report primarily reflects the views of the Equality Commission on implementation of the Section 75 Statutory Duties during 2005-06. Section 2 of this report sets out information included in a sample of public authority annual progress reports. Annual reporting by public authorities is a process of self assessment and the Equality Commission does not currently formally validate the accuracy of information they provide. However, the Commission intends to do this in subsequent years.

Foreword

The period under review can be characterised as a 'last push' by many parts of the public sector to better mainstream equality considerations within their organisations before the commencement of a series of statutory review process. Much discussion took place during the year regarding the Five Year Review of Equality Schemes by public authorities and the Equality Commission's Review of the Effectiveness of Section 75, scheduled to commence during 2006.

Throughout 2005 the Commission carried out its statutory remits regarding Section 75 in terms of offering advice and ensuring compliance. These activities were carried out against the backdrop of the Review of Public Administration (RPA) with the associated opportunities and worries that such a fundamental review exercise brings. In this context the Commission worked to ensure Section 75 considerations were implicit in the RPA and the minds of the various decision makers involved.

This report marks something of a sea change in the Commission's approach to reporting on progress by itself and others in the promotion of the Section 75 duties. Unlike previous years the Commission has moved away from review and analysis of all reports submitted. Instead a range of public authorities have been selected from across the public sector. In addition information from the selected reports is directly reported so as to better reflect on progress within specific authorities. In future years it is hoped to develop this process further.

During 2005-06 many public authorities strove to demonstrate improvement in the promotion of equality of opportunity and good relations in their policies and practices. This report highlights where further developments could be made and illustrates how top level commitment is even more important at this stage of scheme implementation as it was during the initial phase of development.

Once again I would again like to thank those individuals and organisations who sought to contribute to better policy-making through their participation in consultations during the period under review.

Bob Collins
Chief Commissioner

Executive Summary

In this annual report on Section 75 progress, for the first time, the Commission carried out an analysis of a sample of public authority reports. Information from forty three public authority reports has been directly reported to illustrate progress within specific authorities.

Leadership

Effectiveness in reporting progress in meeting the Section 75 duties appears to be most apparent in public authorities where there is evidence of leadership at the highest levels. In addition this commitment is clearly and consistently communicated and there is reporting of wider staff involvement. Ulster Supported Employment Limited (USEL) highlighted the outcome of staff involvement with representative groups in terms of better engagement and staff being invited to participate in voluntary boards and community projects.

Improving Core Business

In general terms the tying of EQIAs into existing plans for policy review was far from the norm in progress reports analysed. In various reports including those from Government Departments, Health bodies and various UK Wide Public Bodies screening was reported as the main mechanism to mainstreaming equality issues into policy development. Of the eight changes in policies or practices highlighted in the Government Department reports sampled, only one resulted from EQIA activities.

Alternatively reports reviewed from smaller public bodies, the Local Government and Housing sectors were more prevalent in reporting the use of EQIAs as a means of mainstreaming equality issues into policy development. This included clear evidence of bodies undertaking EQIAs initially as a means to identify further monitoring requirements in advance of considering policy developments.

Amongst the various improvements in core business noted were:

- An increase in the uptake of special exam arrangements due to increased awareness among College staff and students.
- Ulster Community Hospital Trust (UCHT) reported 257 interpreting episodes in 2005-06 for Black and Minority Ethnic patients, a 76 % increase in annual provision.
- Ards Borough Council reported introduction of a concessionary

rate for disabled people at the Council's Leisure facilities with free admission for carers.

- Northern Ireland Ambulance Service (NIAS) worked with the other emergency services to launch an SMS Texting service to enable members of the deaf community to access Accident and Emergency Ambulance by texting from a mobile phone.

Coherence

Various examples of inter and cross sectoral working were reported during 2005-06. These included efforts by Strabane District Council and the Western Health and Social Services Board to jointly developed a Multi Agency Welcome Pack, providing information in different languages on local services. Details were also provided about the regional translation contract, put in place in March 2006. This ensures that all translations procured by Health and Personal Social Service organisations meet certain quality standards.

Engagement

Several reports including those from the Northern Ireland Social Care Council and Ulster Supported Employment Limited set out definite notable benefits from engagement. These reflected greater transparency in the decision making process and the views of community and voluntary groups informing work. However, some difficulties continue to be reported by bodies regarding “consultation fatigue”. Special European Programme Body for example reported representative bodies/organisations claim a lack of resources to be the main problem and this is viewed as a major constraint around effective implementation.

Good Relations

As in previous years, there was considerable variation in the approaches taken by public authorities to the implementation of the good relations duty. Annual progress reports indicate that some organisations are very proactive. For example the University of Ulster won Business in the Community's 'Good Relations' award in 2006 for its Civic Leadership Programme. Others, have yet to substantively address the duty. And there are also those which may not be reporting their good relations activities in a way that reflects the level of their work or commitment.

1. Introduction

The Statutory Duties

- 1.1 In the Agreement reached between Governments and political parties in April 1998, the section dealing with Rights, Safeguards and Equality of Opportunity included a commitment to a statutory obligation on public authorities. This was implemented through the Northern Ireland Act 1998.
- 1.2 Under Section 75 of this Act (Appendix A), public authorities are required to have due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity between people of different religious belief, political opinion, racial group, age, marital status or sexual orientation; between men and women generally; between people with a disability and people without; and between people with dependants and people without.
- 1.3 A public authority is also required to have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations between persons of different religious belief, political opinion or racial group.
- 1.4 The duties are designed to ensure that government and public authorities make equality of opportunity and good relations considerations central to policy development.

Equality Schemes

- 1.5 Each public authority must have an equality scheme in place, both as a statement of its commitment to the statutory duties, and as a plan for performance of the duties.

Consultation

- 1.6 Consultation with those affected by public policy decisions is central to the effectiveness of the duties. Equality schemes spell out an authority's arrangements for consultation on the duties and on the likely impact of policies.

Impact on Policy

- 1.7 Public authorities must also assess the equality impact of their policies and publish the outcome of such assessments. This assessment includes the identification of measures to better promote equality of opportunity as well as the identification of potential adverse impacts. If a public authority's assessment of the impact of a policy shows a possible adverse impact on any group, it must consider how this impact might be reduced, and how an alternative policy might lessen or reduce any adverse impact the policy may have. The public authority must also show how it considered alternative policies which might better promote equality of opportunity.
- 1.8 Each equality scheme contains a commitment by the public authority to submit an annual report of its progress to the Equality Commission. To help public authorities prepare their reports the Commission has provided a template for them to follow (see Appendix B). The Equality Commission uses the information gathered from these reports to assist it in keeping the effectiveness of Section 75 under review - as we are required under the Northern Ireland Act - and to publicly report on progress.

Summary of Progress to Date

- 1.9 The Commission has published four previous reports of progress on the implementation of the duties, the first covering January 2000 - March 2002, the second covering 2002 - 2003, the third covering 2003 - 2004 and the fourth covering 2004 - 2005. These reports are available on the Commission's website at www.equalityni.org. Each public authority's progress report is a public document and is available from that authority.
- 1.10 The 2005-2006 report includes information provided by public authorities subject to Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act. They were in the first instance asked to report by 31 August 2006, and a reminder was sent to those who had not sent their reports by that time requesting information by 1 October 2006. By the end of October twenty five public authorities set out in Table 1 had not submitted progress reports for the previous year.

Table 1: Submission of Progress Reports Behind Schedule

Public Authority	Date Received
University of Ulster	1/1/2006
Gosford Housing Association	6/11/2006
SHAC Housing Association	6/11/2006
Broadway Housing Association	6/11/2006
Castlereagh Borough Council	6/11/2006
Antrim Borough Council	11/12/2006
Belfast Education & Library Board	11/12/2006
Southern Health & Social Services Council	12/12/2006
South Eastern Education & Library Board	15/12/2006
Consumer Council for Postal Services	5/02/2007
Craigavon Area Hospital Group Trust	15/02/2007
Southern Education & Library Board	23/02/2007
Southern Health & Social Services Board	23/03/2007
Magherafelt District Council	26/03/2007
Dept of Trade & Industry	Not received by end March 2007
NI Authority for Energy Regulation	Not received by end March 2007
NI Council for Curriculum Examinations & Assessment	Not received by end March 2007
North South Language Body	Not received by end March 2007
Open Door Housing Association	Not received by end March 2007
Presbyterian Housing Association	Not received by end March 2007
The Certification Office	Not received by end March 2007
Western Education & Library Board	Not received by end March 2007
Woodvale & Shankill Housing Association	Not received by end March 2007

1.11 Advice on making official complaints regarding scheme implementation was provided by the Commission on sixty seven occasions. This advice related to complaints and investigations in connection with Schedule 9 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998, known as Paragraph 10 and 11 investigations. At the start of the period under review, investigations of equality scheme implementation by public authorities were in progress as follows:

- Sinn Fein and Department for Social Development (Paragraph 11) - investigation as to whether DSD had failed to screen an alleged policy adopted by it for allocating funding under the Peace II initiative, adversely affecting areas that would generally be perceived to be Catholic/Nationalist. The investigation concluded that the alleged failure had not been established.
- Childrens Law Centre and Northern Ireland Office (Paragraph 10) - alleged failure to properly apply the screening criteria to and properly consult upon its policy proposals and legislation in respect of anti-social behaviour affecting children and young persons. The investigation concluded that both failures had been established, and the Commission recommended that an Equality Impact assessment be carried out by the Northern Ireland Office of the Anti-Social Behaviour Order policy and legislation in relation to its potential impact on children and young people.
- Northern Ireland Commissioner for Children and Young people and Northern Ireland Office (Paragraph 11) - investigation into the period of time allowed by the NIO on the legislative stage of the Anti-Social Behaviour Order proposals. The investigation concluded that the alleged failure had not been established.
- Finlay and Department for Regional Development (Paragraph 10) - alleged failure to take into account an EQIA and associated consultation when making its decision concerning its policy on concessionary fares affecting women aged between 60 and 64. The investigation concluded that the alleged failure had not been established.
- Allen and Fire Authority of Northern Ireland (Paragraph 10)- alleged failure to deal with a complaint in line with equality scheme commitments. The Paragraph 10 complaint was subsequently withdrawn.

- 1.12 During 2005-06 the Commission received eleven complaints of alleged failures to implement approved schemes under Paragraph 10, three of which were subsequently withdrawn. Following consideration the Commission authorised two investigations as follows:
- Butler and Lisburn City Council - alleged failure to take the findings of a previous EQIA into account when making a decision to alter a policy relating to the flying of the Union Flag at Civic Headquarters and at various Council locations. The investigation was ongoing at the end of the period under review.
 - Marshall and Omagh District Council - concerns the presence of a Memorial of a political nature on a Council-owned site and a subsequent decision of that Council to dispose of the section of the site in which the memorial is situated to the group believed to have been responsible for erecting the memorial. The resulting alleged failures to comply with approved Equality Scheme related to alleged failure to screen and equality impact assess the policy. The investigation was ongoing at the end of the period under review.
- 1.13 Copies of statutory duty investigation reports can be found on the Commission's website (www.equalityni.org).
- 1.14 The Commission also completed an audit of progress on implementing the good relations duty and made arrangements to publish and disseminate findings. Research work was undertaken to develop guidance on Section 75 monitoring and forty two equality schemes were approved by the Commission. During the year the Commission responded to significant equality impact assessments (EQIAs) reflecting business plan priorities.
- 1.15 Annual reporting is an important mechanism to continue dialogue on mainstreaming. It allows the Commission, public authorities and representative organisations to identify good practice. The analysis set out in the following sections is both a commentary on progress during 2005-06 and an insight into future opportunities to take forward equality scheme commitments. Individuals will benefit most from equality scheme implementation if public authorities review their activities and continue to identify opportunities to better promote equality of opportunity and good relations. Further examples of implementation practice can be found on our website (www.equalityni.org).

1.16 This year, for the first time, analysis of annual progress reports took place at the same time as public authorities' five year equality scheme reviews. Given the considerable information that had already been received and analysed, the Commission carried out an analysis of a sample of public authority reports received. This reflects the initial conclusions of the review of effectiveness of Section 75, which recommended a more strategic approach to monitoring compliance.

2. Summary of Progress Made By Public Authorities

- 2.1 Public authorities subject to Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 (the Act) submitted progress reports to the Equality Commission for the period 1 April 2005 - 31 March 2006. To help public authorities address all of the key issues relating to the period, the Commission produced a reporting template (see Appendix B). This section of the report outlines the steps taken by specific government departments, public authorities from the education, further and higher education, health, local government and housing sectors, authorities responsible for reserved and excepted matters as well as other Northern Ireland, cross border and UK wide public authorities, to promote the equality of opportunity and good relations duties.
- 2.2 In order to summarise progress a number of public authorities which were due to submit progress reports for this reporting period were selected from across the public sector. Information from forty three reports is directly reported to illustrate progress within specific authorities. The Commission has sought to highlight the impacts and outcomes of work, the Equality Commission's assessment of the main areas where progress has been made on scheme commitments, and areas where the Commission believes further improvement is needed.

Government Departments

- 2.3 This section of the report includes two of the eleven government departments established under the Northern Ireland Act 1998: the Department of Culture, Arts and Leisure (DCAL) and the Department of Education (DEd)

Impacts and Outcomes

- DCAL launched a new angling website which included details of fisheries with disabled angler facilities, and the nature and level of accessibility.
- DCAL reported the Public Records Office for Northern Ireland (PRONI) sought to address a gender imbalance in its user profile by including women's groups in its outside lecture programme and engaging ethnic minorities through a Northern Ireland and China exhibition as part of a wider "Big Draw" programme.
- DCAL detailed efforts by PRONI to redevelop its website to enable customers generally, and for people with visual impairments in

- particular, to view large print on screen through an electronic mouse thus improving access to catalogues, finding aids and documents.
- DEd highlighted accessibility improvements made during the review of the Religious Education Core Syllabus. Questionnaires and consultation documents were provided for primary and post primary schools in understandable formats and on line. Over 500 responses were received and the exercise was seen as making a successful impact.
 - In its concluding remarks DEd indicated that persons of political opinion and marital status were not applicable to the consideration of positive benefits arising from the Department's work to implement the statutory duties.

Areas of progress

- Both Departments reported continuing progress in building equality and good relations into corporate, business and/or operational planning.
- In its report DEd highlighted its strategic framework which is designed to provide clear direction and guidance over a 3-5 year period. The department's 2005-06 business plan included two strategic aims linked to Section 75 and eighteen supporting actions and targets. Of these seven were reported as achieved during the year, ten achieved with some delay and one likely to be achieved with some delay.
- DCAL highlighted its' strategic framework against which policies are regularly reviewed. This is seen as maximising opportunities for joined up working with partners including other government departments, non departmental public bodies and non governmental organisations.
- Both DCAL and DEd detailed the extent of training provision for staff, reporting the range of workshops and conferences which staff benefited from.
- DCAL outlined how it successfully extended consultations by posting an on line version on all library computers throughout Northern Ireland. It was reported this practice alone generated almost a thousand replies from individuals on occasions.
- DCAL also made significant progress through the Sign Language Partnership Group in producing best practice guidance on the provision of public services to deaf people, with the actual guidance due to be launched slightly outside the reporting period.

- During the year no Section 75 complaints into scheme implementation were reportedly received by these two government departments.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- During the year only one change to policies or practices, resulting in positive changes was reported as a result of EQIA activities amongst these two departments.
- DCAL highlighted business area responsibilities for establishing monitoring systems and the department wide continuous survey of participation and satisfaction with services. However, data from this can only be analysed by six of the nine Section 75 categories.
- DEd reported the action “to publish a revised schedule of EQIA's by December 2004” amongst those actions achieved with some delay. While a revised EQIA programme was issued for consultation it was not finalized by the end of the reporting period.
- While DCAL highlighted technological developments to enhance accessibility in its report DEd merely described progress in terms of website maintenance and updating with information about the statutory duties and ongoing consultations.
- DEd reported limited information on data collection and analysis particularly regarding supplementing available research. During the year additional research was undertaken by DEd relating to carers, young people, Travellers, disability and race and such could be more effectively reported in terms of supplementing existing systems to monitor future impact.
- DCAL pointed out that following its EQIA of the Public Angling Estate and Water Recreation Facilities it gave a commitment to consult interested parties on an annual basis. The Department went on to highlight the lack of response from a particular representative group. This development of reporting in this way is not welcomed by the Commission.

Education

2.4 The education sector comprises the five Education and Library Boards (ELBs), the Staff Commission for Education and Library Boards (SCELB), the Council for Catholic Maintained Schools (CCMS), the Council for the Curriculum, Examinations and Assessment (CEA) and the Youth Council for Northern Ireland. This section of the report focused on information reported by Belfast Education & Library Board (BELB) and the South Eastern Education & Library Board (SEELB).

Impacts and Outcomes

- BELB and SEELB indicate in their reports that their work on implementing the statutory duties has produced positive benefits for all of the Section 75 categories. However, as in previous years the focus of reporting is on actions taken to implement the duties rather than outlining evidence of impacts and outcomes.
- During the early part of the year BELB and SEELB, along with the other three Education and Library Boards (ELBs), issued a report on the screening of their Resource Allocation Plans. Briefing sessions were held with trade unions and Joint Consultative Forum members and twenty one regional and local consultation meetings were held. Thirty three written submissions were received and a report on the screening exercise was issued in August 2005.
- An EQIA of Work-Life Balance Policies was completed and an action plan produced. One of the actions was the publication of a Guide to Work-Life Balance policies which was produced for issue to staff.
- The ELBs/Staff Commission held a Five Year Review workshop, to give affected representative groups the opportunity to participate in the review process. A report of the event was compiled and issued during the reporting year.

Areas of Progress

- The inter-ELB/Staff Commission Statutory Duty Co-ordinating Group met on thirteen occasions during the year to progress equality issues.
- The Staff Commission/ELB Joint Consultative Forum, which includes representatives from the trade union, community and voluntary sector and public sector, held five meetings and issued

- eight update leaflets to Forum members.
- BELB and SEELB, as part of a sectoral arrangement, developed a draft Good Relations Policy. A workshop, attended by participants from a range of functional areas across the Boards, was held. It is intended that the draft policy will be consulted upon and an interim action plan, which will operate until the Education and Skills Authority is established, will be drawn up.
- Fifteen pupils from the SEELB area took part in the 'Exploring Diversity Programme', which explores issues affecting young people from a variety of ethnic backgrounds. In light of the success of the Programme SEELB plan a follow-up programme for schools in the Lisburn area.
- BELB and SEELB held a number of equality training events, including EQIA and race awareness training, for a variety of staff.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- BELB and SEELB should provide more evidence of impacts and outcomes in terms of positive benefits for individuals from the nine equality categories as a result of implementing the commitments outlined in their Equality Schemes.
- BELB and SEELB should provide more information regarding progress made locally i.e. within their Board areas.
- During the year no Section 75 complaints regarding scheme implementation were received by BELB and SEELB.

Further and Higher Education

2.5 The Further and Higher Education sector comprises the sixteen Institutes/Colleges of Further and Higher Education and the five Universities. This section of the report focuses on four of the above public authorities: Armagh College, Belfast Institute of Further Education (BIFHE), Fermanagh College and the University of Ulster.

Impacts and Outcomes

- In their reports both the Colleges and the University of Ulster state that they believe their work on implementing the statutory duties has produced positive benefits for most of the Section 75 categories.
- During 2005-06 three cultural diversity projects were completed by the Colleges and an event was held in February 2006 to showcase

- the projects.
- Following the success of the cultural diversity project BIFHE decided to appoint a Cultural Diversity Project Worker, to roll out the outcomes from the project and to further mainstream diversity into the Institute's curriculum and student services.
 - An increase in the uptake of special exam arrangements was reported by the Colleges, due to increased awareness among staff and students.
 - The University of Ulster completed two EQIAs during the year. The EQIA of Recruitment and Selection resulted in a new recruitment policy being approved by Council. The EQIA of Aquatic Facilities at Jordanstown identified impacts in relation to age and disability and as a result of consultation the University committed to actions intended to have a beneficial effect on those categories.

Areas of Progress

- The University of Ulster's Equality & Diversity Advisory Group met on a bi-monthly basis throughout the year to oversee the implementation of the University's Equality Scheme.
- Research to identify 'chill factors' in Colleges (i.e. factors which might make a College less attractive to students from a particular community background), was completed and the research report was presented to College Principals.
- BIFHE targeted programmes at a number of single identity groups providing women-only classes in English/literacy, maths/numeracy, Irish, arts & crafts, as well as specific classes for male Travellers, and classes for members of the Chinese and Indian communities.
- The University of Ulster won Business in the Community's 'Good Relations' award in 2006 for its Civic Leadership Programme which involved 100 staff, 150 students and local residents.
- During the period under review the University of Ulster established a Sexual Orientation Working Group to review guidance on sexual orientation in employment and draft an action plan for this area of equality.
- College staff received training in a number of equality areas including disability, age legislation and harassment.
- Over 350 University of Ulster staff and a number of students received equality awareness training in the year. As a result of this training the University believes that senior management are more aware of equality issues and that equality is taken into account at an earlier stage of policy development.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- It is important that individual Colleges ensure that the statutory duties continue to be implemented and mainstreamed during the transition period of the 'Further Education Means Business' programme, which will result in the sixteen Colleges being merged into six.
- The Colleges should provide more evidence of impacts and outcomes in terms of positive benefits for individuals from the nine equality categories as a result of implementing the commitments outlined in their Equality Schemes.
- The Colleges and the University of Ulster should provide more information regarding progress made within their areas of responsibility, as well as areas of joint working.
- No Section 75 complaints were reportedly received by the Colleges or the University of Ulster.

Health

2.6 The Health and Social Services sector comprises the Department of Health, Social Services and Public Safety (DHSSPS), four Health and Social Services Boards covering the North, South, East, and Western areas, four Health and Social Services Councils, 19 Health and Social Services Trusts and 11 other Agencies and authorities. This section of the report focuses on progress reports provided by Altnagelvin Hospital Health & Social Services Trust (AHSST), Eastern Health and Social Services Council (EHSSC), Northern Ireland Social Care Council (NISCC), Southern Health & Social Services Board (SHSSB), Ulster Community and Hospital Trust (UCHT), Western Health & Social Services Board (WHSSB), Western Health & Social Services Council (WHSSC) and the Northern Ireland Ambulance Service Trust (NIAST).

Impacts and Outcomes

- UCHT reported 257 interpreting episodes for Black and Minority Ethnic patients during 2005-06, a 76 % increase on provision in the previous year.
- UCHT was involved in the production of 'Equality Vision' DVD, video and booklet, in conjunction with the Junction Club, an independent group of adults with learning disabilities.
- SHSSB is a member of the Southern Area Action with Travellers (SAAT) group which successfully brought new funding to help

- Travellers improve health status, accommodation and educational status through a range of practical schemes.
- Northern Ireland Ambulance Service (NIAS) worked with the other emergency services to launch an SMS Texting service to enable members of the deaf community to access Accident and Emergency Ambulance by texting from a mobile phone.
 - As part of its' Community Education Project, NIAS worked with young people on a cross- community basis to outline and explain the impact of attacks on emergency services.
 - Northern Ireland Social Care Council improved registration services for persons of different racial groups; persons with and without a disability and persons with and without dependants and produced a Welcome pack specifically for staff from overseas.
 - Along with other public authorities, the Board is included in the regional translation Contract, put in place in March 2006. This ensures that all translations procured by HPSS organisations meet certain quality standards.

Areas of progress

- Ulster Community and Hospital Trust incorporated equality and human rights into its NVQ training, in the form of a series of two-hour modules entitled 'Fostering Equality and Human Rights'.
- SHSSB in partnership with the three local health and social care groups in the Southern area jointly commissioned services for elderly people. The Board reports that the partnership has proved to be very effective in addressing local issues to improve care for older people, facilitating hospital discharge and maintaining people in their homes.
- SHSSB highlighted some initiatives undertaken in 2005-06 with the key aim of improving the well-being of vulnerable children and young people. This included planning services through the Sixth Sense group, which brings together young people with a range of complex disabilities. In addition supported housing schemes were set up in three Trust areas including development of a major project for all children in the Brownlow area of Lurgan.
- NIAS identified differences at the divisional level in the operation of policies. As a result the Trust has embarked on a Policy Review to ensure consistency in policy implementation to ensure best practice throughout the Trust.
- NIAS also reported details of its work in conjunction with Trademark, to develop a programme of Equality and Good

Relations Training. A total of 110 managers have attended the Good Relations training in the reporting period.

- Northern Ireland Social Care Council commenced an EQIA on its policy - 'Registration of Social Workers, Social Care Workers and Student Social Workers' and during a review of the scope of the EQIA two further areas of work were identified.
- Eastern Health and Social Services Council provided a comprehensive training programme for staff, including Equality Vision training, and all staff attended racial equality training provided by NICEM.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- Altnagelvin Hospital Health and Social Services Trust, Western Health and Social Services Board, Western Health and Social Services Council, Ulster Community and Hospital Trust and Southern Health and Social Services Board variously reported on input to the DHSSPS regional EQIA programme. However, none gave any indication of local EQIAs of Trust policies being undertaken in the reporting period.
- While Northern Ireland Ambulance Service did not report undertaking any EQIAs during the period it embarked on a major Policy Review. The Commission anticipates that details on the outcomes of this review of policies will be included in future reports along with details of any EQIAs undertaken as a result of the review.
- Eastern Health and Social Services Council reported limited progress in development of data collection and analysis systems which are highly relevant in respect of its advocacy role for patients and users of health and personal social services.
- Altnagelvin Hospital Health and Social Services Trust, Western Health and Social Services Board and Western Health and Social Services Council reported a comprehensive screening of policies and a major review of internal systems and procedures for screening during the year. Of the 28 policies subjected to screening none were screened in for an EQIA. The Commission looks forward to further information on the proposed EQIA on Mental Health Services Review due to be commenced in 2006-07.

Housing

2.7 The Housing sector comprises 39 registered Housing Associations. For the purpose of reporting progress the following associations have been reviewed: Ballynafeigh, Choice, Clonard, Donacloney Hearth, Triangle and Ulidia.

Impacts and Outcomes

- Housing Associations schemes were approved during this reporting period. Therefore progress largely focused on scheme actions to implement the duties and impacts and outcomes are not yet prevalent. However, some were evident.
- The various Housing Associations registered with Language Line enabling access to telephone based translation services on demand. 'Welcome' poster's, which provide information on translation services, were displayed. Additionally facilities were put in place so that information can be provided in alternative formats.
- Choice and Donacloney Housing Association reported their Tenant's handbooks were reformatted in an appropriate font size and colour.

Areas of progress

- Housing Associations progressed a collaborative approach to the implementation of the statutory duties with the Northern Ireland Federation of Housing Associations (NIFHA) playing a co-ordinating role in this process. This involved facilitation of meetings, information/advice provision, arranging training, managing consultation processes, developing guides or template documents, liaising with the Equality Commission and acting as a link between Housing Associations and representative groups.
- Implementation targets for meeting equality scheme obligations have been included in Business or Corporate Plans of the Housing Associations.
- The Housing Associations conducted a joint policy screening exercise which identified 16 main policy areas, of these 10 were screened in for Equality Impact Assessment.
- An EQIA Co-ordination group was established and work was commenced on two equality impact assessments covering access and communications, and complaints.
- Various Housing Association staff and some Board members

attended a number of training events and seminars organized by NIFHA in relation to the implementation of Section 75, policy development, screening, and undertaking EQIAs.

- Choice and Triangle Housing Associations reported that equality scheme awareness has been incorporated into staff inductions for all new employees. Triangle has also built in Equity, Diversity and Interdependence awareness into induction training for staff and board members.
- Triangle Housing Association facilitated the establishment of a special needs Tenant Advisory Group (TAG) to engage with their main stakeholder group. They have also created a new staff post - Tenant Participation coordinator to assist two way communication with tenants.
- In relation to data collection and analysis Housing Associations highlighted various socio- economic data collected about applicants and tenants for new lettings through 'NICORE' returns which includes information on seven of the nine equality categories.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- As well as reporting on joint areas of work Housing Associations should provide specific detail on progress within their own Association. For example Housing Associations should report if they are undertaking a screening exercise or carrying out Equality Impact Assessments on policies which are specific to them.
- Housing Associations should work with other sectoral bodies to extend their data collection systems so that data is collected on all nine equality groups.
- Housing Associations should seek ways to progress the good relations duty effectively.
- Housing Associations should involve the affected Section 75 groups in the development and delivery of training.

Local Government

2.8 The Local Government sector comprises 26 Local Councils, the Local Government Staff Commission (LGSC) and the Northern Ireland Local Government Officers Superannuation Committee (NILGOSC). This section of the report includes six of the above public authorities: Ards Borough Council, Armagh City & District Council, Belfast City Council, Dungannon & South Tyrone District Council, Magherfelt District

Council and North Down Borough Council

Impacts and Outcomes

- Ards Borough Council reported introduction of concessionary rate for disabled people at the Council's Leisure facilities with free admission for carers.
- North Down Borough Council decided the National Anthem would no longer be sung at the end of the Annual Meeting. This change was the result of an EQIA.
- Dungannon & South Tyrone District Council adopted mitigating actions following an EQIA of Community Grants to ensure greater access to grants for political groups. The Council also reported increases in the representation of women in its senior and middle management with actual proportions reported. The Council highlighted the identification of a Champion for Women in Local Government and an action plan developed.
- Armagh City and District Council made Browse Aloud software available on their website to increase access to information and services by those with visual impairments.
- Belfast City Council indicated implementing the Council's Disability Strategy lead to thirty two work experience placements. The Council was also awarded the Opportunity Now Gold Standard in respect of their Gender equality work.

Areas Of Progress

- Ards Borough Council reported the introduction of Service Delivery Improvement Plans with Equality and Good Relations targets that link directly with corporate themes.
- North Down Borough Council highlighted that pre-screening of Notices of Motion assisted discussion and understanding of the potential issues identified.
- Dungannon District Council highlighted meetings with Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency with a local community race initiative ANIMATE regarding planning and population statistics. The Council also worked with Animate to amend monitoring of applicants from migrant populations and examine pilot community planning models.
- Armagh City and District Council indicated the Section 75 duties were incorporated in its New Employees Handbook.
- Belfast City Council reported progress in establishing Consultative

- and Youth Forums and revision of the Councils Induction Programme to include an equality and good relations module.
- Belfast City Council also progressed its equality reporting procedure so that each report presented to Council must enclose an equality statement in relation to the screening procedure. The Council also reported the introduction of an Irish Language voice mail service and establishment of an interdepartmental liaison working group on Travellers.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- As Ards Borough Council acknowledged itself, feed back to consultees could be better particularly by showing positive outcomes achieved.
- Magherafelt Council should formalise a detailed training plan and attention should be given to number of EQIAs started in mid 2004 but not yet completed.
- Armagh City and District Council should publish a report on its Financial Assistance Policy and ensure awareness training for all casual staff is delivered.

Reserved and Excepted Matters

- 2.9 The Northern Ireland Act included provision for a Northern Ireland Assembly to make laws and take decisions on all the functions of the Northern Ireland departments. The Secretary of State for Northern Ireland retained responsibility for Northern Ireland Office matters not devolved to the Northern Ireland Assembly. These reserved and excepted matters include policing, security policy, prisons and criminal justice, elections and peace and reconciliation. This section of the report includes progress reported by the Police Ombudsman and the Northern Ireland Court Service.

Impacts and Outcomes

- Little evidence of specific outcomes was provided by either of the two bodies analysed with the focus being on outputs.
- The Office of the Police Ombudsman for Northern Ireland reported that its work on implementing the statutory duties had positive benefits for all the Section 75 categories with the exceptions of persons of different religious belief and persons of different marital status.

Areas of progress

- During the year under review Court User notices containing important information were produced in Russian, Lithuanian, Polish and Portuguese for distribution by the Northern Ireland Court Service's front-line staff.
- A customer survey was undertaken by the Northern Ireland Court Service asking participants to declare their religion, gender and age to enable assessment of differential impact for the groups in question.
- The Office of the Police Ombudsman for Northern Ireland jointly funded and published the findings of two major reports regarding the experiences of the Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual and Black Minority Ethnic Communities with policing. The Office held meetings with representatives of the Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual community, delivered a presentation and held a question and answer session as part of Gay Pride Week during 2005-06.
- The Office of the Police Ombudsman for Northern Ireland engaged in an extensive outreach programme with schools, District Partnerships, voluntary and community groups and political parties.
- The Office of the Police Ombudsman for Northern Ireland initiated a training process with input from minority ethnic NGOs to address diversity issues through the provision of anti-racism, diversity and cultural awareness training.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- Although a number of delivery targets included in the Northern Ireland Court Service Business Plan for 2005/06 were cited (such as the delivery of an Employment Equality Plan and a programme of community outreach), no information was provided as to the impacts or outcome of these initiatives.
- Though general information on initiatives was provided the Office of the Police Ombudsman for Northern Ireland should provide further detail of impacts and outcomes for the nine section 75 categories as a result of the implementation of the statutory duties.

Other Northern Ireland and Cross Border Public Authorities

2.10 Thirty-three public authorities subject to Section 75 have been grouped as 'Other Northern Ireland and Cross Border' public authorities for reporting purposes. These include significant regional non-departmental public bodies such as the Northern Ireland Housing Executive (NIHE) and a variety of other authorities with specific sectoral remits e.g. the Health and Safety Executive of Northern Ireland (HSENI). This section of the report includes eight of the above bodies: Waterways Ireland, Ulster Supported Employment Limited (USEL), Intertrade Ireland, NI Authority for Energy Regulation, Special European Programmes Body (SEUPB), Coleraine Harbour Commissioners and the NI Audit Office (NIAO).

Impacts and Outcomes

- Intertrade Ireland reported a range of positive measures, as detailed in the Employment EQIA, were undertaken to encourage greater levels of participation from the Protestant community.
- USEL reported that the Section 75 duties were strategically set out in its 2005 - 2008 Corporate Plan with input from targeted consultative groups and individuals.
- USEL indicated the outcome of staff involvement with local community representative groups throughout Northern Ireland. This was developed to ensure groups understood the services provided by USEL, however, a number of staff from different operational levels have been invited to participate in voluntary Boards and community projects as a result of this fieldwork.
- Waterways Ireland developed its Sponsorship programme to include specialized advertisements and editorials in targeted publications such as Age Action's "Aging Matters", NCCRI's e-bulletin, the Irish Wheelchair Association's staff newsletter and sports network, the National Council for the Blind's NCBI News Magazine and Focus (spoken magazine) and the Gay Community News.
- Waterways Ireland also adopted an Access For All policy aimed at promoting access for people with disabilities to goods, services and information across the organization.
- In the latter part of 2005, Intertrade Ireland took a lead in sourcing and co-coordinating a comprehensive training programme, covering anti-discrimination law north and south, for personnel across all cross border bodies.

Areas of progress

- Coleraine Harbour Commissioners reported liaison with the local Council in order to promote good relations.
- InterTrade Ireland highlighted the development of detailed knowledge of the process of Equality Impact Assessment (EQIA) of its Equity Networks, Graduate programmes and Communications policies.
- Intertrade, USEL, NIAO highlighted training of staff and new starts in particular. With additional awareness training provided on specific areas including disability, Sexual Orientation and Age issues in particular.
- USEL undertook an internal review of communication and implementation of duties resulting in the realignment of organisational S75 responsibilities to ensure more effective proactive internal/external communication.
- Between 2003 and the end of 2005 SEUPB has collated monitoring information, covering eight of the nine section 75 categories, from over 30,000 individual returns from Peace II Projects in Northern Ireland.
- SEUPB established a Consultation Zone on its Website to enable access via the internet to on-line consultation and submissions with plans to further enhance this aspect in time for consultation on the new programmes in coming years.
- Waterways Ireland outlined details of updates to staff through its quarterly staff newsletter "Water Matters". During the reporting period features included updates on the Equality Work Programme, the Access For All project, and an article on "Racism - the challenge ahead".
- In terms of taking forward commitments to the promotion of good relations a range of initiatives were reported. Waterways Ireland highlighted the organisation wide Customers Services training which examined how each individual, through the acceptance and the valuing of our diversity and interdependences, can contribute positively to good relations.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- NI Authority for Energy Regulation must submit an annual report on progress to the Commission.
- While there has been some reporting of activities by working or task groups their interaction and role vis a vis the responsibilities

- of senior management in driving scheme implementation could be further developed.
- SEUPB previously outlined slippage in the timetable for scheme implementation, particularly in relation to impact assessments. However, the body is committed to completing the full programme of impact assessments covering all existing functions within the five year timetable for implementation of the scheme.
 - USEL reported the outcome of tracking software purchased to monitor uptake of programmes by the nine equality categories. Difficulties were encountered in monitoring the effectiveness of outreach and programme uptake by all of the specific groups covered by S75.
 - While SEUPB highlighted its strategic implementation role in relation to its function as a managing authority for both the Peace II and Interreg IIIA Programmes the organisation could enhance its annual reporting to include evidence of addressing disadvantage given that both programmes have equality mainstreaming as one of the key principles.
 - Some problems continue to be reported by bodies from this sector regarding “consultation fatigue”. SEUPB for example reported representative bodies/organisations claim a lack of resources to be the main problem and this is viewed as a major constraint around effective implementation.
 - While the NIAO highlighted that it does not deliver services directly to the public, it noted it can contribute in terms of promoting equality of opportunity through heightening awareness of the statutory equality duties in the course of audit work. In addition to ensuring that staff are fully aware of the statutory duties further reporting of the result of greater awareness in the course of audit work is important.

UK Wide Public Authorities

2.11 Eighteen UK wide public authorities, referred to as 'UK authorities', were subject to Section 75 during the period under review. These include major Whitehall government departments and various non-departmental public bodies with functions relating to Northern Ireland. This section of the report includes four of these authorities: Big Lottery, British Council, Information Commissioner, and HM Revenue & Customs

Impacts and Outcomes

- Big Lottery amended its organizational wide risk injury policy to more fully consider the needs of staff with visual impairments and minimize the risk of injury while carrying out duties.
- Big Lottery launched the Young Peoples Fund (NI) in September 2005. The programme targets resources at young people at greatest risk of exclusion and/or offending. It was developed in consultation with young people and other key stakeholders, and through screening a number of changes were made before its launch.
- HM Revenue & Customs (HMRC) agreed with the Royal National Institute for the Blind (RNIB) to offer a single memorable telephone number for visually impaired and blind customers for assistance with their tax affairs.
- HMRC reported on benchmarking and equality network initiatives including the Employers Forum on Age, The Gender Trust, and the Civil Service Race Equality Network, which helped the organization focus on future policy developments and delivery of day to day business objectives. Resulting independent assessments of HMRC's diversity performance reported: Race for Opportunity Gold Standard (7th in the public sector), Disability Standard (3rd out of 80 public and private sector organisations), Opportunity Now - Gold Standard (92%).
- The Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) produced specific publications on Data Protection issues for people with learning difficulties.
- The ICO developed guidance on how to carry out monitoring in a privacy friendly way as a result of concerns from some public authorities that data protection was a bar to meeting the Section 75 duties.

Areas of progress

- HMRC developed a detailed and comprehensive Diversity Action Plan (DAP) to ensure consistent strategic direction taking account of responsibilities under Section 75 of the NI Act, the Cabinet Office 10 point plan, the Race Relations Act and forthcoming Equality legislation.
- HMRC conducted an evaluation of Equality Matters learning in two stages. Stage 1 involved a sample of 765 questionnaires completed immediately after the learning was delivered. Stage 2

took place between 4 and 6 weeks after the learning was delivered and involved telephone interviews with 135 of the participants including both staff who had attended, and managers who had facilitated the sessions.

- BIG Lottery piloted its new Equality Assurance Process in Northern Ireland and Britain. The process, which supports screening activities, is intended to ensure equality monitoring is built in at every stage to meet Section 75 and Race Relations Amendment Act 2000 statutory requirements.
- In terms of training initiatives BIG Lottery reported a programme of mental health training was provided to staff by Action Mental Health during 2005/6. HMRC reported details of participative diversity and equality training for all senior and middle managers.
- HMRC launched an Accessibility Awareness site to help IT developers/programmers by making them aware of how their actions could exclude users from the systems they build. Seven golden rules for IT design are presented and a demonstrator shows how easy it is to put obstacles in a user's path.
- The first HMRC National Staff Survey took place in May/June 2005 with questionnaires including perceptions of performance in relation to equal opportunities and seeking information in relation to each of the nine Section 75 groups. Results were considered by each of the thirty six business units with priorities and appropriate actions identified at business unit level.
- In terms of good relations several aspects of progress were highlighted. HMRC highlighted a series of intercultural events with representatives of the Indian and Chinese Community involving senior and middle managers. Big Lottery highlighted the strategic role of its programmes in dealing with community relations and the legacy of the Troubles while the Information Commissioner's Office noted the role of NI regional Office in dealing with particularly sensitive issues and ruling on such in an information context in an even handed manner indirectly contributes to meeting the good relations duty.

Areas for further improvement noted by the Commission

- No EQIAs were reported as being progressed during the period under review by Big Lottery, HMRC or the ICO.
- Further reporting of impacts is needed by these bodies, particularly in terms of identifying and delivering positive benefits.
- The Information Commissioner acknowledged in his report a lack

of significant progress on the part of the office during 2005/6. A number of factors were cited including staff changes and the operational challenges experienced by the office as a result of full implementation of access rights under Freedom of Information legislation in January 2005. In the area of screening in particular a more meaningful consultation exercise is anticipated.

- More progress in adding generic and mandatory monitoring categories could be made, as well as communicating to data providers the benefits of providing such information.

3.0 Conclusions

- 3.1 The key developments and lessons from the public authority reports reviewed have been arranged in terms of Leadership, Improving Core Business, Coherence, Engagement and Good Relations. Examples of practical developments and good practice in scheme implementation can be found on the Commission's web site under Section 75 www.equalityni.org. Specific examples of promoting good relations by public authorities can also be found in the document Promoting Good Relations: A Guide for Public Authorities, which is also on the web site.

General Points on Leadership

- Effectiveness in reporting progress in meeting the Section 75 duties appears to be most apparent in public authorities where there is evidence of leadership at the highest levels, and that this commitment is clearly and consistently communicated and evidenced in progress reports.
- A number of reports highlighted the role of leadership in driving scheme implementation forward. For example one local authority cited a particular emphasis of its mayor during 2005-06 who held a sizeable number of civic events and meetings with Section 75 representative groups. Other reports noted the role of Chief Executives in ensuring scheme commitments were resourced and organizational arrangements put in place to ensure such. There were a notable number of public bodies which created new posts directly reporting to the Chief Executive that had specific equality scheme focus.
- In addition there were a number of bodies which reported changes in responsibility for implementation of equality scheme. These included new cross departmental co-ordination teams, usually based within a centre of expertise or business improvement team.

General Points on Improving Core Business

- In general terms the tying of EQIAs into existing plans for policy review was far from the norm in progress reports. In various reports analysed including those from Government Departments, Health bodies and various UK Wide Public Bodies progress was on screening was reported as main mechanism to mainstreaming equality issues into policy development. Alternatively various

Smaller public bodies and those from the local government and Housing sectors were more prevalent in the use of EQIAs as a means of mainstreaming equality issues into policy development. Indeed there is clear evidence some of the smaller Northern Ireland and Cross Border bodies are undertaking EQIAs initially as a means to identify further monitoring requirements.

- The number of public bodies that have provided half day workshops and awareness sessions, facilitated by representative groups and targeted at front-line staff remains low. While these activities are resource intensive and demanding in terms of ensuring continuity in service provision it also has the most potential to greatly improve access to services.
- There were many examples of mainstreaming and development of service delivery arrangements. Perhaps the best example was reported by Altnagelvin HSS Trust which provided antenatal classes for Chinese Women with its Midwives developing appropriate information materials with class attendees also having interpreter support. This Trust also reported employing a community midwife with designated responsibility for providing support to women in the Travelling community.

General Points on Coherence

- The number of public bodies that are involved in sectoral consortium is very small. More examples, like the Western Equality and Human Rights Forum (WEHRF), would ensure greater consistency in implementation of the Section 75 statutory duties.
- Various examples of cross sectoral working were reported during 2005-06 including efforts by Strabane District Council and the Western Health and Social Services Board to jointly developed a Multi Agency Welcome Pack, providing information in different languages on local services.
- A further example of regional joined up working was evident during the year in the health sectors 'Accessible Formats Working Group'. This working group produced an information resource for migrant workers and their dependants on health and social services in Northern Ireland.
- The Information Commissioner's report noted in the past the Equality Commission had facilitated a number of networks, which had been useful as a meeting and contact point, and the expectation of future network meetings was raised.

General Points on Engagement

- Several reports including those from the Northern Ireland Social Care Council and Ulster Supported Employment Limited set out definite and notable benefits from engagement. These reflected not only on internal corporate governance and greater transparency in the decision making process but the views of community and voluntary groups informing the organisations work.
- Several reports outlined public authority perceptions of the difficulties some Section 75 groups face in terms of resources to respond fully to public authority consultations. To this end some bodies are becoming increasingly flexible regarding closing dates for response.

General Points on Good Relations

- As in previous years, there was considerable variation in the approaches taken by public authorities to the implementation of the good relations duty. Annual progress reports indicate that some organisations are very pro-active: there are those building on strategies, action plans and initiatives commenced in previous years, and others conducting audits, developing vision statements and incorporating objectives in corporate or business plans to start or formalise good relations work. Others, however, have yet to substantively address the duty. And there are also those which may not be reporting their good relations activities in a way that reflects the level of their work or commitment.
- Good relations work was stronger during the year in authorities in which equality of opportunity and good relations were embedded and mainstreamed into core business functions, rather than being regarded as a separate or parallel process. Effective implementation of the good relations duty was also more likely where there was sustained provision of resources, enabling staff to continuously deliver on actions.
- Some public authorities reported work regarding the promotion of good relations amongst people with disabilities, older people and people of different sexual orientations. While the Commission welcomes the undertaking of work beyond the existing categories and encourages public authorities to work to a good practice model of promoting good relations, the three Section 75(2) categories must be addressed.

APPENDIX A - Section 75 Northern Ireland Act 1998

- 75.(1) A public authority shall in carrying out its functions relating to Northern Ireland have due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity -
- (a) between persons of different religious belief, political opinion, racial group, age, marital status or sexual orientation;
 - (b) between men and women generally;
 - (c) between persons with a disability and persons without; and
 - (d) between persons with dependants and persons without.
- (2) Without prejudice to its obligations under subsection (1), a public authority shall in carrying out its functions relating to Northern Ireland have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations between persons of different religious belief, political opinion or racial group.
- (3) In this section “public authority” means -
- (a) any department, corporation or body listed in Schedule 2 to the Parliamentary Commissioner Act 1967 (departments, corporations and bodies subject to investigation) and designated for the purposes of this section by order made by the Secretary of State;
 - (b) any body (other than the Equality Commission) listed in Schedule 2 to the Commissioner for Complaints (Northern Ireland) Order 1996 (bodies subject to investigation);
 - (c) any department or other authority listed in Schedule 2 to the Ombudsman (Northern Ireland) Order 1996 (departments and other authorities subject to investigation);
 - (d) any other person designated for the purposes of this section by order made by the Secretary of State;
- (4) Schedule 9 (which makes provision for the enforcement of the duties under this section) shall have effect.
- (5) In this section -
“disability” has the same meaning as in the Disability Discrimination Act 1995; and
“racial group” has the same meaning as in the Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order 1997.

APPENDIX B - Progress Report Template 1 April 2005 - 31 March 2006

EQUALITY COMMISSION FOR NORTHERN IRELAND

Public Authority Progress Report 2005 - 2006

Template to assist Public Authorities to report on implementation of the equality and good relations duties under Section 75 of the NI Act 1998

The information required from public authorities will be based on the period from 1 April 2005 to 31 March 2006. Please ensure that it is submitted to the Commission by 31 August 2006, electronically (by completing this template) and in writing, with a signed cover letter from the Chief Executive or, in his/her absence, the Deputy Chief Executive.

This year's progress report template is significantly different from earlier guidance, reflecting the work that many authorities will be undertaking on their five year review of equality schemes. It is important that the authority reports on what it views as being relevant in terms of progress made on the implementation of the statutory duties from April 2005 to March 2006.

Please enter information at the end of each Section in the template.

Name of public authority (Enter details below)

--

Equality Officer name and contact details (Enter details below)

--

Section 1: Strategic Implementation of the Section 75 Duties

- Outline evidence of progress made in developing equality and good relations objectives, performance indicators and targets in corporate and annual operating plans during 2005-06. Your response should include any targets for 2006-07.
- Please provide details of the direct resourcing of Section 75 work during 2005-06. This should include staff appointed/directed (not names) and details of any budget allocation, to specifically deliver equality scheme commitments.

(Enter text below)

Section 2: Screening & Equality Impact Assessment (EQIA)

- 2a) If a Screening Report has not yet been submitted to the Commission please advise us on the current position with regard to producing this report and forwarding to the Commission.

(Enter text below)

- 2b) If a Screening Report and EQIA Timetable has previously been submitted to the Commission please provide an update (using the matrices in Appendix A) of policies subject to EQIA during 2005-06, new/proposed/revised policies screened during 2005-06, ongoing EQIA monitoring activities and 2006-07 EQIA timetable.

Section 3: Training

- Outline staff and Management Board/Committee training during 2005-06 associated with the Section 75 duties/Equality Scheme requirements (Provide details of types of training provision e.g. general awareness raising, specialist training on EQIA, Screening and Consultation). Provide a summary of any training evaluations and comments on the benefits of such training.

(Enter text below)

Section 4: Communication

- Provide details of how the authority communicated progress on delivery of the statutory duties during 2005-06.
- Provide details of any review of communication activities during the year to ensure effective communication on progressing the statutory duties.

(Enter text below)

Section 5: Data Collection & Analysis

- Describe any systems that were established during 2005-06 to supplement available statistical and qualitative research, including consideration given to using internal organisational data and external networks.
- Describe any systems established during the year to monitor the future adverse impact of policies that were subject to EQIA.
- Detail any research undertaken/commissioned during 2005-06 to obtain data/information relating to the nine equality categories.

(Enter text below)

Section 6: Information Provision, Access to Information and Services

- Outline what action has been taken during 2005-06 to develop arrangements for the provision of information in accessible formats.
- Detail any initiatives/steps taken to improve access to services.

(Enter text below)

Section 7: Complaints

- Identify, during 2005-06, the number of Section 75 complaints:
 - received by the authority;
 - resolved by the authority;
 - which were not resolved to the satisfaction of the complainant; and
 - which were referred to the Equality Commission.

(Enter text below)

Section 8: Scheme Timetable

- Provide an update of your equality scheme implementation timetable (covering all the scheme commitments), identifying any changes since your previous report. Please detail any planned actions outstanding.

(Enter text below)

Section 9: Consultation, Participation and Engagement

- Provide details of the processes adopted to engage with representative groups during 2005-06.
- Outline measures taken to enhance the level of engagement that were successful and unsuccessful.

(Enter text below)

Section 10: The Good Relations Duty

- Provide details of steps taken to implement or progress the good relations duty during the year. Please indicate any findings or expected outcomes from this work.

(Enter text below)

Section 11: Additional Comments on Mainstreaming

- The main aim of the statutory duties is to mainstream equality of opportunity and good relations considerations into the functions of the authority, leading to better policies and service delivery. Please provide any additional information/comments you think may be relevant.

(Enter text below)

Section 12: Concluding Questions

12a) Does the authority believe its work on implementing the statutory duties during 2005-06 produced positive benefits for the organisation?

Yes if yes please complete the following

No

	Very noticeably	Noticeably	No real change
i) Increased awareness of equality issues in policy making			
ii) Increased ability to ensure policies are designed and targeted to reflect equal opportunities objectives			
iii) Increased awareness of good relations issues in policy making			
iv) Increased ability to ensure policies are designed and targeted to reflect good relations objectives			
v) Increased awareness of equality issues in service delivery			
vi) Increased ability to ensure services are designed and targeted to reflect Section 75 requirements			

12b) Does the authority believe its work on implementing the statutory duties during 2005-06 produced positive benefits for groups within the Section 75 categories?

Yes if yes please complete the following

No

	Very noticeably	Noticeably	No real change
Persons of different religious belief			
Persons of different political opinion			
Persons of different racial groups			
Persons of different age			
Persons with different marital status			
Persons of different sexual orientation			
Men and women generally			
Persons with and without a disability			
Persons with and without dependants			

QUESTION 12C

If you answered yes to QUESTION 12 B, for each of the categories where a noticeable or very noticeable change has occurred, please give examples of those changes to policies or practices which have resulted in positive change. If the change was a result of an EQIA please tick the appropriate box in column 3:

	Policy or Practice	Tick if result of EQIA
Persons of different religious belief		
Persons of different political opinion		
Persons of different racial groups		
Persons of different age		
Persons with different marital status		
Persons of different sexual orientation		
Men and women generally		
Persons with and without a disability		
Persons with and without dependants		

Appendix A Screening & EQIA Update

Please enter details relating to the authority's progress using the following matrices.

i) EQIA Timetable - 2005-06

Title of policy EQIA underway during April 2005 - March 2006	Stage (as per Steps 1-7 of EQIA Process) As at end March 2006	If joint - EQIA please state partner authorities	Outline any adjustments to policy intended to benefit individuals from the nine equality categories and outline the relevant categories affected.	Were adjustments to policy a result of Assessment of adverse impact/ feedback from Consultation, or Both Please enter A, C or Both	If EQIA decision making stage completed, is amended policy being implemented? Yes/No
1.					
2.					
3.					
4.					
5.					

ii) Ongoing Screening Activities 2005-06

Title of policy subject to screening during April 2005 - March 2006	If joint policy please state partner authorities	Was initial screening decision changed following consultation? Yes/No	If Screening completed is policy being subject to EQIA? Yes/No	If EQIA planned indicate year for assessment
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				
5.				

iii) Ongoing EQIA Monitoring Activities 2005-06

Title of EQIA subject to Stage 7 monitoring during April 2005- March 2006	If joint policy please state partner authorities	Indicate if differential impacts previously identified have reduced or increased	Indicate if adverse impacts previously identified have reduced or increased
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			

iv) 2006-07 EQIA Time-table

Title of EQIAs due to be commenced during April 2006 - March 2007	Existing or New policy? Please enter E or N below.	If joint-EQIA please state partner authorities	Please indicate expected date of completion of EQIA Stage 6 i.e Decision making stage
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			
7.			
8.			
9.			
10.			

Equality Commission

FOR NORTHERN IRELAND

Section 75 Statutory Equality and Good Relations Duties Acting on the evidence of public authority practices

Full Report

June 2018

Equality Commission for Northern Ireland

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Foreword

The statutory equality and good relations duties on public authorities in Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 are a vital part of the legal framework in Northern Ireland. It is as important as ever that public authorities pay due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity and regard to the desirability of promoting good relations.

It is hard to believe that it is 20 years since the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement and the Northern Ireland Act 1998. Much in the landscape has changed in the intervening period. But what has remained constant, recognising some progress, is the need to continue to address inequalities in Northern Ireland. Some of these are enduring inequalities and some are more recently emerging – it is imperative that public authorities effectively mainstream equality and good relations considerations in the planning and delivery of public policy and the public services for which they are responsible.

The Commission has a role to keep the effectiveness of the Section 75 duties under review. The duties were intended to transform the practices of public authorities so that considerations of equality of opportunity and good relations are central to policymaking and implementation. We have gathered evidence of practices amongst public authorities fulfilling their statutory equality and good relations duties.

Our consideration of public authorities' practices is timely, not only as we are 20 years on, but also because of the real and concrete opportunities to embed fully equality and good relations considerations through the approach taken to the current draft Programme for Government, which has a specific focus on delivering better outcomes for individuals.

This report presents the evidence gathered and makes recommendations on how to address a number of issues identified. The Commission agreed that there is sufficient evidence of issues for public authorities to address as a matter of priority, to ensure the effective implementation of their statutory equality and good relations duties. These issues have been presented to and discussed with a range of stakeholders; and the Commission is already addressing them through its advisory work.

It is clear that cultural and institutional change is required to fully embed the legislative requirements, and to ensure a focus on the impacts and consequences of policies and decisions on the lives of people in Northern Ireland. We have highlighted leadership, in particular, as core to the effective delivery of the statutory equality and good relations duties. We are fully committed to engaging with leaders across the public sector to encourage renewed focus on such delivery.

Dr Michael Wardlow
Chief Commissioner

Summary

- The Commission has a considerable body of evidence available on the operation of the Schedule 9 requirements of the Northern Ireland Act 1998. The Schedule 9 requirements are there to enable public authorities to fulfil their statutory equality and good relations duties set out in Section 75, and to enable enforcement of those duties.
- This report sets out the evidence that the Commission considered during the course of the 2016-17 business year. The evidence has presented a picture of how the duties are being implemented by public authorities.
- This picture has been drawn from: detailed consideration of the evidence gathered; the Commission's understanding from experience in advising public authorities and others; the Commission's understanding of the wider political and economic context for public services in Northern Ireland; and other sources such as from the use of our investigation powers. A number of reviews commissioned during the period; analysis of other research and relevant sources that are referenced in this report, as well as stakeholder engagement, have also contributed.
- The draft of this report was consulted upon in late 2017, with comments received from a range of stakeholders. Consultees confirmed the issues identified and made a number of comments which have been considered and incorporated, as appropriate, in this report. The majority of consultees emphasised the need for the Commission to focus more on enforcement of the duties on public authorities.
- As a result of examining public authority practices, the Commission is concerned about the effective implementation of the Section 75 duties by public authorities.
- The Commission has identified a number of issues from this, which it believes are fundamental to the effective implementation of the duties by public authorities.
- The Commission continues to act in accordance with the statutory framework as set out in Section 75 and Schedule 9 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998, and its actions and interventions are identified and planned accordingly.
- The Commission deploys its resources along the continuum of the "enforcement" functions that are available: from providing advisory materials and advice to public authorities and others; to approving equality schemes; and to fulfilling its responsibilities in relation to complaints and investigations.

Issues identified in public authorities' implementation of the Section 75 duties

- **Leadership.** While recognising the circumstances of reduced resources, leadership continues to be imperative within public authorities to ensure the maintained focus on equality matters, as well as ensuring good governance and

the mainstreaming of equality considerations throughout the business of the authority.

- **Ownership.** The evidence, and our experience in providing advice, suggests that public authorities do not, in all instances, see the purpose of having an Equality Scheme as assisting in fulfilling their statutory equality and good relations duties.
- **Understanding and/or misinterpreting the purpose and scope of the duties.** The evidence clearly suggests that Equality Schemes continue to be seen by public authorities as processes in themselves; they are not seen as contributing equality of opportunity and good relations considerations to decision making.
- The evidence also suggests there are different understandings of, or expectations of, what is required in fulfilling the duties (i.e. to have “due regard/regard to...”) amongst different stakeholders.
- **Definitions of key terms and expectations.** It remains the case, reflected in the evidence of practice, that there is an issue in the continuing differences among stakeholders in what is understood by the terms “equality of opportunity” and “good relations”.
- **Transparency and accountability.** The evidence suggests that some public authority practices have moved away from engagement and consultation informing their equality assessments, limiting opportunities for stakeholder involvement in decision making through use of the Equality Scheme processes. In addition, public authorities present limited information in their equality assessments when using screening templates.
- **Data development.** Equality Scheme commitments have not driven a data development agenda in the public sector, despite the requirements in Schedule 9 for particular monitoring arrangements and the Commission’s longstanding advice.
- **Accountability and risk.** Evidence suggests that the perceived risks of not fulfilling the statutory equality and good relations duties, and/or non-compliance, are probably small.

Issues identified in the Commission’s powers and duties in Schedule 9

- **Complaints.** There are specific requirements on the Commission in relation to complaints. The range and nature of complaints to the Commission has consistently reflected particular issues on policies and practices that are of concern to the complainant, which are not always clearly associated with what Equality Scheme arrangements provide for.
- **Investigations** are adversarial, given the statutory requirement that they are considered in relation to a belief of non-compliance by a public authority with an equality scheme. They have mostly been driven by particular circumstances.

They have provided some learning for public authority practices, but can be limited in the ripple effect of the findings, particularly when arising from a paragraph 10 complaint.

Recommendations

- The Commission recommends to public authorities that:
 - public authority leaders make clear the necessity of fulfilling the duties throughout their organisation – that they continue to be a statutory requirement;
 - senior leaders and decision-makers in organisations actively request the evidence from equality assessments, as well as routinely seek assurance within their organisations that they are fulfilling the duties to have due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity and regard to the desirability of promoting good relations;
 - those responsible for providing information for decision-making on a function or policy should ensure they provide sufficient information, from their equality assessments, for the appropriate consideration (i.e. due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity and regard to the desirability of promoting good relations) to be given in particular decisions;
 - the importance of the statutory equality and good relations duties are highlighted within the organisation, on a continuing basis, and particularly given the current wider political and economic context;
 - the shift of focus from process to outcomes should continue. Equality Schemes are to enable public authorities to fulfil the Section 75 duties – to give the appropriate consideration to the need to promote equality of opportunity and desirability of promoting good relations - when they deliver their functions. Through giving the appropriate consideration, a public authority will ensure that the decisions they take will be mindful of “the consequences on the lives of people”¹; and
 - they ensure their consideration of the need to promote equality of opportunity, and desirability of promoting good relations, is evidence based and the data is available to support the consideration. There is a clear link between the consideration needed to meet the Section 75 duties and the data development agenda that is required for the Outcomes Based Accountability approach to the draft Programme for Government. This should drive the collection and use of equality data.

¹ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 10.

Actions for the Equality Commission

- The Commission has identified a number of actions that it will undertake in support of the recommendations:
 - In its leadership role, the Commission will engage specifically with politicians, senior leaders in public authorities and decision makers to remind them of their roles and responsibilities in ensuring these statutory duties are fulfilled.
 - The Commission will set the agenda and debate in highlighting the importance of the duties and their continuing relevance to, and assistance in the development of, public policy and service delivery in Northern Ireland.
 - The Commission will convey and communicate one of the most important issues and success factors – leadership. While recognising the circumstances of reduced resources, leadership continues to be imperative within public authorities to ensure the maintained focus on equality matters, as well as the mainstreaming of equality considerations throughout the business of the authority.
 - The Commission will continue to prioritise its advisory activities on public authority practices in screening and Equality Impact Assessment (EQIA), as set out in the 2018-19 Business Plan. This will ensure that these central methodologies are used to greatest effect by public authorities in consistently providing meaningful equality assessments of the policy objectives and policy goals under consideration at any given time.
 - The Commission will use the issues identified in this report and review its approach to investigations generally, as set out in the 2018-19 Business Plan.
 - The Commission will collate and publish the Commission’s evidence base on and recommendations relating to equality data and gaps for the draft Programme for Government, as set out in the 2018-19 Business Plan
- The Commission will continue to engage with and work in partnership with stakeholders who have an interest in and role in relation to ensuring that public authorities are fulfilling their statutory equality and good relations duties, as required by Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998.

1. Introduction

- 1.1. This report presents evidence the Commission has gathered from recent practices by public authorities in the implementation of their Section 75 duties, alongside our assessment of those practices. It includes some examination of the wider context, including the political and economic environment, which has informed our understanding.
- 1.2. The Commission has a duty in Schedule 9 of the Act to “to keep under review the effectiveness of the duties imposed by Section 75”². The Commission does this in a number of ways - through its continuing work to provide advice and guidance, as well as through specific review activities, such as the strategic review of the effectiveness of the Section 75 duties it undertook in 2006-8³.
- 1.3. The value and purpose in keeping the effectiveness of the duties under review is set out in the Commission’s draft Corporate Plan for 2016-19:

“We know the strengths in using our legislative framework as a driver for change: whether in the workplace; in the provision of goods, facilities and services; or the mainstreaming of equality and good relations considerations through public policy and public services. We remain in a unique position to evidence and argue for what that framework needs to be, and know that this can shape the wider discourse.”⁴

- 1.4. The draft plan also set out that, in the 2016-17 Business Plan, action would be taken to:

“Examine the evidence we have of current practice in public authorities of fulfilling their statutory equality and good relations duties in order to prepare for a formal effectiveness review of these duties.”

- 1.5. This report compiles the findings of the examination of evidence of current practices within public authorities and wider context in the following chapters:
 - The Section 75 statutory equality and good relations duties: background;
 - Fulfilling the statutory equality and good relations duties in Section 75;
 - Evidence of public authority practices;
 - Mainstreaming and action measures;
 - Public sector equality duties in Britain and the Republic of Ireland;
 - The Commission’s role to consider complaints and investigate;
 - Issues and opportunities identified.

² Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 1(a).

³ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008).

⁴ [Draft Corporate Plan 2016-19](#) (ECNI, 2015), page 10.

- 1.6. As has been set out in the Foreword, the report presents the issues that the Commission has identified and agreed arising from this work. It concludes with a chapter setting out recommendations and proposed actions to address these issues.

2. The Section 75 statutory equality and good relations duties: background

2.1. This section highlights points relating to the background and purpose of the Section 75 duties, what the legislation provides for and how the duties fit within the current context and environment for public service delivery. It also provides a reminder of what the duties are.

The statutory equality and good relations duties on public authorities in Section 75

2.2. Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 (the Act) requires public authorities, which are designated for the purposes of the Act⁵, to comply with two statutory duties.

2.3. The first duty is the *Equality of Opportunity* duty, which requires public authorities in carrying out their functions relating to Northern Ireland to have due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity between the nine equality categories of: persons of different religious belief; political opinion; racial group; age; marital status or sexual orientation; men and women generally; persons with a disability and persons without; and persons with dependants and persons without.

2.4. The second duty, the *Good Relations* duty, requires that public authorities in carrying out their functions relating to Northern Ireland have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations between persons of different religious belief, political opinion and racial group⁶.

2.5. These duties are statutory requirements; the vast majority of public authorities in Northern Ireland are bound by them⁷. These public authorities must pay the **appropriate amount of regard** to the “statutory goals”⁸ set out above when they are carrying out their functions in Northern Ireland.

2.6. These wide reaching requirements on public authorities are given practical effect through Schedule 9 of the Act, which sets out what a public authority must do to show how it will **fulfil** these duties. The central requirement is that a

⁵ See designation as explained in [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 26.

⁶ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 7.

⁷ [List of Public Authorities designated for the purposes of section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998](#), (ECNI, 2017).

⁸ “Statutory goals” is used as a generic term in this report for what a public authority is required to give the right amount of regard to in the legislation. It reflects legal language used and refers specifically to “the **need** to promote equality of opportunity” and the “**desirability** of promoting good relations” [emphasis added]. Using it as a single term for the goals of both duties **does not** lose the different emphasis given in those goals between need and desirability.

public authority must have an Equality Scheme, which will show its arrangements for how it proposes to fulfil the duties imposed by Section 75 to the relevant functions⁹.

The Commission’s advice on the importance of the Section 75 duties

- 2.7. The Commission advises and provides guidance, particularly to public authorities, on Equality Schemes and the duties. The main source of advice is the *Section 75 – Guide for Public Authorities* (the Guide)¹⁰ which says in a section called “*Why the duties are important*”:

“The Section 75 statutory duties aim to encourage public authorities to address inequalities and demonstrate measurable positive impact on the lives of people experiencing inequalities, through paying due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity and paying regard to the desirability of promoting good relations.

Section 75 is a policy tool and its use should facilitate better public policy making and outcomes by focusing particular attention on the promotion of equality of opportunity and good relations. Its effective implementation should improve the quality of life for all of the people of Northern Ireland.

...

Those with responsibility for public policy should remember the reality of inequality, to have it in mind in the decisions they take, and to adjust or modify those decisions so that they can reduce its consequences on the lives of people.”¹¹

Origins of and developments in the implementation of the Section 75 duties

- 2.8. The statutory equality and good relations duties set out in Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 were part of the political agreement at that time – through the Belfast/Good Friday Agreement (the Agreement) itself to the subsequent legislation. Their inclusion in the Northern Ireland Act 1998, as well as the enforcement framework that became Schedule 9, were part of the political and public policy debate at the time, and led to the creation of the Equality Commission itself.
- 2.9. The inclusion of a “due regard” duty in Section 6 of the Agreement¹² was linked to a consultation at the time on the UK Government’s White Paper entitled “*Partnership for Equality*”. That consultation document set out a range of provisions to extend and strengthen the anti-discrimination legislation, and also

⁹ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 4(1).

¹⁰ The Commission has a number of responsibilities set out in Schedule 9 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998, many of which relate to Equality Schemes. The Commission’s *Section 75 – A Guide for Public Authorities*, 2010 contains its Guidelines on form and content of an Equality Scheme, as required by Schedule 9, paragraph 4. (3) (a) and approved by the Secretary of State.

¹¹ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 10.

¹² [The Belfast/Good Friday Agreement](#), 1998, Section 6, paragraphs 3 and paragraph 4 in the Economic, Social and Cultural Rights subsection.

linked to recommendations arising from the earlier guidelines for “*Policy Appraisal and Fair Treatment*”¹³ (PAFT) and work undertaken by, and associated with, the Standing Advisory Committee on Human Rights (SACHR).

- 2.10. A further contribution to the inclusion of statutory equality duties on public authorities in the Agreement was through a discussion paper “*Mainstreaming Fairness*” that was commissioned by Unison¹⁴ and a consultative process on it facilitated by the Committee on the Administration of Justice in 2006-7¹⁵.
- 2.11. This report has been prepared 20 years on from those detailed debates and consideration. It is important to remember that the duties were seen as providing the means to change the public policy landscape and its development at the time. There was interest in the details, including proposed wording for arrangements and methodologies. This interest came from politicians, those with a direct interest in human rights and equality matters, whether as public servants, members of advocacy groups or NGOs and other interested individuals¹⁶.
- 2.12. There was particular focus and debate on the underlying processes that are contained in Schedule 9. The consultation on “*Partnership for Equality*” contributed to the proposed framework; as did the work arising from the PAFT guidelines, and experiences of mainstreaming particular issues to contribute to public policy formulation and development¹⁷. The debates from Parliament at the time illustrate this, and the Commission has continued to reflect this in its guidance¹⁸ on the statutory equality and good relations duties.

Contributors

- 2.13. When Section 75 was established, it was set out in terms of three contributors. First, there are the public authorities themselves on whom the duties lie. Second, there are those who have a contribution, and role in contributing to, the decision-making processes as members of the equality groups and/or representative groups, as well as holding public authorities to account in their fulfilment of the duties. Third is the Equality Commission, with its powers and duties as set out in Schedule 9.
- 2.14. While this report mainly presents evidence of practices by public authorities in implementing their Equality Schemes, it also reflects the role, contribution and issues currently presented by equality groups and groups representing particular interests. Practices have been shaped in conjunction with, and in response to, work and engagement by members of equality groups,

¹³ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 7.

¹⁴ McCrudden, C., [Mainstreaming Fairness? A discussion paper on “Policy Appraisal and Fair Treatment”](#) (Committee on the Administration of Justice, 1996).

¹⁵ [Mainstreaming Fairness “Policy Appraisal and Fair Treatment” A summary of a consultation process around “Policy Appraisal and Fair Treatment”](#) (CAJ, 1997).

¹⁶ The debates in Parliament during the passage of the Northern Ireland Bill in 1998 are illustrative of this, see in particular the [Hansard record of 27 July 1998](#).

¹⁷ Conley, H., [A review of available information on the use of impact assessment in public policy formulation and in contributing to the fulfilment of statutory duties](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 1.

¹⁸ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 9.

representative groups and individuals who have maintained their interest in not only ensuring public authorities are fulfilling their statutory equality and good relations duties, but also that public services reflect their needs and interests in equality terms.

Keeping the effectiveness of the duties under review

2.15. After a number of years of the duties being in operation, the Commission undertook a strategic review of the effectiveness of the Section 75 duties, which culminated in the Commission's report published in 2008¹⁹.

2.16. There were a number of overarching findings at that time, as well as detailed consideration of a range of issues that lead to recommendations that were intended to improve practices and methods for Equality Schemes. In general:

*"... the Commission found overwhelming support for the principles of Section 75. Expectations of the achievements of Section 75 remain high. However, contributors to the review called for a debate on what Section 75 is actually meant to achieve, so that the intended impact of Section 75 does not become so broad as to be meaningless ..."*²⁰

2.17. The vision provided from the 2008 review was of an active, anticipatory duty; an innovative approach to mainstreaming; actions on the duties which would have an impact on inequalities – considering the potential consequences of public policy decision making on the lives of people²¹.

2.18. The Commission at the time set out not only the opportunities but also the challenges that were identified going forward:

*"And here, also, is both opportunity and challenge for the Commission. Opportunity to show the way towards realising what the Statute intended, demonstrating that Section 75 is a mechanism with enormous potential, not a threat; challenge to ensure that its own processes and approaches adapt to the needs of the time and that the public know what the Section offers them."*²²

2.19. The Commission also concluded at that time that, while Section 75 had been effective in a number of key areas, *"a shift in gear was needed to take place within public authorities; away from concentrating primarily on the process of implementing Section 75, towards achieving outcomes"*²³.

2.20. The Commission's focus following the publication of its review report in 2008 was to update its guidance. This guidance provides advice on Equality Schemes²⁴. The purpose of these schemes is to enable public authorities to

¹⁹ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008).

²⁰ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), page 19.

²¹ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), chapter 1.

²² [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), page 3.

²³ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), page 4.

²⁴ The Commission provides guidance on the "form or content" of equality schemes as a public authority must draft an equality scheme to conform with any such Guidelines issued by the Commission, as set out in: Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 4(1).

fulfil their Section 75 duties by paying the appropriate amount of regard in any given circumstances²⁵. The Commission updated its advice and recommendations on the particular methodologies recommended to public authorities for their Equality Scheme arrangements. These methods were familiar to public authority practitioners and other stakeholders at the time and therefore retained and updated. Following the publication of its revised Guide²⁶, the Commission implemented a strategy requesting revised Equality Schemes from public authorities.

2.21. It should be noted that the requirements in Schedule 9 for what is included in an Equality Scheme apply to any public authority designated and required to produce a scheme. The Schedule makes no provision for different types of public authority, whether by size or sector. The Commission's guidance has similarly not differentiated between different types of public authority and has recommended common arrangements for all public authorities with Equality Schemes.

2.22. The Commission also reflected the principles of proportionality and relevance in the Guide²⁷. The subject of relevance in particular is considered in greater detail below, as there are issues identified on this. The principles are important for the public authority, as they provide the basis for ensuring that it can give the appropriate consideration to the statutory goals in particular circumstances²⁸, and so fulfil the duties in set out in Section 75.

Current environment and context for public service delivery

2.23. Through recent advice work and in the collection of the evidence for this report, a number of issues in the current economic environment for public service delivery have been identified. These have been reported as having a direct effect on public authorities and their actions to fulfil their statutory equality and good relations duties:

- The progressive reductions in the budgets available to public authorities have affected the resources dedicated to, and available for, equality matters. This has been apparent in the loss of both institutional memory and knowledge of the equality matters for organisations where there have been reductions in staff.
- In many of the designated public authorities with an approved equality scheme, the resource restrictions have resulted in reorganisation of functions. The equality responsibilities have in places been merged with other responsibilities, and also taken on by those who have not had previous experience in these matters. This has been particularly apparent in either smaller public authorities or those authorities where the functions considered relevant to the duties are fewer.

²⁵ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 4(1).

²⁶ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010).

²⁷ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), pages 26-27.

²⁸ i.e. the "need to promote equality of opportunity" and "desirability of promoting good relations"

- The evidence collected from public authority practices also suggests that the statutory equality and good relations duties are not a particular priority in many public authorities²⁹.

2.24. There have been a range of reviews of organisational practices in Northern Ireland³⁰. There appears to be some coherence in the issues identified here, of transparency and accountability in fulfilling the Section 75 duties, with wider observations of public sector practices in areas of involvement, governance and accountability.

Summary points from this chapter

2.25. Support for statutory equality and good relations duties and their establishment was a significant part of the political discourse and processes around the Agreement twenty years ago. They remain not only statutory requirements but also continue to be important.

2.26. Over time, the focus of attention has been on the requirements for an Equality Scheme, given what is set out in Schedule 9 for the Commission and that the Equality Scheme is the framework through which the public authority is expected to fulfil its duties.

2.27. In recent times, the Commission has noted a number of trends in public authorities where either institutional expertise on equality matters has been reduced, or the equality function has been combined with other responsibilities for particular officers, and evidence that the duties in organisations as a whole might not have the focus they once did.

²⁹ For a summary of the findings on good relations see, for example: Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 27.

³⁰ See, for example, [Northern Ireland \(United Kingdom\): Implementing joined up governance for a common purpose](#) (OECD, 2016) – recommendations are made for the establishment of a framework in Northern Ireland which would address early intervention/prevention: “as a building block for new social policies and programmes, and strengthening data driven analysis for improving service design and delivery”. The Review summary also identifies: “to enhance public trust in the government’s ability to pursue better outcomes for people the Review recommends that Northern Ireland improve dialogue with key stakeholders...” (p16).

3. Fulfilling the statutory equality and good relations duties in Section 75

3.1. This section sets out what is required in practice to fulfil the Section 75 duties and some issues arising from that. It describes what is required to pay “due regard” as established in caselaw. It also sets out a number of specific areas where the Commission has provided advice and guidance, in order to assist public authorities to fulfil their statutory equality and good relations duties through the application of the requirements in Schedule 9.

Context

3.2. When the Northern Ireland Act was passed in 1998 and relevant parts commenced in 1999, the duties conferred in Section 75 were not unique in the United Kingdom as “due regard” duties; they are long established in legislation for a range of statutory goals reflecting political and policy priorities³¹.

3.3. However, the approach to their enforcement was unique at the time; this is what is set out in Schedule 9 and has not changed since the Act commenced. Also, the scope of the Section 75 duties was much wider in its application than preceding legislation, as they cover nine equality categories.

3.4. Section 75 (3) of the Act sets out how bodies come within scope of the duties. The authorities are wide ranging, from small public authorities with functions in Northern Ireland, to government departments and District Councils.

3.5. The Commission implemented a strategy to request revised Equality Schemes from public authorities, following the publication of its revised Guide in 2010. This strategy concluded in the 2013-14 business year, with over 150 revised Equality Schemes approved³² by the Commission for public authorities. The Commission expects public authorities to implement their schemes, using the methods they have committed to, so they can to fulfil their statutory equality and good relations duties.

3.6. The Commission has prioritised advice and guidance on Equality Schemes given its statutory role and the requirements on the Commission: to provide guidance on Equality Schemes; to provide advice to public authorities and others; and to approve equality schemes³³. It has more recently developed a

³¹ “Due regard” duties have not been limited to anti-discrimination or equality legislation, but an example was contained in Section 71 of the [Race Relations Act 1976](#) (repealed): “Without prejudice to their obligation to comply with any other provision of this Act, it shall be the duty of every local authority to make appropriate arrangements with a view to securing that their various functions are carried out with **due regard** to the need—

(a) to eliminate unlawful racial discrimination; and

(b) to promote equality of opportunity, and good relations, between persons of different racial groups”

³² The number of public authorities subject to the requirement that they prepare and submit an equality scheme varies. The Commission maintains a list of current public authorities with schemes approved [here](#).

³³ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraphs 1-3 and 6.

number of short advice notes, which address particular themes such as the principles established for paying the required “regard”³⁴.

- 3.7. Schedule 9 sets out the circumstances which trigger the preparation of an equality scheme, whether on establishment of the authority or in response to a Commission request. A high level of compliance has been maintained with the requirement on authorities to prepare and submit equality schemes. The Commission has focused on this during the preceding Corporate Plan period, given the Strategy referred to above. It should also be noted that the Commission has to date approved the schemes submitted; there have been no referrals to the Secretary of State, nor circumstances where the Commission has not approved a submitted scheme.
- 3.8. The development of the Commission’s revised Guide for public authorities in 2010 focused on revising the Commission’s approach in the central processes of assessments. Part of this was in order to facilitate the “*shift in gear*” that was identified as needed: “*away from concentrating primarily on the process of implementing Section 75, towards achieving outcomes*”³⁵.
- 3.9. However, through the development of the revised Guide, the Commission also considered how the recommended processes, such as screening and Equality Impact Assessment (EQIA), could be improved. The results of the work to amend the methodology of “screening” were contained in its Guide in 2010. The Commission also incorporated an emphasis on “proportionality” and “relevance” into its advice to public authorities.

What is required to have (due) regard

- 3.10. There has been considerable legal interpretation of what is required by a public authority to pay the **regard** that is due or appropriate in the particular circumstances, and this is determined on a case by case basis.
- 3.11. The Commission’s advice has been revised to take account of the appropriate interpretations of the statutory requirements. Specifically, there has been a considerable amount of judicial interpretation of the statutory equality and good relations duties, much of this in England, and the now well-established principles for what is required for a public authority to have “due regard” are relevant for Northern Ireland. The Commission’s advice reflects this.
- 3.12. Case law has determined some principles, commonly known as the Brown principles, from a case of that name in Great Britain. These are principles that the courts in Great Britain take account of when assessing compliance with the public sector duties. The Commission advises public authorities that, in planning for compliance with their duties, they may find these helpful:

³⁴ For example: [Budgets and Section 75: a short guide](#) (ECNI, 2015).

³⁵ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), page 4.

- a decision-maker must be aware that he/she is obliged to comply with the public sector duties;
- the duties must be fulfilled before and at the time that a particular decision is being considered, and not afterwards;
- the duties must be exercised in substance, with rigour and an open mind; and not as a “tick boxing” exercise;
- the duties are non-delegable; meaning that it is the actual decision-maker who must comply with the duties, and not some other person;
- the duties are continuing ones;
- it is good practice to keep adequate records that will show that the statutory goals have actually been considered and pondered and to promote transparency and discipline in the decision-making process.³⁶

3.13. In terms of “due regard”, it is established that the consideration must be given in advance of a final decision being made, not afterwards, and it must be done with an open-mind to achieve the goals set out in statute. Hence, due regard and regard are not determinants of final policy outcomes, but are the processes of providing the appropriate levels of consideration.

In practice

3.14. The duties apply across the range of a public authority’s functions; it is for the public authority to determine when the duties are relevant. The way public authorities are expected to fulfil the duties is through the use of the processes and methods that they commit to in their Equality Scheme. For example, the Commission’s advice is that the “arrangements” a public authority is required to have in their Equality Scheme for “assessing and consulting on the likely impact of policies...”³⁷ should enable an authority to determine whether, and to what extent, the duties are relevant to the function in question and the related policy and decision making processes.

3.15. The processes in Equality Schemes should also ensure transparency and accountability. Anyone who has an interest in the public authority’s business should be able to find out if a particular function is considered relevant, as well as how that function has been being developed and delivered, giving the appropriate consideration to the need to promote equality of opportunity and the desirability of promoting good relations. Public authorities must have arrangements in their Equality Schemes to publish information, such as the results of their assessments of the likely impact of policies on the promotion of equality of opportunity.

³⁶ [Section 75, Northern Ireland Act 1998 and Section 49A, Disability Discrimination Act 1995](#) (ECNI, 2015).

³⁷ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 2(b).

3.16. The Equality Scheme arrangements that the Commission recommends – screening and Equality Impact Assessment, or equivalent methods – are central to providing a public authority with an assessment of the likely impacts of a function or policy on the need to promote equality of opportunity³⁸.

3.17. Public authorities may develop alternative approaches to the Commission’s recommendations for arrangements in Schemes. This is best described through the guiding principles for the Equality Scheme approval process:

*“The Commission’s guide to the statutory duty provides the parameters of the approval process. Recommendations in the guide are, in the main, related to secure the effective implementation of the statutory requirements. The Commission’s test will be that, where a recommendation is not followed, approval will be granted if the public authority can demonstrate that its alternative approach is adequate to secure the statutory requirements.”*³⁹

Relevance

3.18. Section 75 applies to a public authority in carrying out its functions. As it is required to have “(due) regard”, this has been considered in caselaw in terms of “relevance”. Also, the Equality Scheme arrangements are in relation to those functions of a public authority which are “relevant”⁴⁰.

3.19. Commission guidance notes that:

*“...certain functions may be more relevant than others to the Section 75 statutory duties. Case law has also determined that a duty to give “due regard” to certain statutory goals means giving appropriate consideration to them i.e. the degree of consideration that is appropriate in the specific circumstances of the decision or policy being made. What is appropriate is likely to vary from case-to-case, and from one public authority to another. As a general rule-of-thumb, where the level of relevancy is high, then a proportionately high level of consideration is required; and vice versa.”*⁴¹

3.20. The process of “screening”, which is part of the methodology recommended by the Commission to public authorities for their Equality Scheme arrangements, **should be** central to enabling public authorities to address relevance.

3.21. In its initial guidance, the Commission developed a two stage process and revised this in the course of revising its Guide in 2010, in conjunction with public authorities and other stakeholders. The process includes a number of questions for public authorities about the purpose and potential effect of the

³⁸ The Commission also recommends that this methodology can also be used by public authorities to inform its decisions so that it can have the appropriate “regard to the desirability of promoting good relations”.

³⁹ *Section 75 Equality Scheme Approvals Committee – Terms of Reference*, (ECNI, 2011)

⁴⁰ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 4(1).

⁴¹ [Section 75, Northern Ireland Act 1998 and Section 49A, Disability Discrimination Act 1995](#) (ECNI, 2015) and [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), chapter 5.

policy or matter being considered, reviewed or developed. These screening questions should aid the public authority's consideration of relevance. However, the focus of the revisions for the 2010 Guide were the result of a number of aims set out in the Effectiveness Review and screening was revised also to help "*streamline the policy making process*"⁴².

Summary points from this chapter

- 3.22. The focus of legal interpretation has been on what is required by a public authority to pay the **regard** that is due or required in particular circumstances, and this is determined on a case by case basis.
- 3.23. The public authority's Equality Scheme is the framework through which the public authority is expected to fulfil its statutory equality and good relations duties in Section 75.
- 3.24. Relevance and proportionality are core concepts for public authorities in ensuring they fulfil their duties, and the assessment methods recommended should assist in this.

⁴² [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), page 39.

4. Evidence of public authority practices

4.1. This chapter sets out evidence that the Commission has gathered from practices by public authorities and patterns identified. It considers how the central methods in Equality Schemes, those of screening and Equality Impact Assessment, are being used by public authorities. It also considers other processes that are set out in Equality Scheme arrangements and current practices.

Context

4.2. The Commission provides advice to public authorities in relation to their duties. The Commission's advice has focused on the requirements in Schedule 9, particularly that a public authority shall prepare and submit an Equality Scheme to the Commission.

4.3. Schedule 9 is clear about the purpose of the Equality Scheme – as it must set out the arrangements through which the public authority proposes to fulfil its statutory equality and good relations duties - and is prescriptive in what an Equality Scheme shall include⁴³.

4.4. The Commission's guidance throughout the time of public authorities having Equality Schemes has been in providing support and advice on what the requirements set out in Schedule 9 should be in practice. The Commission developed detailed advice at the outset in 1999 and has progressively considered its advice contained therein, developing and adapting the recommended methods accordingly.

4.5. The Commission's approach to advice and the recommendations it makes for Equality Scheme arrangements was looked at for the project on public authority practices in screening and EQIA in 2016⁴⁴. The report notes: "*the review has highlighted a number of occasions where public authorities have succeeded in mainstreaming s75 activity despite both difficult economic circumstances and a degree of frustration with some existing procedures and arrangements*".

4.6. The Commission recognises this point. For example, it provides common advice and guidance on the requirements set out in Schedule 9. That Schedule 9 applies to any public authority, regardless of its size or nature of its functions has been identified as an issue. The requirement is that a public authority has a framework for arrangements which it applies for relevant functions. This is a long standing issue, particularly for small public authorities and/or those with limited functions when they have been preparing or revising their Equality Schemes.

⁴³ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 4.

⁴⁴ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 21.

Assessment and consultation on the likely impact of policies

- 4.7. The processes contained within an equality scheme, which provide the cornerstone for enabling a public authority to have the required regard, are their arrangements for “*assessing and consulting on the likely impact of policies...*”⁴⁵. Other scheme arrangements provide for creating the circumstances within a public authorities for it to be able to fulfil its duties with respect to all relevant functions.
- 4.8. The Commission commissioned a review of practices in relation to screening and EQIA by public authorities⁴⁶. The report reflects both quantitative and qualitative analyses from a wide range of public authority practices and experiences. Its findings also reflect the Commission’s experience from the advice given to public authorities on screening and EQIA.
- 4.9. In the quantitative assessment of “screening”, the report shows that in the time period covered, information analysed for all 163 public authorities showed 73 authorities reported in their Annual Progress Report that they had carried out screening exercises, where 31 public authorities reported that they did not⁴⁷.
- 4.10. The finding that a number of public authorities reported no screening activity is a concern. The Section 75 duties are continuing duties and apply to relevant functions of a public authority; screening, as part of an assessment, should be central for a public authority to ensure it can fulfil its duties and provide evidence of this.
- 4.11. But this finding needs to be set into the context of the wider findings in the report, particularly:
- “Probably above all else the review has thrown into stark relief dramatic differences in the level of engagement with s75 across the Northern Ireland public sector, and in turn disparate interpretations of what s75 means for the day-to-day business of each organisation.”*⁴⁸
- 4.12. The report does, however, find there to be close adherence by public authorities to the Commission’s guidance on EQIAs, when they occur, and data being used in a meaningful way to inform decision making. EQIAs tend to be the preserve of larger organisations, but are spread across all sectors. They

⁴⁵ See: Conley, H., [A review of available information on the use of impact assessment in public policy formulation and in contributing to the fulfilment of statutory duties](#) (ECNI, 2016) – for a detailed consideration of the continuing use of equality impact assessment in the different devolved regions of Britain and its continuing role as evidence of giving the required regard when a public authority has been subject to judicial review.

⁴⁶ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016).

⁴⁷ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), chapter 3.

⁴⁸ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 19.

are noted as being used when the matter under consideration is contentious and/or politically sensitive⁴⁹. The report notes:

*“More generally, few EQIAs were of a minimalist type and many revealed considerable effort had been exerted to ensure a thorough assessment.”*⁵⁰

- 4.13. The report also illustrates the difficulties of presenting good practice examples where both the statutory requirements are determined by the particular circumstances in the public authority, and the practices in implementing common methods vary so widely:

“On the one hand, undoubtedly there is considerable evidence of good practice, underpinned by mechanisms and support systems which ensure that s75 considerations permeate policy development from an early stage of formulation through to implementation, monitoring and review. In these examples, screening and EQIAs are used routinely and systematically to ensure that fairness is afforded due regard as an integral part of policy development and implementation.

*On the other hand, there would appear to be examples of organisations that have singularly failed to buy-in to both the principles and the practice of s75, either applying screening in a perfunctory manner in the latter stages of policy development or choosing not to engage with s75 processes routinely.”*⁵¹

- 4.14. The report continues with the identification of a number of examples of good practice, noting that they have been identified throughout the sample of public authorities contributing to the project. They have been brought together as themes and presented with a caveat; there are few public authorities exhibiting all the factors identified⁵².

Issues identified in the timing of assessments and whether the Equality Scheme processes are considered needed at all.

- 4.15. The recent review of public authority practices⁵³, looked at how public authorities applied the templates developed by the Commission for the screening part of assessments. There is a particular issue about how public authorities view the template, the Commission’s advice on it and their use of it, which has also been identified as an issue.

- 4.16. The findings of the recent review of public authority practices also identified circumstances where public authorities were reporting that action had been taken at initial stages in the development of the policy, such as at the stage of

⁴⁹ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), pages 19-20.

⁵⁰ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 12.

⁵¹ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), pages 19-20.

⁵² Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), chapter 6.

⁵³ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 23.

setting objectives, to mitigate already known equality issues⁵⁴. This did not necessarily involve the use of the arrangements in their Equality Schemes.

4.17. The report also reflects a concern as to whether the policy, when the screening process had been used, or the template applied, “*had been genuinely scrutinised against the four screening questions*”⁵⁵.

4.18. The Commission has also noted practices where the public authority may have taken the view that it already has all the information required to fulfil the duties⁵⁶. This has been explained as circumstances:

- where public authorities consider that they have available to them within their authority the information on equality required for particular assessments; or
- their early engagement in the development of a policy or the policy options has enabled them to take the equality matters into consideration in the formulation of the proposals; or
- undertaking a consultation exercise does not provide any further information to aid their equality assessment of the policy under consideration.

4.19. A further practice has been noted of public authorities considering that an assessment is required **only** when a potential adverse impact has been identified, which is not consistent with the Commission’s advice. The review of public authority practices on screening and EQIA identified this point⁵⁷. This appears to suggest that public authorities are not applying their Equality Scheme arrangements in order to fulfil requirements to have “(due) regard”; the overarching duties are a positive consideration of the need to promote equality of opportunity and/or the desirability of promoting good relations.

4.20. The Commission has also noted a practice, evidenced from screening forms, that the policy under consideration is said to be relevant to the duties, but the policy purpose/goal will result in better outcomes for all, or the criteria being applied in the policy apply to all⁵⁸. This does not appear to conform with the

⁵⁴ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 27.

⁵⁵ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 23.

⁵⁶ This evidence is drawn from a number of sources, both in the evidence provided by Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, and/or from events the Commission has held with public authority Equality Officers.

⁵⁷ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page 9.

⁵⁸ For examples of this approach taken, see: Dugdale, P. and Pidgeon, C., [In year monitoring of public expenditure: an analysis of departmental bid documentation](#) (Northern Ireland Assembly, 2014), in particular sections 1.3.3 and 2.23.

principles, in that an adequate inquiry of the equality matters is needed in order to fulfil the duties to pay the required regard⁵⁹.

- 4.21. Further, a number of public authorities have conducted policy consultation exercises where the policy proposals are set out, but only the “screening” questions are presented within the document. These consultations provide no analysis, nor the authority’s equality assessment of the policy in question.
- 4.22. There are risks for public authorities in these practices, in particular that those in the authority will not be able to give the appropriate consideration to “the need to promote equality of opportunity” and/or “desirability of promoting good relations” when it comes to take decisions on the policy in question. Public authorities also risk not being able to evidence their assessment of the potential impacts of that policy.

Availability of relevant data and the use of data

- 4.23. Data and evidence of how policies operate should be central to an assessment of potential impacts. Public authorities are required to have certain monitoring arrangements in their Equality Schemes.
- 4.24. The Commission provides advice and guidance for public authorities on the monitoring and data collection elements of Equality Scheme requirements. Again, this advice covers not only what Schedule 9 sets out for public authorities, but also practical guidance that is designed to encourage and assist a public authority to use data collection and monitoring to inform its policies, practices and procedures.
- 4.25. The use of data for equality assessments has varied, and this has been identified as an issue of concern. The particular issues noted have been in relation to screening, as this forms the main activity on assessments⁶⁰. The pattern in the presentation of general demographic data in screening templates has been noted from the Commission’s advice, which is not consistent with our guidance, which says that the data should be linked to the purpose of the policy or matter under consideration⁶¹. The recent review provides evidence to support this observation, noting that public authorities identified a number of contributory factors which inhibit data development, such as the resources required for data collection in an environment where resources have been significantly reduced⁶².
- 4.26. This issue was also raised when the Commission considered its advice on Equality Scheme consultation arrangements. Stakeholders also raised other

⁵⁹ For a detailed discussion and examples of a public authority’s understanding of the relevance of equality in the context of fulfilling a duty to have “due regard”, see: Hooper, J., [The role of Impact Assessment in effective decision making: Learning from recent Judicial Reviews](#) (Devon County Council, 2013), in particular pages 13 and 14.

⁶⁰ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), chapter 3.

⁶¹ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010).

⁶² Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), section 6.4.

matters that were considered neglected in the implementation of Equality Scheme arrangements. One specific area was that of data development to enable understanding of how policies operated and raising concerns that public authorities were not, over the course of the duties having effect, routinely collecting and using that data for further policy development work⁶³.

Arrangements for consultation

- 4.27. Schedule 9 sets out specifically that a public authority will include arrangements for consultation in its Equality Scheme, and a number of circumstances where consultation shall happen. For example, a public authority must consult on its Equality Scheme before submitting it to the Commission. Schedule 9 also stipulates that the equality scheme shall state the authority's arrangements "... for consulting on matters to which a duty under that section is likely to be relevant..."⁶⁴; and "for assessing and consulting on the likely impact of policies..."⁶⁵. However, it should be noted that all the arrangements in an Equality Scheme, including any consultation, are for the purposes of enabling a public authorities to fulfil its statutory equality and good relations duties.
- 4.28. The Schedule further sets out that there will be a consultation list contained within the Equality Scheme⁶⁶.
- 4.29. These arrangements have been a matter of significant interest over the years. For example, following the *Keeping it Effective* Report in 2008, the Commission sought to reconcile the Schedule 9 requirement that an Equality Scheme must contain details of persons to be consulted, with the practical implications of maintaining such a list, when it was developing the revised Guide⁶⁷.
- 4.30. The Commission's guidance on the consultation arrangements for an Equality Scheme takes into account wider consultation practices and public policy requirements for consultation. There have been a number of changes to this wider context, in particular a Supreme Court ruling on consultation requirements generally and the changes to public policy consultation practices in Northern Ireland following the Stormont House Agreement⁶⁸. Given these, and that the Commission's Guide includes principles which were drawn from Cabinet Office guidance on consultation which has now been superseded, the Commission gave specific consideration to its advice on consultation

⁶³ [Proposals to amend the Commission's advice to public authorities on: Timescales for consulting on matters relevant to the statutory equality and good relations duties – Consultation Report](#) (ECNI, 2016).

⁶⁴ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 4(2)(a).

⁶⁵ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 4(2)(b).

⁶⁶ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 4(2)(a).

⁶⁷ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), pages 40-44.

⁶⁸ [Proposals to amend the Commission's advice to public authorities on: Timescales for consulting on matters relevant to the statutory equality and good relations duties – Consultation Report](#) (ECNI, 2016), Section 3.

arrangements in Equality Schemes in 2016. The Commission concluded the consultation by not changing its advice, as an interim measure⁶⁹.

4.31. However, through the consultation exercise, it was clear that the Equality Scheme consultation arrangements are seen to confer a wider duty to consult than for the purposes of fulfilling a public authority's statutory equality and good relations duties⁷⁰.

4.32. In the context of the evidence of public authority practices, this raises an issue about the understanding of what the duties require, and also what the Equality Schemes provide for.

Evidence of Equality Scheme practices for fulfilling the duty to have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations (Section 75 (2))

4.33. The Section 75 statutory duties require that a public authority must have due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity, while it must also have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations.

4.34. The term due regard was intended to be, and is, stronger than regard, but in either case an authority is required by the statute to take the specified matters into account and give them the required weight when carrying out its functions relating to Northern Ireland⁷¹.

4.35. There is a difference in the way Schedule 9 sets out how the public authority will set out in its Equality Scheme how it will fulfil the separate and distinct duties in Sections 75 (1) and (2). The key arrangements required for assessing and consulting on the likely impact of policies is directed, in the Schedule, to the "need to promote equality of opportunity" alone.

4.36. The Commission conducted events with public authorities specifically and found little appetite for further guidance on Section 75 (2); "good relations" was seen to be of relevance only when particular issues arose and a framework for action on an issue needed⁷². The understanding of "good relations", and therefore its definition, varied widely too.

4.37. The implementation of Equality Schemes for the purposes of fulfilling the duty under Section 75 (2) was considered further in the recent review of public authority practices in screening and EQIA. This found a low level of activity

⁶⁹ [Proposals to amend the Commission's advice to public authorities on: Timescales for consulting on matters relevant to the statutory equality and good relations duties – Consultation Report](#) (ECNI, 2016).

⁷⁰ [Proposals to amend the Commission's advice to public authorities on: Timescales for consulting on matters relevant to the statutory equality and good relations duties – Consultation Report](#) (ECNI, 2016).

⁷¹ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010).

⁷² The Commission's business plan in 2014-15 included actions to consider a number of good relations matters in the expectation of an enhanced Equality and Good Relations Commission as set out in the Executive's Together: Building a United Community Strategy

generally on good relations and sets out similar issues for public authorities to those identified by the Commission⁷³.

- 4.38. In the period since the publication of the Commission's Guide in 2010, some concerns have been raised about the Commission's approach to advising public authorities on their duties for Section 75 (2) specifically⁷⁴; albeit the Commission disagreed with the conclusions reached⁷⁵.
- 4.39. More recently, those raising concerns about how public authorities should fulfil their duty in Section 75 (2) have focused on the Commission's advice to public authorities on the Equality Scheme arrangements for this⁷⁶, as well as engaging with public authorities directly on those arrangements when the Equality Scheme is being drafted.
- 4.40. The evidence points to low levels of activity relating to the good relations duty for public authorities generally and that, in many instances, it is not seen as relevant.
- 4.41. This section does however, link to the wider issue of whether the Equality Scheme arrangements are seen as, and used for, helping the public authority to ensure it gives the appropriate regard to those statutory goals set out in Section 75, and the regard that is appropriate in the circumstances.

⁷³ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), section 6.6.

⁷⁴ [Unequal Relations](#) (Committee on the Administration of Justice, 2013).

⁷⁵ [Speech to CAJ Conference on 11 June 2013](#).

⁷⁶ [CAJ's submission to the 11 new District Councils in relation to draft Equality Schemes](#) (Committee on the Administration of Justice, 2014).

Summary points drawn from this chapter

- 4.42. The Equality Scheme does not appear to be seen as the vehicle for enabling the authority to pay the appropriate “regard” as a continuing statutory requirement. This is suggested in the evidence of public authority practices in screening and EQIA particularly.
- 4.43. Through the detailed consideration of the evidence of public authority practices, it is clear that, while there are some frustrations expressed about the Commission’s advice and perceptions of a lack of flexibility in the approach, there appear to be a number of other factors that are also of concern. The practices are varied, with areas where there are clear gaps in assessment processes for some public authorities, there are real risks identified that public authorities may not be implementing their Equality Schemes in a way that enables them to demonstrate and be accountable in fulfilling their statutory equality and good relations duties.
- 4.44. The monitoring requirements set out in Schedule 9, and data collection to inform equality assessments, have not driven a data development agenda for public authorities in recent times. There are a number of reasons found for this, not least that this appears not to be seen as a high priority in an environment of reducing resources.

5. Mainstreaming and action measures

5.1. This chapter looks at a number of ways that the implementation of the statutory equality and good relations duties can be described, and how they should link more widely to the effective development and delivery of public services. It is set in the context where outcomes are now being considered throughout the public sector. It also considers progress on the Commission's recommendation in its revised Guide⁷⁷ that public authorities develop action plans/action measures.

Context

5.2. The Commission concluded in 2008 that public authorities' focus, in relation to the implementation of the Section 75 duties, should shift from the processes contained within an Equality Scheme towards impacts and better outcomes⁷⁸.

5.3. The Commission's Effectiveness Review in 2008 addressed mainstreaming specifically⁷⁹ as "*Section 75 makes equality of opportunity central to public policy decision making. It must be an essential consideration in policy development, implementation, monitoring and review. ... Section 75 has transformed the policy making process, making it more inclusive, more evidence-based and as a result, more informed*".⁸⁰

5.4. The Commission gave effect to this through its advice in its revised Guide in 2010; re-confirming the importance of mainstreaming as the approach that embeds equality and good relations centrally in the whole range of public policy decision-making⁸¹, with the tools of screening and Equality Impact Assessment.

5.5. The Commission also recommended that public authorities commit to developing action plans or action measures as part of their Equality Scheme arrangements⁸². These plans run alongside Equality Schemes – they are not specific requirements for a scheme.

5.6. During the development of successive Programmes for Government, there has been an increasing focus on outcomes. This culminated in the adoption by the Executive of the Outcomes Based Accountability/Results Based Accountability⁸³ methodology for the draft Programme for Government in 2016.

⁷⁷ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010).

⁷⁸ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 5. See also the recommendations from [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008).

⁷⁹ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), chapter 4.

⁸⁰ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008), page 36.

⁸¹ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 8.

⁸² [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 36.

⁸³ Friedman, M, *Trying Hard is Not Good Enough* (PARSE Publishing, 2015).

5.7. Given the adoption and development of similar outcomes approaches in other jurisdictions, particularly in Scotland where there are also the equivalent statutory equality and good relations duties on public authorities, the Commission commissioned a discussion paper that looks at key factors that contribute to better equality outcomes⁸⁴.

Commission recommendation that public authorities develop action plans/action measures

5.8. The Commission's Guide⁸⁵ recommends that public authorities have arrangements, in relation to assessing their own compliance with the duties, to develop action plans/action measures. The plans/measures themselves do not form part of the approved Equality Scheme.

5.9. The revised Equality Schemes, submitted by public authorities and approved by the Commission in the period of its recent strategy⁸⁶ to request these, included these arrangements. The Equality Schemes submitted at that time and since have included either the commitment that the public authority would develop an action plan or contained a plan in an appendix or as a separate document.

5.10. There was a high level of acceptance of this recommendation; all public authorities made this commitment.

5.11. The Commission recommended that public authorities report progress towards the outcomes identified in their plans in their annual reporting on progress with the Section 75 duties. These reports are generally published by public authorities, as well as being submitted to the Equality Commission.

5.12. In a recent review of action plans, the high level of initial activity in developing the action plans was noted, but the evidence shows a lower level of activity in their maintenance and renewal. Of the 86 public authorities sampled, only 28% had action plans covering 2017 and beyond⁸⁷.

5.13. While the report findings show a wide variation in the practices of public authorities in relation to their action plans, it concludes that the framework continues to provide "*the best example of reflexive and responsive legislation and of statutory equality mainstreaming.*"⁸⁸

5.14. The researchers who undertook the review recognised the work of equality officers but also acknowledged the role of both political and organisational

⁸⁴ MacMillan, K., [Discussion Paper: Key factors that contribute to better equality outcomes](#) (ECNI, 2017).

⁸⁵ MacMillan, K., [Discussion Paper: Key factors that contribute to better equality outcomes](#) (ECNI, 2017), page 40.

⁸⁶ During the period 2011-2013.

⁸⁷ Conley, H. and Warren, S., [A Review of Action Plans developed by public authorities in relation to their statutory equality and good relations duties](#) (ECNI, 2017), page 14.

⁸⁸ Conley, H. and Warren, S., [A Review of Action Plans developed by public authorities in relation to their statutory equality and good relations duties](#) (ECNI, 2017), page 30.

leadership in ensuring success. They identified a number of factors contributing to current practices, not least the level of priority currently being given to equality in some organisations, as well as the continuing restrictions in resources. The report concludes:

“... s.75 remains influential on public authorities but the difficult political and economic context has discouraged critical self-reflection in public authorities that is key to the success of the legislation.”⁸⁹

5.15. The report’s recommendations reflects that many of the actions contained within the action plans were process, rather than outcome, orientated:

“Extending process based action measures: Public authorities tend to develop process based action measures that are designed to initiate new or enhance existing internal systems (e.g. monitoring data, collecting data, reviewing policy, setting up working parties).”⁹⁰

5.16. The findings in this report suggest that the action plans/action measures are being treated as processes, and that the recommendations by the Commission have not driven a focus on outcomes in the action measures developed by public authorities as intended.

Mainstreaming and evidence of other public authority practices

5.17. Some public authorities have suggested that if mainstreaming is successful, the subject of that mainstreaming should no longer be visible. However, the Commission’s Guide notes that questions of equality and good relations may easily become sidelined in organisations⁹¹. Also, what is required from a public authority, to have the required regard to the statutory goals set out in Section 75, ensures transparency and accountability⁹².

5.18. Experience to date of public authority practices in mainstreaming suggest that these practices span a broad spectrum. As is noted by the Policy Arc/Kremer report, *“there is clearly a continuing motivation among many representatives [amongst the public authority equality officers] to work with s75 processes in order to improve policies and to mainstream equality of opportunity and good relations and this commitment provides a sound foundation for the future”⁹³*. But there are also clear differences in interpretation of the requirements and implementation of practices.

⁸⁹ Conley, H. and Warren, S., [A Review of Action Plans developed by public authorities in relation to their statutory equality and good relations duties](#) (ECNI, 2017), page 5.

⁹⁰ Conley, H. and Warren, S., [A Review of Action Plans developed by public authorities in relation to their statutory equality and good relations duties](#) (ECNI, 2017), page 31.

⁹¹ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 8.

⁹² See paragraph 3.12 above (the Brown principles).

⁹³ Policy Arc Ltd and Kremer Consultancy Services Ltd, [Section 75 - Screening and Equality Impact Assessment: A Review of Recent Practice](#) (ECNI, 2016), page v.

Evidence from public authority annual progress reports

5.19. Public authorities report their own progress with the duties and equality schemes, which is the implementation of their arrangements for assessing their compliance.

5.20. The Equality Commission provides public authorities with a template they can use for their progress.

5.21. For the 2014-15 business year, the following information was recorded from these reports⁹⁴. This illustrates that half of public authorities are of the view that, due to their equality and good relations considerations, changes have occurred:

“Section 1: Equality and good relations outcomes, impacts and good practice

Question: Has the application of the equality scheme commitments resulted in any changes to policy, practice, procedures and/or service delivery areas?

*50% (N=61) of public authorities reported that the application of equality scheme commitments had resulted in **changes** to policy, practice, procedures and/or service delivery areas;*

45% (N=54) reported that it had led to no changes; and

5% (N=6) reported that the question was not applicable.

Question: if yes to question above, what aspect of the equality scheme prompted or led to the change(s)?

*36% (N=22 of 61) reported that the aspect of the equality scheme leading to change was a result of **changes to access to information and services**;*

*34% (N=21 of 61) reported that it was as a result of the organisation’s **screening of a policy**;*

*26% (N=16 of 61) reported that it was as a result of analysis from **monitoring impact**;*

*37% (N=23 of 61) cited **‘other’ reasons**; and*

*25% (N=15 of 61) reported that it was as a result of what was identified through the **EQIA and consultation exercise**.”*

⁹⁴ *Public Authority Section 75 Equality Duties Summary of Annual Progress Reports 2014-15*, ECNI, 2016. This is the first year when the template provided to public authorities, to facilitate their commitments to report on their progress annually, used this format.

Summary points drawn from this chapter

- 5.22. This chapter looked at action plans/measures specifically and found there are wide variations in practices⁹⁵ and, while there are some places where the development of action plans has provided a focus on the outcomes, they have been found more often to focus on processes.
- 5.23. The evidence also identifies a range of factors contributing to public authority practices. In the wider context, where there is a current focus in public policy development to be outcomes focused, there is an opportunity to ensure that these outcomes, where relevant, take into account the need to promote equality of opportunity and desirability of promoting good relations.

⁹⁵ Conley, H. and Warren, S., [*A Review of Action Plans developed by public authorities in relation to their statutory equality and good relations duties*](#) (ECNI, 2017), page 14.

6. Public sector equality duties in Britain and the Republic of Ireland

6.1. This chapter briefly sets out how equivalent statutory duties in other jurisdictions have developed. It identifies common duties where a public authority must have “(due) regard”, and specific duties on a subset of public authorities. It also considers what is required of other Commissions, where there are statutory equality and good relations duties on public authorities, and makes links to Northern Ireland where appropriate.

Context

- 6.2. Where Northern Ireland established the duties and associated enforcement mechanisms in 1998, similar duties in the Race Relations Act 1976 in Britain were expanded and enhanced with enforcement powers in 2000⁹⁶.
- 6.3. It is equally important to reflect the evidence that suggests such statutory “**due regard**” duties and equivalents continue to be used to achieve particular public policy goals. They are used in legislation for equality goals in public services and the delivery of public functions, as evidenced in a recent report that assessed such duties from sixteen jurisdictions, published by Equinet - the European Network of Equality Bodies⁹⁷.
- 6.4. In Scotland, in addition to the Public Sector Equality Duties (PSEDs) on public authorities⁹⁸, the Scottish Government recently legislated for a statutory equality duty in education, which requires specific organisations to have “**due regard** to the need to exercise the powers ...in a way designed to reduce inequalities of outcome...” for the pupils experiencing inequalities of outcome⁹⁹.
- 6.5. The Republic of Ireland established similar duties to those in Section 75 on public bodies in 2014. A public body must, “in the performance of its functions, **have regard to** the need to... eliminate discrimination, promote equality of opportunity and treatment of its staff and the persons to whom it provides services”, as well as protect human rights¹⁰⁰.

⁹⁶ [The Race Relations \(Amendment\) Act 2000](#)

⁹⁷ Crowley, N., *Making Europe more Equal: A Legal Duty?* (Equinet, 2016), see in particular the assessment of Mainstreaming Duties in Section 3.3, page 29.

⁹⁸ There are broadly equivalent duties to those in Section 75 on public authorities in England, Wales and Scotland which are set out in Section 149 of the [Equality Act 2010](#).

⁹⁹ [Education \(Scotland\) Act 2016, Part 1, Section 1.](#)

¹⁰⁰ [Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission Act 2014](#), Section 42.

Requirements on public authorities in other jurisdictions

- 6.6. The statutory equality and good relations duties in Britain were extended in 2010 to other grounds covered in the anti-discrimination legislation, when the Equality Act 2010 came into effect. The current duties on public authorities in Britain are set out in Section 149 (see Appendix 1).
- 6.7. Section 42 of the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission Act 2014 establishes a statutory equality duty for public bodies in the Republic of Ireland which is similar in formulation to those in the UK (see Appendix 1).
- 6.8. The approach for equivalent duties, whether in Britain or the Republic of Ireland, differs both in the public authorities they apply to and how they apply. In Britain, there is a common set of duties - to have due regard - for a list of public authorities which is set out in Section 149 of the Equality Act 2010. There are then “specific duties” (set out in subordinate legislation) applying to a much more limited number of, and generally larger, public authorities.
- 6.9. The requirement set out in specific duties in Britain vary according to the devolved region in which the public authority operates. For example, in Wales there is still a requirement on public authorities to produce an equality scheme¹⁰¹. In Scotland there are very specific requirements on not only the public authorities but also Scottish Ministers to address outcomes¹⁰².
- 6.10. Recently the UK Government’s commitments on gender pay gap reporting were given effect for public bodies through amendments to the specific duty regulations under Section 149 of the Equality Act 2010¹⁰³.
- 6.11. There are no reviews currently available from Britain to provide evidence of the effect of these changes or their impact on public authority practices in fulfilling their duties.
- 6.12. However, the principles established from caselaw continue to apply in Britain, and public authorities can be subject to challenge in relation to their fulfilling of their statutory equality and good relations duties¹⁰⁴. While the specific duties to produce a scheme or undertake the particular process of impact assessment have been removed in England, the practice of impact assessment remains a

¹⁰¹ See: Conley, H., [A review of available information on the use of impact assessment in public policy formulation and in contributing to the fulfilment of statutory duties](#) (ECNI, 2016) – for a list of the different sources of the specific duties.

¹⁰² MacMillan, K., [Discussion Paper: Key factors that contribute to better equality outcomes](#) (ECNI, 2017).

¹⁰³ [The Equality Act 2010 \(Specific Duties and Public Authorities\) Regulations 2017](#), SI 353

¹⁰⁴ Conley, H., [A review of available information on the use of impact assessment in public policy formulation and in contributing to the fulfilment of statutory duties](#) (ECNI, 2016).

key process for a public authority to evidence how it has paid the required “regard”¹⁰⁵

6.13. There are examples of good practice that have arisen from this: one County Council developed extensive guidance following its experience of judicial review challenges on several occasions¹⁰⁶.

Enforcement of equivalent Public Sector Equality Duties

6.14. The Commission looked at what is provided for in law for the equivalent equality bodies in relation to enforcement of the public sector equality duties in Britain and the Republic of Ireland.

The Equality and Human Rights Commission

6.15. The Equality and Human Rights Commission (EHRC) in Britain has enforcement powers set out in the Equality Act 2006, and amended by the Equality Act 2010, which provide the Commission with a power to assess the extent of compliance by a public authority with the general duty. The Commission also has a wide ranging power of inquiry, and can conduct inquiries into a number of areas under the section entitled equality and diversity, as well as investigation powers (see Appendix one).

6.16. The EHRC can issue a compliance notice where it thinks that an authority has failed to comply with a duty under section 149¹⁰⁷.

6.17. It should be noted that these statutory powers enable the EHRC to assess compliance by a public authority with its duty to have “due regard”; their powers are not set with reference to the “specific duties”.

Enforcement powers in relation to the Public Sector Duties for the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission

6.18. There are powers and duties set out for the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission¹⁰⁸ which provide scope for a review if there is evidence of a failure by a public body to comply with the overall duties to pay regard (see Appendix one).

¹⁰⁵ Conley, H., [A review of available information on the use of impact assessment in public policy formulation and in contributing to the fulfilment of statutory duties](#) (ECNI, 2016).

¹⁰⁶ For a detailed discussion and examples of a public authority’s understanding of the relevance of equality in the context of fulfilling a duty to have “due regard”, see: Hooper, J., [The role of Impact Assessment in effective decision making: Learning from recent Judicial Reviews](#) (Devon County Council, 2013) – in particular pages 13 and 14.

¹⁰⁷ [Equality Act 2006](#), Section 32.

¹⁰⁸ [Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission Act 2014](#), Section 42(5).

Summary points drawn from this chapter

- 6.19. Equivalent duties for public authorities to pay (due) regard to statutory equality goals continue to be legal requirements in Britain and have recently been established for the Republic of Ireland.
- 6.20. The specific requirements on a number of public authorities (specific duties) vary between the devolved regions in Britain and these requirements have changed and developed over time. They are set through secondary legislation; they are not set out in the primary legislation of the Equality Act 2010.
- 6.21. The enforcement of the duties in other jurisdictions is also different from Northern Ireland, particularly in the statutory role for the respective Commissions.
- 6.22. The statutory equality and good relations duties operating in the UK are subject to administrative law standards in the respective jurisdictions.

7. The Commission's role to consider complaints and investigate

7.1. This chapter covers the Commission's specific powers and duties in Schedule 9 on complaints and investigations. It sets out a number of issues that have been identified through the Commission's use of these powers. It also identifies differences in legislative powers available to the different Commissions in the UK and Republic of Ireland for their respective duties.

Context

7.2. Schedule 9 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 as a whole is entitled enforcement¹⁰⁹. The Schedule sets out duties for the Commission and what is required of public authorities. It also sets out accountability processes through complaints (Paragraph 10) and investigations (Paragraph 11).

7.3. Individual complaints can be made to the public authority about a failure to comply with its approved Equality Scheme. These complaints can subsequently be brought to the Commission, which must investigate or give reasons for not investigating. The Commission can also undertake an investigation where it believes that a public authority has failed to comply with its approved Equality Scheme. The Commission has procedures that govern the operation of these functions¹¹⁰.

7.4. As a result of an investigation:

- the Commission can make recommendations to the public authority, in the context of how it should comply with its approved Equality Scheme;
- copies of the investigation report are issued to specific bodies/people, such as the Secretary of State and the Assembly, as well as the relevant parties to the complaint/investigation; and
- there could be a referral to the Secretary of State if action is not taken on the recommendations made to the public authority within a reasonable time.

7.5. There has been an increasing interest in the use of complaints and investigations from advocacy groups and non-governmental organisations¹¹¹. The Commission receives correspondence from a range of sources, and on a

¹⁰⁹ "Schedule 9 Equality: Enforcement of Duties"

¹¹⁰ [Investigation procedure under paragraphs 10 and 11 of Schedule 9 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998](#) (ECNI, 2014).

¹¹¹ See, for example: http://www.equalitycoalition.net/?page_id=28 (accessed: 02/08/17)

number of issues, in any year containing requests for an investigation of the concerns raised.

- 7.6. The Commission dealt with 25 enquiries by providing advice on the complaints process available under Paragraph 10 in the 2015-16 business year. Four written complaints were received in that year.
- 7.7. The Commission had undertaken 27 investigations since 2004 at the time it considered this evidence; 18 of them arose from written complaints from individuals (Paragraph 10), nine were investigations arising from the Commission's belief of non-compliance. In the 2015-16 business year, the Commission was undertaking 3 investigations.
- 7.8. It has been of note that where a complaint has been received under Paragraph 10, the issue of concern to the complainant has tended to relate to a policy or practice in the public authority. The complaints and investigations mechanisms as set out in Schedules 9 relate to where there is a belief that a public authority has failed to comply with its approved equality scheme, which is largely about process.

Public authorities' reported activity on complaints

- 7.9. Public authorities are prompted, in the template, to report on the numbers of complaints they receive in any year when they report their progress on implementing their Equality Schemes annually. Progress reporting is self-reporting by the public authority.
- 7.10. The number of complaints reported on an annual basis has been routinely low. To illustrate this, the number recorded across all public authorities who submitted a progress report to the Commission for the business year 2014-15 was 21 complaints. The details provided also illustrate that the issues raised and considered in the context of the Equality Scheme complaints mechanism are wide. In some cases it is not clear how the issues raised directly relate to how the Equality Scheme and its arrangements have been implemented. For example:
 - one authority reported a case of potential harassment as a complaint it received on its Equality Scheme;
 - two reported complaints related to the use of accessible parking bays by non-disabled people in one authority's car parks;
 - one public authority recorded one complaint which was then described as 300 "template" complaints about one issue; they were considered resolved through the organisation's internal complaints mechanism;
 - one public authority reported a case relating to an Equality Commission complainant under the anti-discrimination legislation;

- two reported complaints related to matters which were subsequently brought to the Commission by individuals under Paragraph 10 of Schedule 9.

The different enforcement frameworks for Commissions in the UK and Republic of Ireland

7.11. The comparable duties through the three jurisdictions are similarly framed: the statutory duties are on the public authorities, these are mainstreaming duties to ensure equality and related matters are considered throughout an organisation's functions.

7.12. In all cases, the legislation sets out a framework for enforcement, but does not prescribe how respective Commissions should interpret and implement its powers and duties, nor how they should be most effectively deployed.

7.13. Neither the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission (IHREC) nor the Equality and Human Rights Commission (EHRC) in Britain have specific functions set out in the legislation in relation to individual complainants, in the same way as Paragraph 10 of Schedule 9.

7.14. The Commission's powers to investigate are in circumstances where it can form a belief that a public authority has not complied with its approved Equality Scheme¹¹². In practice, this has resulted in an investigation of a very particular issue of concern, the specific circumstances of that issue, and the specific circumstances of one public authority.

7.15. As a result, while the findings and recommendations from an investigation will provide some learning for public authority practices, the ripple effect can be limited beyond the public authority that has been subject to the investigation.

7.16. All three Commissions (the Equality Commission, IHREC and EHRC) have investigation/inquiry or review powers. Neither the IHREC nor the EHRC appears to have to identify where it "believes that a public authority may have failed to comply with a scheme" in order to intervene using its enforcement powers, albeit this option is not expressly precluded.

¹¹² Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 11.

Summary points from this chapter

- 7.17. The provision of powers and duties for the Equality Commission in relation to complaints and investigations are set out in Schedule 9. There have been relatively few complaints made to both public authorities and the Commission where there may be a failure by a public authority to comply with its Equality Scheme.
- 7.18. The matters raised in complaints on which the Commission advises, the evidence of the complaints reported by public authorities, and those matters the Commission considers for further investigation are generally a concern about a public authority's policies or practices. There is not necessarily a clear link to particular commitment in an equality scheme.
- 7.19. There is experience within all the Commissions identified of a range of powers and duties for enforcement, such as investigation and/or inquiry. The provisions of Schedule 9 for the Equality Commission have resulted in a range of investigations, and they have been on specific issues with one public authority at any one time.

8. Issues and opportunities identified

8.1. This chapter sets out a number of issues identified from our review of the evidence and patterns of practices by public authorities. It sets them out as the fundamental issues that the Commission has agreed need to be addressed by public authorities as a matter of priority. Through the course of gathering and examining the evidence, the Commission has also identified a number of opportunities going forward, which have contributed to the identification of the agreed issues.

Context

8.2. The preceding chapters set out the evidence that the Commission has considered during the course of the 2016-17 business year. The evidence has presented a picture of how the duties are being implemented.

8.3. This picture has been drawn from detailed consideration of the evidence gathered; the Commission's understanding, from experience in advising public authorities and others; the Commission's understanding of the wider political and economic context for public services in Northern Ireland; and other sources such as from the use of our investigation powers. A number of reviews commissioned during the period; analysis of other research and relevant sources that are referenced in this report, as well as stakeholder engagement, have also contributed. The Commission consulted on this report in 2017 and the responses received have been considered and incorporated, as appropriate.

8.4. As a result of examining public authority practices, the Commission is concerned about the effective implementation of the Section 75 duties by public authorities.

8.5. The Commission has identified a number of issues from this, which it believes are fundamental to the effective implementation of the duties by public authorities.

8.6. The Commission also considers that there are clear opportunities to further support, enable and advise public authorities in their fulfilment of their statutory equality and good relations duties.

Issues identified in public authorities' implementation of the Section 75 duties

8.7. **Leadership.** While recognising the circumstances of reduced resources, leadership continues to be imperative within public authorities to ensure the maintained focus on equality matters, as well as ensuring good governance and the mainstreaming of equality considerations throughout the business of the authority.

- 8.8. This has been evidenced through the Commission’s advisory work and the reviews of practices set out in this report. The Commission’s public policy positions recognise leadership as a key success factor in securing greater equality of opportunity¹¹³, as well as good relations.
- 8.9. In Scotland, there has been a coherence in political leadership and sustained commitments to address equality matters centrally in the National Outcomes Framework, in successive Programmes for Government, the legislative programme, and within assessment and reporting frameworks¹¹⁴, including high level programmes such as the budget¹¹⁵.
- 8.10. **Ownership.** The evidence, and our experience in advice, suggests that public authorities do not, in all instances, see the purpose of having an Equality Scheme as assisting in fulfilling their statutory equality and good relations duties.
- 8.11. This issue has been drawn from evidence particularly in the implementation of the main processes in Equality Schemes, as set out in Chapter 4, as well as the Commission’s advice in confirming what is required to fulfil a “due regard” duty.
- 8.12. **Understanding and/or misinterpreting the purpose and scope of the duties.** The evidence clearly suggests that Equality Schemes continue to be seen by public authorities as processes in themselves; they are not seen as contributing equality of opportunity and good relations considerations to decision making.
- 8.13. The evidence also suggests there are different understandings of, or expectations of, what is required in fulfilling the duties (i.e. to have “due regard/regard to...”) amongst different stakeholders.
- 8.14. **Definitions of key terms and expectations.** It remains the case, reflected in the evidence of practice, that there is an issue in the continuing differences among stakeholders in what is understood by the terms “equality of opportunity” and “good relations”.
- 8.15. Within the wider context, particularly in the current political environment, the understanding and use of the terms “equality” and “good relations” differ. There is particular evidence presented of practices relating to good relations and how this is being shaped by understandings and expectations of good relations.

¹¹³ See, for example, the [Commission’s submissions](#) to consultation exercises in order to secure the equality principle in the Code of Conduct for District Councillors.

¹¹⁴ MacMillan, K., [Discussion Paper: Key factors that contribute to better equality outcomes](#) (ECNI, 2017).

¹¹⁵ [Equality Statement: Scottish Draft Budget 2017-18](#) (Scottish Government, 2016).

- 8.16. But the wider understanding of what the Section 75 duties provide for also remains an issue, as evidenced in the understanding of how consultation arrangements in the Equality Schemes apply (see Chapter 4), given what is clearly established for what is required to pay “due regard” (see Chapter 3).
- 8.17. **Transparency and accountability.** The evidence suggests that some public authority practices have moved away from engagement and consultation informing their equality assessments, limiting opportunities for stakeholder involvement in decision making through use of the Equality Scheme processes. In addition, public authorities present limited information in their equality assessments when using screening templates.
- 8.18. Chapter 4 considers evidence from public authorities where Equality Officers have reported on the perception that there are limited contributions to policy development from applying the Equality Scheme processes, but also that the knowledge and experience of equality matters continues to be held, for a range of reasons, by those Equality Officers.
- 8.19. **Data development.** Equality Scheme commitments have not driven a data development agenda in the public sector, despite the requirements in Schedule 9 for particular monitoring arrangements and the Commission’s longstanding advice (see Chapter 4).
- 8.20. Evidence-based policy making is not a recent development; nor is advice on how to collect information to inform service development and the benefits of this.
- 8.21. **Accountability and risk.** Evidence suggests that the perceived risks of not fulfilling the statutory equality and good relations duties, and/or non-compliance, are probably small.
- 8.22. In public authorities where the duties are of higher relevance to the functions, it is likely that the risks of non-compliance are considered relatively low; it is likely to be quantified in relation to the risk of a Commission investigation. It has been less likely to be considered a risk in public law, although a number of cases have been heard recently in Judicial Review where the public authority’s fulfilment of its Section 75 duties has been considered.
- 8.23. In the annual progress reports, there is a small number of complaints reported by public authorities.

Issues identified in the Commission's powers and duties in Schedule 9

8.24. **Complaints.** There are specific requirements on the Commission in relation to complaints. The range and nature of complaints to the Commission has consistently reflected particular issues on policies and practices that are of concern to the complainant, which are not always clearly associated with what Equality Scheme arrangements provide for.

8.25. **Investigations** are adversarial, given the statutory requirement that they are considered in relation to a belief of non-compliance with an Equality Scheme. They have mostly been driven by particular circumstances. They have provided some learning for public authority practices, but can be limited in the ripple effect of the findings, particularly when arising from a paragraph 10 complaint.

Opportunities

8.26. There is ongoing interest in the circumstances and context in Northern Ireland, particularly given the 20th anniversary of the signing of the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement in April 2018.

8.27. The Commission will continue to provide advice and information on the statutory equality and good relations duties, and fulfil its functions as set out in Schedule 9.

9. Conclusions, recommendations and proposed actions

- 9.1. The Commission has a considerable body of evidence available on the operation of the Schedule 9 requirements of the Northern Ireland Act 1998. The Schedule 9 requirements are there to enable public authorities to fulfil their statutory equality and good relations duties set out in Section 75, and to enable enforcement of those duties.
- 9.2. The Commission has a duty in Schedule 9 of the Act to “to keep under review the effectiveness of the duties imposed by Section 75”¹¹⁶. The Commission does this in a number of ways, through its continuing work to provide advice and guidance, as well as through specific review activities, such as the strategic review of the effectiveness of the Section 75 duties it undertook in 2006-8¹¹⁷.
- 9.3. The work to examine evidence of public authority practices arose from the Commission’s advisory role. This report has brought together evidence of public authorities’ practices on their statutory equality and good relations duties, and wider evidence such as the issues and evidence from complaints. It has also enabled some examination of the wider circumstances and from other relevant jurisdictions, particularly Britain and the Republic of Ireland.
- 9.4. The Commission agreed that the collection and consideration of evidence, the issues identified, and the opportunities currently available, allow for this report to “*provide strategic direction for the Commission’s future focus on the statutory equality and good relations duties on public authorities in Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998*”¹¹⁸.
- 9.5. The Commission agreed to consolidate the evidence base available in a report, reflecting the issues identified and to be addressed in order to encourage public authorities to sustain and improve implementation of their statutory equality and good relations duties¹¹⁹.
- 9.6. The draft of this report was consulted upon in late 2017, with comments received from a range of stakeholders. Consultees confirmed the issues identified and made a number of comments, which have been considered and incorporated, as appropriate, in this report. The majority of consultees emphasised the need for the Commission to focus more on enforcement of the duties on public authorities.
- 9.7. The Commission continues to recognise the importance of respective stakeholder roles in engaging with and challenging public authorities in the fulfilment of their statutory equality and good relations duties, in order to

¹¹⁶ Northern Ireland Act 1998, [Schedule 9](#), paragraph 1(a).

¹¹⁷ [Section 75: Keeping it Effective](#) (ECNI, 2008).

¹¹⁸ Agreed at the Commission Meeting held in [March 2017](#).

¹¹⁹ Agreed at the Commission Meeting held in [March 2017](#).

mainstream the consideration of equality matters in the planning and delivery of public functions and services.

- 9.8. The Commission continues to act in accordance with the statutory framework as set out in Section 75 and Schedule 9 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998, and its actions and interventions are identified and planned accordingly.
- 9.9. The Commission deploys its resources along the continuum of the “enforcement” functions that are available: from providing advisory materials and advice to public authorities and others; to approving equality schemes, and to fulfilling its responsibilities in relation to complaints and investigations.

Recommendations

9.10. The Commission recommends to public authorities that:

- public authority leaders make clear the necessity of fulfilling the duties throughout their organisation – that they continue to be a statutory requirement;
- senior leaders and decision-makers in organisations actively request the evidence from equality assessments, as well as routinely seek assurance within their organisations that they are fulfilling the duties to have due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity and regard to the desirability of promoting good relations;
- those responsible for providing information for decision-making on a function or policy should ensure they provide sufficient information, from their equality assessments, for the appropriate consideration (i.e. due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity and regard to the desirability of promoting good relations) to be given in particular decisions;
- the importance of the statutory equality and good relations duties are highlighted within the organisation, on a continuing basis, and particularly given the current wider political and economic context;
- the shift of focus from process to outcomes should continue. Equality Schemes are to enable public authorities to fulfil the Section 75 duties – to give the appropriate consideration to the need to promote equality of opportunity and desirability of promoting good relations - when they deliver their functions. Through giving the appropriate consideration, a public authority will ensure that the decisions they take will be mindful of “the consequences on the lives of people”¹²⁰; and
- they ensure their consideration of the need to promote equality of opportunity, and desirability of promoting good relations, is evidence based and the data is available to support the consideration. There is a clear link between the consideration needed to meet the Section 75 duties and the data development agenda that is required for the Outcomes Based Accountability approach to the draft Programme for Government. This should drive the collection and use of equality data.

¹²⁰ [A Guide for Public Authorities](#) (ECNI, 2010), page 10.

Actions for the Equality Commission

9.11 The Commission has identified a number of actions that it will undertake in support of the recommendations:

- In its leadership role, the Commission will engage specifically with politicians, senior leaders in public authorities and decision makers to remind them of their roles and responsibilities in ensuring these statutory duties are fulfilled.
- The Commission will set the agenda and debate in highlighting the importance of the duties and their continuing relevance to, and assistance in the development of, public policy and service delivery in Northern Ireland.
- The Commission will convey and communicate one of the most important issues and success factors – leadership. While recognising the circumstances of reduced resources, leadership continues to be imperative within public authorities to ensure the maintained focus on equality matters, as well as the mainstreaming of equality considerations throughout the business of the authority.
- The Commission will continue to prioritise its advisory activities on public authority practices in screening and Equality Impact Assessment (EQIA), as set out in the 2018-19 Business Plan. This will ensure that these central methodologies are used to greatest effect by public authorities in consistently providing meaningful equality assessments of the policy objectives and policy goals under consideration at any given time.
- The Commission will use the issues identified in this report and review its approach to investigations generally, as set out in the 2018-19 Business Plan.
- The Commission will collate and publish the Commission's evidence base on and recommendations relating to equality data and gaps for the draft Programme for Government, as set out in the 2018-19 Business Plan

9.12 The Commission will continue to engage with and work in partnership with stakeholders who have an interest in and role in relation to ensuring that public authorities are fulfilling their statutory equality and good relations duties, as required by Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998.

APPENDIX 1

Northern Ireland Act 1998, Section 75

Statutory duty on public authorities

75. (1) A public authority shall in carrying out its functions relating to Northern Ireland have due regard to the need to promote equality of opportunity -
- (a) between persons of different religious belief, political opinion, racial group, age, marital status or sexual orientation;
 - (b) between men and women generally;
 - (c) between persons with a disability and persons without; and
 - (d) between persons with dependants and persons without.
- (2) Without prejudice to its obligations under subsection (1), a public authority shall in carrying out its functions relating to Northern Ireland have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations between persons of different religious belief, political opinion or racial group.
- (3) In this section “public authority” means -
- (a) any department, corporation or body listed in Schedule 2 to the Parliamentary Commissioner Act 1967 (departments, corporations and bodies subject to investigation) and designated for the purposes of this section by order made by the Secretary of State;
 - (b) any body (other than the Equality Commission) listed in Schedule 2 to the Commissioner for Complaints (Northern Ireland) Order 1996 (bodies subject to investigation);
 - (c) any department or other authority listed in Schedule 2 to the Ombudsman (Northern Ireland) Order 1996 (departments and other authorities subject to investigation);
 - (d) any other person designated for the purposes of this section by order made by the Secretary of State;
- (4) Schedule 9 (which makes provision for the enforcement of the duties under this section) shall have effect.
- (5) In this section -
- “disability” has the same meaning as in the Disability Discrimination Act 1995; and
- “racial group” has the same meaning as in the Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order 1997.

Equality Act 2010 – public sector equality duty on public authorities

149 Public sector equality duty

- (1) A public authority must, in the exercise of its functions, have due regard to the need to—
- (a) eliminate discrimination, harassment, victimisation and any other conduct that is prohibited by or under this Act;
 - (b) advance equality of opportunity between persons who share a relevant protected characteristic and persons who do not share it;
 - (c) foster good relations between persons who share a relevant protected characteristic and persons who do not share it.

Equality Act 2006 – EHRC powers and duties for enforcement of the Public Sector Equality Duties

Section 31: Public sector duties: assessment

- (1) The Commission may assess the extent to which or the manner in which a person has complied with a duty under or by virtue of section 149 ... of the Equality Act 2010 (public sector equality duty).

Section 16: Inquiries

- (1) The Commission may conduct an inquiry into a matter relating to any of the Commission's duties under **sections 8¹²¹ [F1 and 9]**.
- (2) If in the course of an inquiry the Commission begins to suspect that a person may have committed an unlawful act—
- (a) in continuing the inquiry the Commission shall, so far as possible, avoid further consideration of whether or not the person has committed an unlawful act

¹²¹ Emphasis added

Section 8: Equality and diversity

- (1) *The Commission shall, by exercising the powers conferred by this Part—*
- (a) promote understanding of the importance of equality and diversity,*
 - (b) encourage good practice in relation to equality and diversity,*
 - (c) promote equality of opportunity,*
 - (d) promote awareness and understanding of rights under the [F1Equality Act 2010],*
 - (e) enforce [F2that Act],*
 - (f) work towards the elimination of unlawful discrimination, and*
 - (g) work towards the elimination of unlawful harassment.*
- (2) *In subsection (1)—*
- “diversity” means the fact that individuals are different,*
 - “equality” means equality between individuals, and*
 - “unlawful” is to be construed in accordance with section 34.*
- (3) *In promoting equality of opportunity between disabled persons and others, the Commission may, in particular, promote the favourable treatment of disabled persons.*

Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission Act 2014, Section 42

42. (1) A public body shall, in the performance of its functions, have regard to the need to—
- (a) eliminate discrimination,
 - (b) promote equality of opportunity and treatment of its staff and the persons to whom it provides services, and
 - (c) protect the human rights of its members, staff and the persons to whom it provides services.
- (2) For the purposes of giving effect to *subsection (1)*, a public body shall, having regard to the functions and purpose of the body and to its size and the resources available to it—
- (a) set out in a manner that is accessible to the public in its strategic plan (howsoever described) an assessment of the human rights and equality issues it believes to be relevant to the functions and purpose of the body and the policies, plans and actions in place or proposed to be put in place to address those issues, and
 - (b) report in a manner that is accessible to the public on developments and achievements in that regard in its annual report (howsoever described).
- (3) In assisting public bodies to perform their functions in a manner consistent with subsection (1), the Commission may give guidance to and encourage public bodies in developing policies of, and exercising, good practice and operational standards in relation to, human rights and equality.
- (4) Without prejudice to the generality of subsection (3), the Commission may—
- (a) issue guidelines, or
 - (b) prepare codes of practice in accordance with [section 31](#), in respect of the development by public bodies of performance measures, operational standards and written preventative strategies for the purpose of reducing discrimination and promoting human rights and equality in the public sector workplace and in the provision of services to the public.
- (5) Where the Commission considers that there is evidence of a failure by a public body to perform its functions in a manner consistent with subsection (1) and that it is appropriate in all the circumstances to do so, the Commission may invite the public body to—
- (a) carry out a review in relation to the performance by that body of its functions having regard to *subsection (1)*, or
 - (b) prepare and implement an action plan in relation to the performance by that body of its functions having regard to *subsection (1)*, or both.
- (6) A review or an action plan under *subsection (5)* may relate to—
- (a) equality of opportunity or human rights generally, or

- (b) a particular aspect of human rights or discrimination, in the public body concerned.
- (7) The Commission may, and, if requested by the Minister, shall, review the operation of *subsection (1)*.
- (8) For the purposes of assisting it in carrying out a review under *subsection (7)*, the Commission shall consult such persons or bodies as it considers appropriate.
- (9) Where the Commission carries out a review under *subsection (7)* it—
- (a) may, or
- (b) where the Minister has requested the review, shall, make a report of the review to the Minister and any such report shall include such recommendations as the Commission thinks appropriate.
- (10) The Commission shall cause a copy of the report to be laid before each House of the Oireachtas.
- (11) Nothing in this section shall of itself operate to confer a cause of action on any person against a public body in respect of the performance by it of its functions under *subsection (1)*.

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Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998

EQUALITY COMMISSION FOR NORTHERN IRELAND

PROMOTING GOOD RELATIONS

A Guide for Public Authorities

October 2007

Equality Commission

FOR NORTHERN IRELAND

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Foreword

“A Society’s cultural life is rich if people in the society can communicate with each other, describe their reality and their experiences, voice their feelings, understand one another and thus in the end - be in a position to respect one another”.

Council of Europe, 1978

Northern Ireland’s recent history has been one of considerable political turmoil and community conflict resulting in social and economic disturbance and disadvantage for many living here. The Good Friday Agreement rightly recognised the need for a statutory intervention, situated within a framework of equality, to promote good relations between differing sections of the community in Northern Ireland. That found expression in the obligation placed upon designated public authorities to promote good relations in the development and implementation of their policies and in the discharge of all their functions, building on existing rights and responsibilities under fair employment and race relations legislation.

The increase in inward migration and changing demographics in Northern Ireland have reinforced the importance of constructively promoting good relations, have broadened the base of the debate on this important topic, and have underlined the need for all sectors (public, private, voluntary and community), political parties, trade unions and others to show commitment and strong leadership in addressing both sectarianism and racism.

Section 75 (2) places a duty on the public sector in Northern Ireland to put good relations at the heart of public policy and its implementation; to shape policies around the people they affect. It is not only a legal requirement; it is also a social and economic imperative. The public sector reaches into virtually every home and workplace in Northern Ireland and affects the lives of many in fundamental ways. By embracing the challenge that is embodied in this duty, by internalising the responsibility it entails, by recognising its centrality and its valid claim on time and resources, and by its creativity and imagination, the public sector can make a real difference to the quality of the relations between all who live in Northern Ireland.

The Equality Commission's Review of the Effectiveness of Section 75¹ found that, to date, public authorities have tended to focus on the equality of opportunity duty rather than the good relations duty when addressing their commitment to Section 75 and that, as a consequence, good relations work appears to have featured to a lesser extent in their Section 75 activities than work undertaken to promote equality of opportunity.

Clear leadership which identifies the direction and sets the tone is critical to the successful implementation of the good relations duty. Leaders of public authorities need to demonstrate publicly in an unequivocal manner that promoting good relations is both central to and a measure of their success. The duty is not just directed at removing or avoiding occasions of difficulty between various groups but, rather, is intended actively to encourage the expression of good relations and their promotion in all aspects of an authority's work. The inclusion of the duty in the legislation that sets out the constitutional framework for Northern Ireland is not a mere token or a platitude. It is intended to be transformative; it is about changing attitudes as well as behaviour.

Clearly, the legislative provisions of Section 75 (2) are directed towards the promotion of good relations between people of different religious belief, political opinion and racial group. This Guide reflects that reality. However, while the legislation sets down what must be done, it does not preclude a broader view or the undertaking of other work. The Commission encourages public authorities to look beyond the three categories that the law now requires and to seek to promote good relations in respect of the other equality categories identified in the legislation and more generally.

Equality of opportunity and good relations are complementary and interdependent. Many public authorities are actively and enthusiastically implementing the good relations duty and much has been gained from their experience of what works and what doesn't. A variety of good practice examples from different sectors are included in this Guide. These examples, together with the practical steps and strategic approach recommended in this Guide, can help public authorities to realise the full potential of their role in the community. In that way they can help to create an inclusive society at ease with itself and with difference.

Bob Collins
Chief Commissioner
Equality Commission for Northern Ireland

¹ Equality Commission for Northern Ireland (2007), Keeping it Effective: Reviewing the Effectiveness of Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998.

Chapter 1 - Introduction

- 1.1 **Section 75 (2) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998** places a legal duty on designated public authorities to have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations between persons of different **religious belief, political opinion or racial group**. For ease of reference, the duty under Section 75 (2) is referred to as the '**good relations duty**'.
- 1.2 The Equality Commission's statutory remit (see Chapter 4), coupled with its vision for Northern Ireland as "a shared, integrated and inclusive place, a society where difference is respected and valued based on equality of opportunity and fairness to the entire community"², has driven the production of this detailed guidance for public authorities. In doing so, the Equality Commission has drawn on the unique knowledge, experience and expertise it has gained from its statutory role in advising public authorities on their good relations duty under Section 75, and on the provisions of the Fair Employment and Treatment (Northern Ireland) Order 1998 and the Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order 1997, through intervening on policy issues as diverse as the display of flags and emblems and the allocation of housing, to sensitive and appropriate access to health care and the location of public services.
- 1.3 The Commission is clear that Section 75 (2) formalises the shift from **managing** diversity and difference to **promoting** diversity and integration. It requires public authorities to take a **pro-active** initiating approach to contributing to a shared society, rather than responding to the effects of a divided one. It means recognising and acknowledging the legacy of decades of sectarian conflict, and challenging sectarianism and racism. This requires not only reacting swiftly to incidents and manifestations, such as graffiti or name-calling; but also educating and training people to understand that prejudice is not acceptable. It means creating an ethos, a culture, of good relations, and recognising the need to promote good relations both within, and between, communities.

² Equality for All: Continuing progress in a changing environment. Corporate Plan 2006 – 2009, Equality Commission for Northern Ireland (2006), www.equalityni.org

- 1.4 Given that it is a legal requirement, it is vital that the good relations duty is taken seriously, and that its mainstreaming and implementation can be demonstrated and reported upon. The promotion of good relations requires **imagination, commitment** and **leadership**.
- 1.5 To meet its vision, and to enable designated public authorities proactively to meet their good relations obligations under Section 75 (2), the Equality Commission has established a working definition of good relations (see paragraph 2.1), and outlines in this Guide **key principles** for the successful implementation of the good relations duty (see Chapter 2); namely:-
- Leadership.
 - Commitment and communication.
 - The interdependence of equality of opportunity and good relations.
 - Integration not segregation.
 - Collaboration, co-ordination and consultation.
- 1.6 The Equality Commission recommends that public authorities take time to consider what they can achieve in promoting good relations in the context of the functions and remit of their organisation. One of the Commission's key recommendations is the development of a tailored **Good Relations Strategy**. Advice on the key elements of such a strategy is detailed in Chapter 3 of this Guide. It includes the development of a strategy and action plan which sets out the public authority's vision for good relations in the context of its functions; allocates responsibility for implementation; demonstrates top level commitment; and identifies specific measures which it intends to take within a specified timescale. Progress should be monitored, reported and reviewed annually, with an emphasis on outcomes. Public authorities should detail their actions, planned and taken, and report on progress made in their annual progress reports on the implementation of Section 75.

Purpose and status of the Guide

- 1.7 The purpose of this Guide is to provide public authorities with information and advice on implementing the good relations duty. It outlines what the duty is, how public authorities can proactively address their legal obligations, sets out key principles for the successful implementation of the duty and includes a range of

examples of good practice by public authorities. The examples are based on information either directly supplied to the Equality Commission by public authorities or included as part of their annual reporting on the implementation on Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998. Implementation and good practice examples can also be found in the Equality Commission's publications *Audit of Progress on the Good Relations Duty 2000-2003*, and *Good Relations in Practice: A Report of Progress on the Good Relations Duty 2003-2005*.³

- 1.8 This Guide supplements the *Guide to the Statutory Duties*⁴, which constitutes the primary source of guidance on implementing Section 75. This Guide on Promoting Good Relations will frequently reference the *Guide to the Statutory Duties*, so it is important that readers consult that key document in conjunction with this guidance on the good relations duty (although some extracts are repeated here for ease of reference).
- 1.9 The aim of the Guide, whilst not legally binding, is to make recommendations and provide suggestions and examples of good practice that may be adopted or adapted. It is not intended to be prescriptive. What is appropriate action for one organisation may not be relevant to another, and there is considerable flexibility in the ways in which public authorities can address their good relations duty in the context of their own unique remit and functions. Public authorities should ensure that any work is underpinned by the key principles set out in this Guide, and that actions comply with equality scheme commitments.

Legislative context

- 1.10 Section 75 (2) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 states :

'a public authority shall in carrying out its functions relating to Northern Ireland, have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations between persons of different religious belief, political opinion or racial group'.

³ Equality Commission for Northern Ireland (2006), www.equalityni.org.

⁴ Equality Commission for Northern Ireland: Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998: Guide to the Statutory Duties (2005).

1.11 Section 75 (2) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 therefore places a statutory duty on public bodies to **pro-actively** address good relations. It means a public authority must consider how the policies it makes and implements affect relationships amongst the people it serves and employs. The purpose of the duty, like the equality of opportunity duty, is to mainstream good relations by placing it at the heart of public policy.

‘Regard’ and ‘due regard’

1.12 Section 75 (1) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998, states that a public authority must have **due** regard to the **need** to promote equality of opportunity, while it must also have under Section 75 (2), **regard** to the **desirability** of promoting good relations.

What does having ‘regard’ or ‘due regard’ mean?

1.13 The *Guide to the Statutory Duties* explains “regard” and “due regard” in the following terms:⁵

“The term **due regard** was intended to be, and is, stronger than **regard**, but in either case the authority is required by the statute to take the specified matters **into account** and give them the required weight when carrying out its functions relating to Northern Ireland. Authorities must appreciate Parliament’s stated assessment that there is a **need** to promote equality of opportunity between the categories of persons specified in Section 75 (1) and a **desirability** of promoting good relations between persons of different religious belief, political opinion or racial group (Section 75 (2)).”

What is the relationship between the equality of opportunity duty and the good relations duty?

1.14 In the Parliamentary debates on the Northern Ireland Bill, the then Secretary of State, Dr Marjorie Mowlam said:

“[We] regard equality of opportunity and good relations as complementary. There should be no conflict between the two objectives. Good relations cannot be based on inequality

⁵ Guide to the Statutory Duties, paras. 2.11 – 2.15.

between different religions or ethnic groups. Social cohesion requires equality to be reinforced by good community relations.”⁶

Recognition of the inter-dependence of equality of opportunity and good relations is crucial.

- 1.15 Although there are differences under Schedule 9 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 as regards the implementation of the equality of opportunity and good relations duties, it is important to stress that there is a **clear duty** under Section 75 on public authorities to address **both** equality of opportunity **and** good relations, and this requires placing both at the heart of public policy decision making.

What other equality legislation is relevant to the promotion of good relations?

- 1.16 Under Article 67 of the Race Relations (NI) Order 1997, **local councils** are under a duty ‘to make appropriate arrangements with a view to securing that their various functions are carried out with due regard to the need to eliminate racial discrimination and to promote equality of opportunity and good relations between persons of different racial groups’.
- 1.17 The **Fair Employment and Treatment (NI) Order 1998** (as amended) (FETO), makes discrimination and harassment on the grounds of religious belief or political opinion unlawful. In addition, the **Fair Employment Code of Practice** provides general guidance for employers as regards the promotion of a good and harmonious working environment. Section 5.2 of the Code states that:

‘To promote equality of opportunity you should...promote a good and harmonious working environment and atmosphere in which no worker feels under threat or intimidated because of his or her religious belief or political opinion, e.g. prohibit the display of flags...[etc]...which are likely to give offence or cause apprehension among particular groups of employees.’

The Fair Employment Code of Practice is given particular significance by FETO, which permits it to be taken into account by the Fair Employment Tribunal, in relation to the determination of any question before it. FETO was recently amended to incorporate a new statutory

⁶ House of Commons, Official Report, 27 July 1998, col.109.

definition of harassment (Articles 3A (1) and 3A (2)). The new harassment definition may be paraphrased as follows:

‘Harassment is unwanted conduct which is based on the grounds of religious belief or political opinion, and which has the purpose or effect of violating the dignity of an employee, or of creating an intimidating, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment for an employee.’

- 1.18 Public authorities must ensure that they follow the recommendations of the *Fair Employment Code of Practice*, and the *Code of Practice for Employers for the elimination of racial discrimination and the promotion of equality of opportunity in employment*.⁷ There are also a number of international obligations (listed in Appendix 6 of the *Guide to the Statutory Duties*), with which public authorities should familiarise themselves.

Policy context

- 1.19 Complementary to the legislative framework described above, it is also important to take account of a number of important and relevant government policies in Northern Ireland.

A Shared Future and the Racial Equality Strategy

- 1.20 In 2005, the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister (OFMDFM) published *A Shared Future*⁸, the Government’s policy and strategic framework for good relations in Northern Ireland, and *the Racial Equality Strategy for Northern Ireland (2005 – 10)*⁹. These key government policies and their accompanying action plans represent clear central commitment to an equal and inclusive society in Northern Ireland. The strategies include specific actions for government departments and key non-departmental public bodies, such as the Police Service for Northern Ireland and the Northern Ireland Housing Executive. They set out a number of policy objectives and identify priority areas. Other government strategies, such as the *Our Children and Young People – Our Pledge: A Ten Year Strategy for Children and Young People 2006 - 2016 and Lifetime Opportunities*, the

⁷ Equality Commission for Northern Ireland, 1998, www.equalityni.org.

⁸ www.asharedfutureni.gov.uk.

⁹ www.ofmdfmini.gov.uk.

*government's anti-poverty and social inclusion strategy*¹⁰, also have an important contribution to make to the inclusion of good relations in Northern Ireland.

Review of Public Administration (RPA)

- 1.21 The Review of Public Administration (RPA)¹¹, *A Shared Future* and other government strategies such as the *Racial Equality Strategy*, provide unique and unprecedented opportunities for government and the public sector to show leadership in establishing innovative, challenging and ambitious action plans that target resources where they are most needed, and ensure that equality of opportunity and good relations are at the heart of the development of public policy and service delivery, so that they have the most positive impact on the lives of everyone in Northern Ireland.
- 1.22 The Equality Commission acknowledges that the outcomes of the Review of Public Administration may have a significant impact on the number, structure and functions of public authorities in Northern Ireland. In addition, a range of good relations requirements may be placed on different public authorities under the RPA. Such changes will be taken into account in any future revision of this guidance. However, since the advice contained in this guidance is broad and non-specific regarding types or sizes of organisations, it should be relevant no matter how the public sector in Northern Ireland is organised or reorganised.
- 1.23 Section 75 (2) is a **continuing** duty and all newly established designated public authorities will be subject to the good relations duty. As set out above, it is recommended that public authorities develop a good relations strategy in order to provide a clear and workable framework for the promotion of good relations between people of different religious belief, political opinion and racial group. Public authorities newly established under the RPA should, drawing on the work and experience of their predecessor organisations, develop and implement tailored good relations strategies which reflect the unique remit and functions of the new authority.
- 1.24 The new powers of well being and community planning proposed under the RPA should be used to maximise opportunities for

¹⁰ www.ofmdfmni.gov.uk.

¹¹ www.rpani.gov.uk.

embedding good relations into local services and governance arrangements. A discussion paper, *Embedding Good Relations in Local Government: Challenges and Opportunities*¹², produced by independent consultants, makes recommendations in this regard.

Why promote good relations?

- 1.25 In addition to the **legal requirements** as set out above, public authorities need to pro-actively address good relations to:
- address sectarianism and racism;
 - acknowledge poor relations beyond interfaces; and
 - recognise multiple identities.

Addressing sectarianism and racism

- 1.26 An increasing immigrant population is leading to greater diversity in Northern Ireland. As populations become more mobile across the European Union and worldwide, public authorities face new challenges in addressing the needs of changing and increasingly diverse communities. The introduction of anti-discrimination legislation has had a significant impact in formally addressing issues of equality of opportunity. However, recent research refers to ‘the persistence of virulent sectarian bigotry and hostility in Northern Ireland.’¹³ Sectarian and racist attacks on people and property continue to be reported every week¹⁴, and there is also evidence of continuing polarisation and segregation.
- 1.27 These factors underline the need for public authorities to give serious consideration and commitment to the good relations duty, and specifically to identify what this requires them to do as providers of services, as policy-makers or as employers, in the context of their distinctive functions and as components of the government and administration in Northern Ireland. Equality of opportunity and the promotion of good relations are central to the delivery of good quality public services and a better quality of life for everyone.

¹² Good Relations Associates (2007), ECNI, www.equalityni.org.

¹³ Jarman, Neil, Institute of Conflict Research, ‘No longer a Problem? Sectarian Violence in Northern Ireland’ (2005) commissioned by the Office of the First and Deputy First Minister, www.ofmdfmni.gov.uk.

¹⁴ Statistics produced by the Police Service of Northern Ireland show that during the period 05/06, there were a total of 936 racially motivated incidents and 746 racially motivated offences. During the same period, there were 1,701 sectarian motivated incidents and 1,470 sectarian offences recorded (PSNI Statistical Report, 1 April 2005 – 31 March 2006, www.psni.police.uk).

Not just interfaces

- 1.28 It is tempting to assume that there is only a need to promote good relations when trouble arises or when there is the potential for conflict – such as at interfaces, or in times of heightened tensions (for example, during the ‘marching season’) – and that when the situation is ‘quiet’ there is no need for intervention. However, racism and sectarianism are present at all levels in society. As the Community Relations Council states, “problems of community division exist in not just working class, segregated communities, but also in the minds of many people throughout the region irrespective of class or creed and some of whom are in positions of great power and influence.”¹⁵
- 1.29 Good relations work is not confined solely to interface areas, nor activated only when problems arise. The good relations duty and the tools of Section 75, such as the consultation and equality impact assessment requirements, provide a powerful framework for dialogue and for addressing hard issues in a structured way. Section 75 (2) provides a basis for developing innovative strategies to promote preventative measures, through fostering positive inter-communal work on an ongoing and local basis across the region. Such strategies need to be inclusive of the needs of the members of minority ethnic groups, and others who are subjected to discrimination and exclusion on other equality grounds.

Multiple identities

- 1.30 The Equality Commission recognises the deep-rooted divisions within our society and the impact that this has on people’s daily lives. While not underestimating the crucial importance of eradicating sectarianism and racism, it is vital that a shared and pluralist society also includes proactively addressing homophobic and sexist actions and behaviours, as well as the outworking of prejudiced attitudes to disability. Hate crime law in Northern Ireland encompasses disability and sexual orientation, as well as religion, politics and race.
- 1.31 The legislation as it is currently framed specifies only three grounds for promoting good relations – **religious belief, political opinion and racial group**. Although work undertaken by public authorities to promote good relations with reference to men and women, sexual orientation, disability, age, people with and without dependants, or

¹⁵ www.community-relations.org.uk.

marital status, is **not** currently within the scope of the Section 75 (2) statutory duty, and is not legally required, it is of course **open** to public authorities to undertake work to promote good relations amongst other groups covered by Section 75, and the Equality Commission welcomes such work.

- 1.32 The statutory duties under the Disability Discrimination Act 1995 (as amended by the Disability Discrimination (Northern Ireland) Order 2006), which commenced on 1 January 2007, require public bodies to have due regard to the need to promote positive attitudes towards disabled people, and to encourage the participation by disabled people in public life. Measures undertaken to promote positive attitudes towards disabled people, should work alongside initiatives taken by public authorities to promote good relations under Section 75 (2).

Chapter 2 - Vision and Key Principles

Vision

“The Equality Commission has the vision of Northern Ireland as a shared, integrated and inclusive place, a society where difference is respected and valued, based on equality and fairness for the entire community.”¹⁶

What is meant by ‘good relations’?

2.1 Neither ‘good relations’ nor ‘promoting good relations’ is defined in legislation, nor is there a commonly agreed definition. A number of public authorities have developed their own vision or definition. The Equality Commission, drawing on the knowledge and experience it has gained in overseeing the implementation of Section 75 (2) across the three equality grounds, has developed a working definition of good relations, as follows:

“the growth of relationships and structures for Northern Ireland that acknowledge the religious, political and racial context of this society, and that seek to promote respect, equity¹⁷ and trust, and embrace diversity in all its forms.”

2.2 The Government’s policy and strategic framework for good relations in Northern Ireland, *A Shared Future*,¹⁸ was published in March 2005 and sets out the government’s vision for:

¹⁶ ECNI (2006), Equality for All: Continuing progress in a changing environment, Corporate Plan 2006 – 2009 www.equalityni.org.

¹⁷ “Equity is about ensuring that all sections of society have equal opportunities to participate in economic, political and social life through redressing inequalities arising independently from people’s choices.” (Future Ways, Equity, Diversity and Interdependence Framework, p 21).

¹⁸ A Shared Future and the First Triennial Action Plan, www.asharedfutureni.gov.uk.

“[t]he establishment over time, of a normal, civic society, in which all individuals are considered as equals, where differences are resolved through dialogue in the public sphere, and where all people are treated impartially. A society where there is equity, respect for diversity and a recognition of our interdependence.”

2.3 It goes on to explain that ‘community relations’ refers specifically to divisions between the Protestant and Catholic communities in Northern Ireland, whereas ‘good relations’ refers to Section 75 (2) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998, which relates to relations between persons of different religious belief, political opinion or racial group¹⁹.

2.4 *The Racial Equality Strategy for Northern Ireland (2005-10)*²⁰ also sets out a long-term, high level vision of Northern Ireland as:-

“A society in which racial diversity is supported, understood, valued and respected, where racism in any of its forms is not tolerated and where we live together as a society and enjoy equality of opportunity and equal protection.”

2.5 As stated in Chapter 1, the Equality Commission is clear that Section 75 (2) formalises the shift from **managing** diversity and difference to **promoting** diversity and integration. It requires public authorities to be **pro-active**, recognising and acknowledging the legacy of conflict, and challenging sectarianism and racism. This requires not only reacting swiftly to incidents such as graffiti or name-calling; but also communicating a clear message that prejudice is not acceptable. It means creating an ethos, a culture, of good relations, and recognising the need to promote good relations both within and between communities.

2.6 Promoting good relations can also involve tackling difficult issues such as the display of aggressive and intimidating flags and emblems, and taking steps to create safe and shared public spaces in towns and cities, that can be accessed and used by all sections of all communities.

¹⁹ Under Section 75, ‘religious belief’ includes people of all faiths and none; ‘political opinion’ includes members and supporters of any political party; ‘racial group’ includes people of minority ethnic origin, mixed ethnic origin, different national origin, including asylum seekers, refugees and migrant workers, and Irish Travellers.

²⁰ www.ofmdfmi.gov.uk.

- 2.7 In implementing the fair employment and race equality legislation, public authorities (and others) have been promoting a working environment in which everyone is treated with respect and dignity, where no-one feels threatened or intimidated because of their religious belief, political opinion or racial group. Shared space in the workplace can help to develop respect for, and understanding of, the needs and concerns of diverse communities; laying the foundations for the development of good relations, and creating the momentum for change elsewhere in society.
- 2.8 Promoting good relations can involve challenging misconceptions, preconceptions, stereotypical assumptions and prejudices against people perceived as outsiders or different (such as migrant workers or Irish Travellers), as well as making sure that people from all racial groups are aware of their rights and have access to, and information about, the services available to them. This guidance therefore includes examples of good practice that public authorities and others may use to promote positive attitudes towards people of different faiths (or no faith), different ethnic backgrounds, and migrant workers.

Key principles

- 2.9 There are a number of key principles that should underpin a public authority's implementation of the good relations duty under Section 75 (2) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998.

Leadership

- 2.10 Public authorities each have a **unique contribution** that their organisation can make to promoting good relations in Northern Ireland. By exercising effective leadership and working in partnership with other public authorities and others, (for example, the voluntary and community sectors, private employers, political parties etc), public authorities can use their considerable influence to make a substantial and tangible difference to people's lives and benefit all communities in Northern Ireland.
- 2.11 **Effective leadership** across the political, public, private and voluntary and community sectors is essential to bring about change and to convey consistent messages. Visible committed leadership gives clear vision and direction, and shapes the culture of an organisation,

creating an environment in which good relations can flourish.

- 2.12 The Equality Commission has found that effectiveness in meeting the good relations duty under Section 75 (2), has been most apparent in public authorities where there is evidence of leadership at the highest levels. Some public authorities have embraced the spirit of the legislation, and demonstrated significant commitment and leadership, by embedding and mainstreaming the good relations and equality of opportunity duties under Section 75 into their core business and functions, rather than viewing it as a separate or parallel process.
- 2.13 The promotion of good relations must be **supported** and **endorsed** at the highest levels of an organisation, by both the administrative and governance heads, providing positive and influential role models both in public and to employees. They need to be willing to tackle sensitive and difficult issues, and to challenge sectarianism and racism in all their forms.

Commitment and communication

- 2.14 Strong, visible commitment to improving relations is essential to successfully mainstreaming and implementing the promotion of good relations. Commitment must flow from the highest level and throughout the whole organisation – horizontally and vertically.
- 2.15 One way of ensuring this happens is to include **objectives** relating to the promotion of good relations in corporate and business plans, or their equivalents, and in the performance measures of individual employees. These will vary according to each employee's job description and responsibilities.
- 2.16 Commitment can best be measured through the visible allocation of **resources**. The sustained provision of resources to the implementation of Section 75 is essential to the continuing ability of staff to deliver on actions. Commitment must also therefore include the allocation and **continuing** allocation of appropriate and sufficient resources, in terms of people, time and money, to the effective implementation of a good relations strategy or programme.
- 2.17 **Communication** is a key element in ensuring the effectiveness of any policy or strategy. When people are informed about what an organisation is doing, why they are doing it, and their views are

sought on how to do it, a sense of ownership and inclusion is developed.

- 2.18 The promotion of good relations by public authorities contributes to a society that is more inclusive, more cohesive, more efficient and more effective. Public bodies have a **responsibility** to use their authority and **considerable influence** to contribute to the creation of a shared society in which everyone feels not only physically safe, but also safe in their beliefs and opinions.
- 2.19 Organisations should take all available opportunities to **communicate** and reiterate their commitment, both internally and externally, to their good relations strategy, and the work they are undertaking to promote good relations, both within and between communities (see paragraphs 3.34 – 3.37). Information from annual progress reports and public authorities’ five-year review of equality schemes indicates that public authorities have tended to focus on the equality of opportunity duty rather than the good relations duty when communicating their commitment to Section 75. It is essential that both duties are addressed, and that both employees and the public are aware of an organisation’s commitment to promoting good relations and the positive benefits this has for policy implementation and service delivery.
- 2.20 Public authorities should also ensure that there is a consistent message across the organisation (in terms of words and actions), as regards commitment to promoting good relations, and that different parts of an organisation **do not undermine** the proactive work of other parts.

The interdependence of equality of opportunity and good relations

- 2.21 Equality of opportunity and good relations are inextricably linked and interdependent, and both must be addressed by designated public authorities. A failure to achieve one impacts on the ability to achieve the other. The Equality Commission has consistently stated that “good relations cannot be delivered without equality also being delivered.”²¹

²¹ Guide to the Statutory Duties 2005, ECNI, www.equalityni.org.

2.22 Section 75 recognises the interdependence between equality of opportunity and good relations, and this was clearly articulated by the then Secretary of State during the parliamentary debates on the passage of Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Bill through Parliament.

“Good relations cannot be based on inequality between different religions or ethnic groups. Social cohesion requires equality to be reinforced by good community relations...”²²

2.23 Promoting equality of opportunity sometimes requires the use of positive action measures in order to address existing inequalities with a view to achieving a level playing field for all. In such circumstances, public authorities must have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations both within and between communities, on the grounds of race, religious belief and political opinion, and consider what steps need to be taken to gain the confidence, trust and acceptance of all parts of the community. Communication of the reasons for the positive action is essential in this situation. The equality impact assessment mechanism is an essential tool for identifying relevant equality issues, and actual and perceived adverse impacts, leading to the consideration of appropriate mitigating measures or alternative policies.

Integration not segregation

2.24 In the past, Northern Ireland has dealt with the conflict by providing separate services, such as housing, leisure facilities, and education, for different communities. However, separation emphasises difference and encourages mistrust. Economically, as well as morally, the provision of parallel services is inefficient and unsustainable. In addition, the ‘human cost’ of a divided society in terms of the detrimental impact on the health and well-being of communities is unacceptable. The Equality Commission has consistently emphasized that ‘separate but equal’ is not an option.

2.25 Sectarianism, racism and division all cost jobs and damage prosperity, and the provision of parallel but separate services for different communities is not only socially but also economically unjustifiable. Northern Ireland needs to be able to compete in a global economy, and investment and tourism depend on social and economic stability.

²² Dr Marjorie Mowlam, House of Commons Official Report, 27 July 1998, col. 109.

2.26 A shared society is one which is at ease with diversity. It is held together by a willingness to engage in dialogue, on a basis of equality, by a commitment to the common good, and by a culture of acceptance. Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 is an important tool in working towards this vision. It provides the driver and the mechanisms to enable public bodies to identify, and remove or reduce, barriers.

Collaboration, co-ordination and consultation

2.27 Progress reports received by the Equality Commission to date indicate that there is significant value in public authorities working together to take a joint approach to the promotion of good relations. The Equality Commission encourages public authorities to share information and good practice on promoting good relations. Co-ordination reduces the need for every organisation separately to research problems, identify opportunities and develop strategies, plans and training programmes, and to address common problems, thus achieving economies of scale. Sometimes, separate overall co-ordination bodies for a sector facilitate this; in other cases, joint work is co-ordinated by a Forum or Steering group, which is representative of all of the organisations in the collective.

2.28 There are good examples of co-ordination within various sectors; for example, education (Association of Northern Ireland Colleges (ANIC) and its work with the Further Education Colleges (see case study in Annex 1), the Joined in Equity, Diversity and Interdependence (JEDI) project with the Education and Library Boards; the Higher Education Equality Consortium; health (Southern Health and Social Services Board (SHSSB) and Eastern Health and Social Services Board (EHSSB) areas); and local government sectors (for example the mid-Ulster councils).

2.29 There are also examples of public authorities across sectors working together on a geographical basis. For example, the Southern Health and Social Services Board and Trusts, and the Southern Education and Library Boards (SELBs), worked with the Social Security Agency and Section 75 umbrella organisations in the voluntary and community sectors, to establish a local interpreting service for the Chinese and Asian communities.

Example

During 2005/06, the five education and library boards and the Staff Commission for Education and Library Boards developed a Good Relations Policy and Strategy, which incorporated three important elements: racial equality; community relations; and social inclusion.

The policy emerged from the Good Relations duty encompassed in Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act; it was further developed by the 'Shared Future' document published in March 2005 and substantially enhanced by the *Racial Equality Strategy for Northern Ireland* published in July 2005.

The strategy sets out the context, the policy position, a vision, values and identified shared aims, including the promotion of good relations, equal protection, equality of service provision, participation, dialogue and capacity building. A number of actions were identified under each aim, with responsibility allocated, timescales and anticipated outcomes (which will facilitate evaluation, monitoring and review).

While not specifically stated as an objective, this partnership approach ensures effective use of resources, avoids repetition and ensures consistency, and shares experience.

- 2.30 **Partnerships** with the voluntary and community sectors, which already make a substantial contribution to the achievement of better relations between communities, are particularly important. Drawing on its experience from over-seeing the implementation of Section 75, the Equality Commission recognises the importance of ensuring that the **capacity** of the voluntary and community sectors to deliver community development (and work in partnership with the public sector), is **maintained** and **reinforced**.
- 2.31 Public authorities' approved equality schemes include commitments to meaningful and inclusive consultation, as detailed in the **Guiding Principles on Consultation** and in the explanatory notes in the *Guide to the Statutory Duties*.²³ These apply to all aspects of implementing an equality scheme, and promoting equality of opportunity and good relations, and are particularly pertinent to communication and consultation with third sector partnerships, in order to ensure effective engagement and partnership working (see also Chapter 4).

²³ Guide to the Statutory Duties (pp18 – 25 and pp57-58).

Chapter 3 - Implementing the Good Relations Duty

How to Implement the Good Relations Duty

- 3.1 The purpose of this section is to provide public authorities with information, advice and recommendations on implementing their statutory duty under Section 75 (2) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998, using examples of practical implementation and actual good practice. The **legislative context** of the good relations duty is set out in Chapter 1 of this Guide, while Chapter 2 sets out the Equality Commission's **vision** and **key principles** for promoting good relations in Northern Ireland.
- 3.2 Analysis of Section 75 annual progress reports indicates that good relations work appears to have figured to a lesser extent in public authorities' Section 75 activities than work on equality of opportunity. As emphasised at paragraph 2.12, equality of opportunity and good relations are inextricably linked and interdependent, as failure to achieve one impacts on the ability to achieve the other. Both must be addressed by public authorities. The legislation requires public authorities to implement Section 75 (2) and to **demonstrate** this with **tangible** action. Promoting good relations involves a level of engagement from public servants that has never before been required – to change not only behaviour but **attitudes, hearts and minds**.
- 3.3 The promotion of good relations by public authorities must be action-based in a way that is tailored to the specific remit and functions of the organisation. Each public authority needs to ascertain what needs to be done, and what can be done in the particular circumstances in which it carries out those functions. Therefore, while this Guide provides advice and makes recommendations, not every measure will be appropriate for every organisation, and there is considerable flexibility in the ways in which public authorities can address their good relations duty. What is important is that the good relations duty is taken seriously, and that it is pro-actively implemented, monitored and reported upon.

Mainstreaming good relations into public policy decision-making

- 3.4 The purpose of the good relations duty, like the equality of opportunity duty, is to **mainstream** good relations by placing it at the heart of

public policy decision-making. Promoting good relations must be central to the functions of a public authority and an integral part of policy development and service delivery in an organisational wide approach, which includes incorporating specific objectives, targets and performance measures into corporate, business, and/or operational plans. The equality of opportunity and good relations duties under Section 75 should become core business priorities, rather than being seen as a parallel process, so that good relations is incorporated into all policy decisions at all stages and at all levels.

- 3.5 There must be transparent **responsibility** and **accountability** for driving the authority's good relations programme of work, and this should be clearly assigned. Information about the implementation of equality schemes shows that where there is clarity regarding responsibility for Section 75 obligations, such as through job descriptions and dedicated units, implementation benefits. Some organisations have appointed Good Relations Champions, or specifically designated an individual or group to implement their agreed programme of work on Section 75 (2). However, promoting good relations should **not be viewed as solely their responsibility**. Each member of staff should be encouraged to consider how they, through their own particular roles and duties, can contribute, so that the promotion of good relations is mainstreamed throughout the organisation.

Compliance with equality scheme commitments

- 3.6 Equality schemes produced by designated public authorities and approved by the Equality Commission include, as a minimum, a commitment to 'have regard to the desirability of promoting good relations between persons of different religious belief, political opinion or racial group.' Equality schemes also detail the public authority's arrangements for **assessing compliance** with its Section 75 duties, and set out **commitments** in relation to internal arrangements for ensuring that the duties are effectively complied with, for monitoring and reviewing progress, screening and impact assessment, training and access to information and services. Schemes also include a commitment to conducting an annual review of progress made in implementing the arrangements specified in the equality scheme and in complying with the statutory duties. These commitments and arrangements relate to **both** the good relations duty and the equality of opportunity duty. The approved equality scheme is therefore a public authority's **primary framework** for implementing the good relations duty.

- 3.7 The Equality Commission **recommends** that public authorities' equality schemes set out a **clear** and **unequivocal commitment** to promoting good relations. Public authorities must ensure they **comply** with all good relations actions to which they have committed to in their equality schemes. The Equality Commission will be producing further guidelines on the form and content of equality schemes as a result of the Section 75 Effectiveness Review.

Functions

- 3.8 Each public authority needs to consider what promoting good relations means in the context of their organisation and functions, so that the action it takes is tailored, relevant and appropriate. 'Functions' is the word used in the Northern Ireland Act 1998 to describe the activities of public authorities, and includes a public authority's powers and duties. Certain functions may be more relevant than others to the good relations duty under Section 75 (2). Public authorities should take care when assessing relevance, however, as many functions may not immediately appear to be relevant to the promotion of good relations. In addition, the functions of a public authority may change over time and it is important to recognise that an organisation's approach to good relations will need to be regularly reviewed to reflect its circumstances, (for example, as a result of the Review of Public Administration).

Procurement

- 3.9 Public authorities enter into large numbers of contracts with private and voluntary organisations for goods, works, services and staff. As procurement is a **function** of public authorities, regard to the desirability of promoting good relations under Section 75 (2) is required in carrying out the procurement process.
- 3.10 The Equality Commission has developed separate guidance on procurement which sets out how public authorities can build on good practice to date, and capture opportunities, learning and experience. The procurement guidance has been written at a time when the scale of investment in infrastructure in Northern Ireland offers the opportunities for significant use of the procurement process to promote good relations and equality of opportunity. Equality of opportunity and good relations are cross cutting themes which are integral to all of the procurement principles.

Screening and impact assessment

- 3.11 Section 75 provides ready-made and useful policy tools for promoting good relations. By **screening** and conducting **impact assessments**, public authorities can both address negative policy impacts (perceived or actual disadvantages), and pro-actively identify opportunities to encourage and facilitate better relationships. A public authority should therefore consider using the screening and impact assessment tools to assess how its functions, and the policies it makes and implements, affect relationships amongst the people it serves and employs.
- 3.12 Public authorities should give **greater consideration** to those functions or policies that have the **most effect** on promoting good relations between people of different religious belief, political opinion or racial group. Where changing a policy, or introducing a new policy, would significantly benefit the promotion of good relations, the need for such a change or new policy will carry added weight when balanced against other considerations.
- 3.13 Policies which impact on good relations will also have an impact on equality of opportunity. The Equality Commission's *Guide to the Statutory Duties*²⁴ recommends that any policy with an impact on good relations **should be screened in**. The screening process is not just about identifying adverse impact; **it is an opportunity to identify how to better promote equality of opportunity and good relations**.
- 3.14 Screening can help to identify what current or existing work promotes good relations, and where there is potential for further or better promotion. It therefore enables the identification of key areas or policies for strategic action to be taken. Conversely, the consideration of work or policies which have an **adverse impact** or **potential adverse impact** on good relations identifies the need for mitigating measures or alternative policies.
- 3.15 The *Guide to the Statutory Duties* states that a "systematic review of each policy is required."²⁵ One of the four screening criteria that must be considered addresses the promotion of good relations:

'Is there an opportunity to **better** promote equality of opportunity or good relations by altering the policy or working with others in government or in the larger community?'²⁶

²⁴ Guide to the Statutory Duties, p61.

²⁵ Guide to the Statutory Duties, p61.

²⁶ Guide to the Statutory Duties, p61.

Likewise, proposed policies must also be subject to screening, and the same screening criteria must be applied.

- 3.16 The Equality Commission recommends the use of the seven-step equality impact assessment (EQIA) procedure to consider whether, and how, policies have an impact on good relations, whether that impact is positive or negative, and to consider mitigating measures and alternative policies which might better promote good relations.
- 3.17 The benefits of using the impact assessment tool include the following:
- It is a useful mechanism for addressing contentious issues within a statutory framework.
 - Consultation will be inclusive and participatory, allowing all views to be expressed, heard and taken into account.
 - It enables the acknowledgement of views and impacts.
 - It provides the opportunity for an evidence-based decision-making approach.
 - It provides coherence with policy development processes in public authorities.
- 3.18 Local councils in particular have made significant efforts to progress good relations through this process; with policies regarding bilingualism, celebratory bonfires, the display of portraits of the Queen, flags and emblems including the flying of the union flag from council buildings, and community development funding, being subject to EQIAs. Other policies examined by the seven-step impact assessment process include, policies on minority languages (Department of Culture, Arts and Leisure), a policy on unauthorised encampments (Department for Social Development) and good relations and race relations policies (Further Education sector).
- 3.19 Conversely, failure to screen and conduct an equality impact assessment has been found by the Commission to be a breach of an equality scheme.

Example

In March 2007, the Equality Commission completed an investigation which concluded that a local Council had failed to comply with its equality scheme by not conducting a screening exercise, and by not conducting an equality impact assessment in relation to the

presence of an unauthorised Memorial to IRA hunger strikers which had been erected on Council-owned land. The Commission considered that although the Council was not responsible for the original placement of the Memorial on its property, it was responsible for the action taken subsequently and adopted a policy of allowing the Memorial to remain in place. The decision to dispose of the land in question is also a policy, which the Council acknowledged by screening and deciding to conduct an equality impact assessment of that decision.

In its report of the investigation the Commission states that, “the political nature of the Memorial, and its high level of visibility...may have the effect of marking the village out as Nationalist or Republican, and may not be conducive to good relations, and therefore the matter did have sufficient equality implications to be fully considered by way of equality impact assessment.

Example

In 2003, a local council conducted an equality impact assessment (EQIA) of its policy in relation to the display of the union flag and concluded that it be flown only at the council’s headquarters on the days designated by the Secretary of State in the Flags Regulations (Northern Ireland) 2000. In May 2005, as a consequence of a motion passed by the council, the union flag was flown at six council locations. The Equality Commission was concerned that the council appeared to have introduced a policy which departed from the decision arrived at following the 2003 EQIA. Following an investigation, the Equality Commission concluded that there had been a failure by the local council to comply with the commitment in its approved equality scheme to “take into account any equality impact assessment and associated consultation when making its decision with respect to a policy adopted or proposed to be adopted.” As a result of the investigation the Equality Commission recommended that the council follow the outcome of its own EQIA.

Corporate objectives

3.20 As recommended in the *Guide to the Statutory Duties*:

‘As part of the corporate planning process, objectives and targets relating to the statutory duties should be built into corporate and annual operating plans. These should be reflected at all levels of strategic planning within the organisation, including staff objectives

and annual plans. Progress on meeting objectives relating to the statutory duties should be monitored and reported upon at the most senior level within the organisation on a quarterly basis.²⁷

- 3.21 The development and inclusion of specific good relations objectives in corporate plans, as well as objectives relating to scheme implementation and the promotion of equality of opportunity, demonstrates that the organisation has given serious consideration to its role in promoting good relations in the context of its specific remit. It also ensures the inclusion of good relations work in corporate reviewing and evaluation processes. It enables it to be cascaded down into business, operational or divisional plans, and gives a focus to its inclusion in the individual objectives of employees.

Example

The corporate plans of the Staff Commission for the Education and Library Boards and the five Education and Library Boards declare that the organisation fully supports the principles of fairness, equality, accessibility, inclusivity and promotion of choice, and have as a key corporate objective or core value the promotion of equality, rights and social inclusion. Each states that objectives and targets relating to the statutory duties have been mainstreamed into the organisation's corporate and business plans and that equality objectives have been built into performance targets.

Developing and implementing a Good Relations Strategy and Action Plan

- 3.22 The Equality Commission **recommends** that public authorities develop a **Good Relations Strategy** in order to provide a clear and workable framework for, and to formalise its commitment to, the promotion of good relations between people of different religious beliefs, political opinions and racial group. This will provide a consistent and cohesive approach to the promotion of good relations throughout the organisation. Such a strategy should demonstrate that the public authority has considered what good relations means in the context of the organisation, taking into account the demography, geography, monitoring information, profile of service users, etc.; and identify the organisation's priorities and the key strategic areas in which it is most likely to be able to promote good relations.

²⁷ Guide to the Statutory Duties, Section 4, paragraph 2 (a).

3.23 The good relations strategy can be a separate strategy or part of a wider equality strategy. What is important is that it clearly reflects commitments made in equality schemes, sets out the organisation's vision for good relations in the context of its functions, allocates responsibility, demonstrates top level commitment, identifies the specific measures which it intends to take in an **action plan** with a timetable, and where appropriate, allocates dedicated resources to these measures. Progress should be monitored, reported and reviewed annually, with an emphasis on outcomes. A good relations strategy should include:

- a vision or aim (reflecting leadership);
- the key principles under-pinning the Strategy (see Chapter 2);
- an action plan to include (and clear statements of commitment to) specific measures with a timetable for implementation;
- a commitment to consultation (i.e. ongoing engagement with and participation by stakeholders);
- a commitment to the communication of the strategy;
- training plans; and performance indicators/targets; and
- a commitment to regularly monitor, review and evaluate the strategy and action plan.

Example

In January 2001, Belfast City Council (BCC) adopted promoting good relations as a corporate objective. In February 2003 the Council unanimously adopted a Good Relations Strategy, entitled 'Building Our Future Together', which was officially launched in January 2004. It was developed by a Good Relations Steering Panel made up of one Councillor from each of the six political parties on the Council, plus representatives from the churches, trades unions, business sector, minority ethnic groups and the Community Relations Council. The Good Relations Steering Panel continues to direct the work of the Good Relations Unit in equality, community relations and cultural diversity.

Good Relations Frameworks

3.24 The Equality Commission is aware of the proactive work being undertaken by public authorities using good relations frameworks, such as the *Equity, Diversity and Interdependence Framework* by Future Ways, or the Community Relations Council's *A Good Relations*

Framework. The Equality Commission endorses the use of these frameworks by public authorities in the implementation of their good relations duty, as meeting its recommendation to develop a specific strategy, plan or programme of action to promote good relations. However, it is also important that public authorities consult this Guide, and use it as a benchmark, when addressing their obligations under Section 75 (2).

- 3.25 Public authorities must determine the existing situation, identify the organisation's potential for promoting good relations in Northern Ireland, identify areas for action, draw up an action plan and regularly review and revise it. Available frameworks may greatly assist public authorities in this objective.

Example

Newry & Mourne District Council's REDI (Relationships in Equity, Diversity and Interdependence) programme was initiated with the assistance and advice of Future Ways. A detailed case study is included in Annex 1.

Example

The Probation Board for Northern Ireland (PBNI) has embarked on an initiative, 'Building a Learning Model around Good Relations', facilitated by the University of Ulster's Future Ways programme, which it regards as 'not a training but a learning project'. Following initial discussions, a staff development group was set up and prepared an action plan, which was circulated to all local teams. The achievements identified by the Board include; that good relations is now a key theme of corporate and business plans, and of staff induction; that PBNI is feeding its good relations experience into the wider criminal justice system; and that good relations is now part of the criteria for eligibility to secure Board Community Development funding.

Vision or Aim

- 3.26 Neither 'good relations' nor 'promoting good relations' is defined in legislation, nor is there a single agreed definition. Public authorities may wish to adopt a vision or aim developed by another organisation, or develop their own vision or aim for promoting good relations in the context of their organisation.

- 3.27 A vision statement may be aspirational, and need not be elaborate; it should articulate the aims of the organisation in the context of its remit and functions. However, the development of such a vision statement should not delay the identification of relevant actions to be taken.
- 3.28 A good relations vision might include a statement of commitment to the promotion of good relations, which may then be formally and publicly launched to initiate the authority's Good Relations Strategy.

Examples of visions and aims

Eastern Area Equality and Human Rights Best Practice Forum

launched its statement during Community Relations Week in 2005:

“The EHSSB is committed to the promotion of good relations between people of different religious belief, political opinion and/or racial group. As a health and social services organisation we are committed to promoting respect for diversity and to challenging sectarianism and racism in both employment and services.”

The Good Relations statement adopted by each Eastern Board Trust has been printed on to a freestanding banner and is displayed throughout each organisation at reception areas, at staff training sessions and public consultations events.

Belfast City Council - “Living and working together with understanding and respect and without fear or mistrust”.

Department of Enterprise, Trade and Investment: “Good relations is about promoting fairness, encouraging respect for difference and delivering trust between people of different religious belief, political opinion and racial group”.

Community Relations Council: “Good Relations challenges sectarianism and racism, promotes equality, develops respect for diversity and raises awareness of the interdependence of the people and institutions within NI” (CRC, A Good Relations Framework).

This has been adapted by a number of public authorities which have worked with the Community Relations Council.

The Further Education Colleges, as part of their AGREE programme, (Actioning Good Relations, Equity and Equality), “the ability to acknowledge the existence of conflict, or any tacit cultural tension, and to discuss what are often contentious issues in a safe and supportive environment”.

- 3.29 The Equality Commission’s working definition of good relations is set out in Chapter 2 of this Guide, as is the government’s vision as stated in *A Shared Future*.

Consultation

- 3.30 Like all elements of implementing the Section 75 statutory duties, consultation is key. In developing a vision, determining what is to be achieved, identifying priorities, actions and timescales, and deciding what is to be monitored and how, it is essential to obtain the views of those who are likely to be affected by the actions of the public authority. As set out earlier, consultation is a key principle of promoting good relations which should underpin the good relations strategy. Consultation with affected communities will increase the success of the strategy, as will working with the community to implement the strategy.
- 3.31 There must be a clear commitment to actively engage with affected communities at all stages, including the development, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the strategy. The Equality Commission’s Guiding Principles on Consultation, as contained in Section 2 of the *Guide to the Statutory Duties*, must be followed, and equality scheme commitments complied with. The Equality Commission is also developing guidance on consultation with children and young people.
- 3.32 It is important that the process of consultation is not a paper exercise, that is perceived to have little meaningful value. Consultees need to know that their involvement has been influential and not merely tokenistic.
- 3.33 Public authorities need to build effective working relationships, and work in partnership with communities affected by the strategy. Analysis of public authorities’ five-year reviews of equality schemes, found that the most successful consultation exercises, for example with high levels of engagement, were events organised in partnership with voluntary and community groups, particularly when staff met with people in their own venues.

Communication

- 3.34 As stated in paragraphs 2.14 – 2.20, there needs to be effective communication of the organisation's commitment to the promotion of good relations and of its strategy, as well as its progress on actions, and achieving tangible outcomes. Communication builds confidence and keeps people informed. It also enhances the image of the public authority as an organisation which is being proactive and showing visible leadership. A consistent message contributes to changing wider attitudes.
- 3.35 The Equality Commission **recommends** both external and internal communication of the draft and final good relations strategy, of the action plan and of individual initiatives; including making the strategy and action plan available on the organisation's web site and intranet, where they exist.
- 3.36 External communication can take the form of a launch, use of the media, newsletters, public statements, speeches, and press releases etc. Internal communication can include the use of staff briefings, the internet, intranet, staff and sectoral magazines, newsletters and so on. It would also include referring to and promoting the strategy, action plan and individual initiatives in business plans, meetings, staff reviews and appraisals, etc.
- 3.37 Consideration could also be given to the development and adoption of a logo or slogan, which can be used on correspondence, presentations and publications (including electronic media).

Audits

- 3.38 Many organisations have found conducting external or internal good relations **audits**, or both, to be a useful starting point in developing an action plan. Audits, in this context, are any method of systematic review which help to determine the **existing state of relationships** internally, or with customers and stakeholders, and/or to identify what current or existing work promotes good relations. They enable an organisation to identify where there is potential for further or better promotion, and therefore to identify key areas or policies for strategic action.

- 3.39 Some organisations have audited their current functions, policies and procedures in order to determine the key areas with the **greatest potential** for promoting good relations (and also those which have a negative impact on relations which could be improved with mitigating measures or alternative policies).
- 3.40 A useful starting point is for public authorities to consider the list of functions included in their approved equality scheme, and examine the potential for promoting good relations against each of these, to assess whether the carrying out of each of these functions has an impact on good relations with regard to customers, stakeholders, employees and in the wider context of Northern Ireland. It will be necessary to break functions down into their component parts and policies, to the level of action each requires. A list of areas that can be addressed can then be drawn up with a view to assessing how current implementation can be changed to better promote good relations. These can then be prioritised to form the basis of an action plan for promoting good relations.
- 3.41 Information from screening exercises and equality impact assessments, particularly from consultations on these, may provide a substantial amount of relevant information. It is **recommended** that **all policies** are screened for good relations impacts and promotional opportunities, and public authorities may wish to consider repeating previous screening exercises if originally less attention may have been given to good relations considerations, than to impact on equality of opportunity.
- 3.42 Audits may also take the form of attitude surveys amongst staff, service users and other stakeholders, which can identify issues and concerns amongst individuals and groups of people which impact on relationships.

Example

In November 2004, Derry City Council announced the commissioning of an internal audit of good relations and, based on that audit, the identification of areas for action.

Example

Armagh City and District Council established a working group, involving officers from a cross section of Council Departments (including the Community Relations Officers), to decide on a research protocol for the development of a Good Relations Strategy.

The methodology used included desk top research, questionnaire and focus groups. The questionnaire was designed to include six areas namely; community involvement, religion, political opinion, race, disability and sexual orientation. The personal data section requested details along the Section 75 categories. Two thousand questionnaires were sent on a random basis throughout the City and District with over 400 responses, and the results analysed by the Diversity & Equality Manager. From these findings, focus groups were facilitated by a firm of independent consultants. These involved public meetings and targeted consultations with 'hard to reach groups'. Focus groups were also held with Councillors and staff. The combined research has illustrated the wide 'diversity' within the City and District as well as highlighting the many positive and negative aspects of Good Relations throughout the area.

Action measures

- 3.43 Action plans should include specific measures accompanied by targets for completion or review, which the public authority commits to undertake. These can include measures which public authorities initiate, sponsor, participate in, encourage or facilitate, and can be internal or external, or both. Practical examples of action measures initiated and implemented by a variety of public authorities are included in Annex 1. Screening and impact assessment of policies which are relevant to the promotion or maintenance of good relations should be included as specific actions in plans and timetables.
- 3.44 Government departments and relevant public authorities which have a specific contribution or role under *A Shared Future* and its Triennial Action Plan, or the *Racial Equality Strategy* and its action plan, may wish to consider actions undertaken as part of those strategies to inform its future direction and priorities in promoting good relations. There should be clarity and coherence when reporting on Section 75 (2) and under *A Shared Future* action plans.

- 3.45 Some public authorities' functions are designed to promote good relations, such as Community Relations Programmes, or the District Council Good Relations Challenge Programmes proposed under *A Shared Future*²⁸; the implementation of initiatives funded by the EU Peace programmes; or the provision of grant aid in areas such as community development, peace and reconciliation, capacity building, advice and advocacy work. These measures contribute to the promotion of good relations and therefore to the implementation of the good relations duty. They may be included in good relations strategies and action plans, and should be reported upon in progress and planning review reports; as well as in Section 75 annual progress reports to the Equality Commission.
- 3.46 Public authorities also promote good relations as a by-product of other activities. Health Action Zones (HAZ), for example, bring people together in a common cause, and such positive interaction breaks down barriers and encourages better relations. The lessons which can be learned from these other initiatives can read across and/or enrich good relations work. If included in good relations strategies and action plans, the good relations objectives of such measures should be identified and reported upon.

Example

In the Northern Health and Social Services Board area, eleven Northern Neighbourhood Health Action Zone (NNHAZ) communities were represented at an innovative 'Community Cohesion' residential held in Coleraine in February 2006. Over 30 delegates attended the new training programme developed and delivered by the Northern Ireland Tenants Action Project (NITAP). The 'Community Cohesion' course is accredited by the Open College Network at Level 1 and this is the first time the course has been delivered in Northern Ireland. The two day residential course highlighted the importance of promoting community cohesion through individuals, organisations and local committees.

Participants were provided with the opportunity to learn a range of new skills, discuss issues around discrimination and explore a host of issues to promote cohesion within communities. It gave the participants an opportunity to work with people from different HAZ communities and to share their experiences and knowledge.

²⁸ www.asharedfutureni.gov.uk.

Building a good and harmonious working environment

- 3.47 In addition to promoting good relations in the community, public authorities should consider what steps they can take to promote good relations within the workplace. Public authorities should take steps to build an equality culture and create a good and harmonious workplace environment free from harassment and intimidation in which all employees are treated with dignity and respect. There are a number of practices and procedures which public authorities, as employers, should have in place in order to eliminate religious, political and racial discrimination; for example, the effective implementation of equal opportunities and harassment policies and procedures which deal appropriately with sectarian and racist behaviour in the workplace.
- 3.48 The promotion of fair participation through affirmative action programmes has led to an increase in integrated workplaces. Research has shown that people who have opportunities to meet others from different backgrounds are more likely to have friends (as opposed to colleagues or acquaintances) from different religions and ethnic groups.²⁹ *A Shared Future* identifies the development of shared workplaces and good relations in the workplace as one of its strategic priorities.

Training

- 3.49 Training for employees is one of the most important initiatives that public authorities can take to facilitate the promotion of good relations. Training ensures that employees are fully aware, and informed, of what is expected of them, and it also contributes to individual personal growth, awareness of the need to secure equal citizenship, and the benefits of a more open, diverse and intercultural society. The Commission **recommends** that all training on screening and equality impact assessment should include information on the good relations duty and its legal status effectively communicated.
- 3.50 It is recommended that public authorities ensure that senior level policy and decision-makers are fully aware of the legislative requirement to promote good relations and of the work and progress to which the organisation has committed. Board members and elected officers should likewise be fully briefed in the organisation's responsibilities and regularly updated on action and progress.

²⁹ Dickson and Hargie. Relational Communication between Catholics and Protestants in the Workplace; Osborne and Shuttleworth, Fair Employment: A Generation On, ARK Research Update 43; CRE research.

3.51 It is also particularly important that members of recruitment and selection panels, personnel staff, managers, supervisors, and front line staff receive training. Good relations affects, as well as being promoted by, every individual in an organisation. The quality of internal relationships is an essential building block to the delivery of an effective public service.

3.52 Training in good relations issues for all staff is therefore **recommended**, and should include the following:

- The legislative and policy context, as outlined in Chapter 1.
- A public authority's equality scheme and good relations strategy.
- Relevant equality legislation and Codes of Practice (including FETO, RRO and the Fair Employment and Racial Equality Codes of Practice).
- Prejudice reduction training (sectarianism and racism).
- Cultural / religious diversity awareness training (this is often most effectively delivered by people from the affected groups).

The level of detail included in training may be tailored to suit the needs of the employees attending. However, training need not only take the form of formal sessions or courses; the continual provision of information and communication of sustained commitment is also very important.

3.53 Those providing prejudice reduction training, and often also cultural and religious diversity training, should themselves have been trained in responding to sensitive and contentious issues which may be raised in the course of training.

Example

The Association of Northern Ireland Colleges (ANIC) has piloted an accredited 'training for trainers' course as part of the AGREE Programme (Actioning Good Relations, Equity and Equality), designed and delivered by Trademark. This course, accredited through the NI Open College Network at level 3, aims to build capacity within public sector organisations to deliver the required knowledge and skills based training under Section 75 (1) and (2).

Example

The Northern Ireland Housing Executive appointed two race relations training officers to design and deliver accredited 'intercultural awareness' training to its staff. It has also worked in partnership with the Northern Ireland Tenants Action Project to provide accredited Community Cohesion training to Community Associations.

Example

The Police Service of Northern Ireland (PSNI) has developed training which covers the implications of Section 75, both internally and in relation to service delivery initiatives. Specific training initiatives included Community Relationships, run jointly with Mediation Northern Ireland which focuses on community relations and promoting good relations between people of different religious beliefs and political opinion. The Community Relations Council funded the 'Living with Diversity' programmes which considered diversity, identity and conflict between the main communities in Northern Ireland. Alongside the training, a guide to culture and diversity was issued to staff in October 2004 and placed on the PSNI Intranet.

Monitoring and evaluation

- 3.54 In considering methods of monitoring and evaluating good relations actions, account should be taken of the Equality Commission's *Section 75 Monitoring Guidance for use by Public Authorities*, which includes monitoring advice on the good relations duty.
- 3.55 Like every action that a public authority takes, measures and initiatives undertaken to promote good relations must be monitored, evaluated and reviewed. The aims and objectives of an action or measure which are identified as part of its development should form the basis for its monitoring and evaluation.
- 3.56 Both the impact of an initiative, and the degree to which the objectives have been met, should be part of this process, and feedback from the evaluation of a policy in practice should inform its review and redesign. If it has not been as successful as was anticipated, further action or change to the initiative should be considered.

- 3.57 Action taken in pursuit of a good relations strategy and action plan will result in a series of outputs (for example, the creation of a Forum, undertaking a good relations training programme for staff, awareness-raising seminars / workshops or campaigns). Although it is important to monitor progress on achieving such outputs, it is vital that there is also focus on the **outcomes** of such measures (for example, the degree to which attitudes have changed, relationships have improved etc.)
- 3.58 It is particularly important therefore that there is a focus on **impact and outcomes** rather than simply outputs. Public authorities should therefore consider:
- the likely outcome or impact the measure will have on promoting good relations;
 - what monitoring information they need to collect in order to evaluate whether the outcome has been achieved; and
 - once the measure has been taken, the degree to which that outcome was achieved.
- 3.59 There can be a range of outcomes depending on the type of measures taken. Outcomes will vary depending on the good relations strategy and action plan, but could, for example, include:
- A decrease in complaints of sectarianism / racism in the workplace or of sectarian / racist incidents in the local community.
 - An increase in awareness and understanding of cultural diversity.
 - A reduction of tension and greater co-operation between different communities at interface areas.
 - An agreement about the display of flags and emblems in public spaces.
 - The development of 'shared places' used by all members of the communities.
 - Increased contact among single-identity and voluntary and community groups.
 - Increased participation of members of the BME community in community groups and public authority planning sessions.
- The growth of relationships in the workplace that seek to promote respect, equity and trust and embrace diversity.
- 3.60 Public authorities may undertake a range of qualitative monitoring techniques in order to measure progress towards defined outcomes. For example, they may decide to commission surveys to determine

attitudes to specific issues, either amongst employees or in the wider community, or use information gathered by research organisations, such as data contained in the Northern Ireland Life and Times Survey. Internal and external audits of attitudes to good relations conducted by public authorities as part of the development of good relations strategies and action plans will obviously be relevant and can be used to set baseline indicators. It may also be appropriate for a public authority to commission research in partnership with other bodies.

- 3.61 Initiatives designed to promote shared service delivery, by improving take-up by a particular community, for example, should be amenable to quantitative measurement. This will generally be related to the information which prompted the action – for example, that underuse had been identified through user or customer satisfaction surveys. The most useful information in this regard will be statistical – the number of people from different community backgrounds or racial groups who make enquiries or avail of services (including advice services, employment, grant applications and awards, etc). This may lead to research on potential barriers and on measures that would reduce them or encourage a group of people to take up the service or facility.
- 3.62 The Equality Commission recognises that certain types of outcomes may be difficult to evaluate. It can be difficult to assess if an initiative or work programme has had a direct impact on improving relationships, or how other factors, such as changes in the political environment, have had an influence. Measuring changes or improvement in relations is not easy, involving as it does changing hearts and minds, nor does the Equality Commission expect each public authority to independently assess the state of good relations in Northern Ireland.
- 3.63 Although the focus should be on outcomes, there is also a need to monitor that actions committed to are taken. This can include monitoring and reporting on numbers of employees and others who have received training (and the effectiveness of that training); the frequency of press releases and speeches referring to good relations; good relations events which have taken place; numbers of complaints received or incidents responded to indicating bad relations, and measurement of other actions included in their agreed strategy. It is important to recognise that several measures in an action plan can lead to the same outcome.

- 3.64 It should be noted that the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister has developed high level indicators for monitoring outcomes of *A Shared Future* and the *Racial Equality Strategy* and is reviewing the collection of monitoring data in relation to those indicators.

Reporting

- 3.65 Public authorities are required to detail their actions, planned and taken, and report on progress made, in their annual progress report to the Equality Commission on the implementation of Section 75 (2). The *Guide to the Statutory Duties*³⁰ states that a ‘formal report of progress should be included in the authority’s annual report or review.’
- 3.66 To demonstrate that the consideration of promoting good relations has been mainstreamed, public authorities should record how good relations has been assessed in the development and review of policies (screening and impact assessments are useful tools in this regard), including the identification of mitigations and alternative policies, and taking account of consultations in decision making processes.
- 3.67 Annual reporting on the implementation of promoting good relations not only communicates compliance with the statutory duty to the Equality Commission, to stakeholders and to the management board, it also provides a useful regular review point at which to assess the extent and effectiveness of activity and progress, and to identify further opportunities for action.
- 3.68 It is important, when reporting, to identify and acknowledge all of the work that the authority carries out which promotes and contributes to good relations in Northern Ireland. As is evident from the examples of good practice given in this guidance, good relations work can include work undertaken to meet other objectives (such as Health Action Zones or the events which bring people together), as well as measures specifically identified under Section 75 (2).
- 3.69 It is also useful to include information about future planned actions or next steps, but if these are described in an annual progress report, progress or reasons for change in plans should be reported in the following year.

³⁰ Guide to the Statutory Duties, Section 4, paragraph 2 (a).

3.70 To demonstrate compliance with Section 75 (2), reporting should be in relation to initiatives and measures taken to promote good relations between people of different religious belief, political opinion and racial group. As stated in Chapter 3, the Equality Commission supports the promotion of good relations between members of other Section 75 categories, for example in relation to addressing homophobia, although public authorities are not required under Section 75 (2) to do so.

Chapter 4 – Role of the Equality Commission

Duties

- 4.1 Under Schedule 9(1) of the **Northern Ireland Act 1998**, the Equality Commission has a duty to:
- (a) keep under review the effectiveness of the duties imposed by Section 75;
 - (b) offer advice to public authorities and others in connection with those duties; and
 - (c) carry out the functions conferred on it by Schedule 9.

Complaints and investigations

- 4.2 Under Schedule 9, paragraphs (10) and (11), the Equality Commission has the power to investigate complaints, and to initiate investigations in respect of a failure to comply with an equality scheme.

Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order 1997

- 4.3 Article 42 of the **Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order 1997** (as amended) (RRO) places duties on the Equality Commission:
- (a) to work towards the elimination of discrimination;
 - (b) to promote equality of opportunity, and good relations between people of different racial groups; and
 - (c) keep the legislation under review.

Fair Employment and Treatment (NI) Order 1998

- 4.4 Under Article 7 of the Fair Employment and Treatment Order 1998 (as amended) (FETO), there is a duty on the Equality Commission to:
- (a) to promote equality of opportunity;
 - (b) to promote affirmative action;
 - (c) to work for the elimination of unlawful discrimination; and
 - (d) keep the legislation under review.

Information, advice and training

- 4.5 Information and practical guidance on implementing the good relations duty (including advice on consultation, screening and impact assessment), is available from the Equality Commission. Public authorities can also obtain information and advice on their responsibilities under the fair employment and race equality legislation; including information on measures they can take to eliminate unlawful discrimination and harassment on the grounds of religious belief, political opinion or racial grounds. In addition, guidance is also available on how public authorities, as employers, can promote a good and harmonious work environment as recommended in the *Fair Employment Code of Practice*.
- 4.6 The Commission provides a telephone advisory service and produces a range of advisory publications (including the *Guide to the Statutory Duties*, the *Fair Employment Code of Practice*, *Race Equality Code of Practice*, *Audit of Progress on the Good Relations Duty 2000-2003*, and *Good Relations in Practice: A Report of Progress on the Good Relations Duty 2003-2005*) which can be obtained free of charge from the Commission, or downloaded from its website (www.equalityni.org). The Commission also provides free and confidential training on the equality legislation.

Annex 1

Case Studies and Examples of Good Practice

Introduction

This Annex outlines in detail case studies of three public authorities from different sectors who have shown a clear commitment to the promotion of good relations within the context of their own particular functions, remit and circumstances. By implementing a range of innovative measures, they have demonstrated a desire to go beyond mere compliance with equality and good relations duties under Section 75 and placed both equality of opportunity and good relations at the heart of their public policy decision making.

The case studies are followed by a number of examples of good practice from across the public sector in Northern Ireland. Further examples of implementation of the Section 75 (2) good relations duty are available in the Equality Commission's publications *Audit of Progress on the Good Relations Duty 2000-2003*, and *Good Relations in Practice: A Report of Progress on the Good Relations Duty 2003-2005*.

As mentioned above the measures taken reflect the unique functions remit and circumstances of each of the three individual authorities. Therefore not all of the measures outlined will be appropriate to every public authority. Each public authority should assess, (when having regard to the desirability of promoting good relations), in light of its own particular functions, powers and duties and circumstances, which measures are most appropriate and effective in promoting good relations.

Case Studies

Association of Northern Ireland Colleges (ANIC)

In response to the requirements of Section 75, the 16 colleges of further and higher education have adopted a co-ordinated approach. One central body, the Association of Northern Ireland Colleges (ANIC) provided each college with a common approach to organizational change, a strategy and a training package as well as pro forma responses for the colleges' annual reports to the Equality Commission.

The AGREE Programme

The **A.G.R.E.E Programme** (Actioning Good Relations, Equality and Equity) was a four year strategy (2002 – 2006), funded by the Community Relations Council, and developed by Trademark in partnership with ANIC, which sought to ensure that equity and respect for difference are placed at the heart of day-to-day life in further education colleges in Northern Ireland.

ANIC was established in 1998 following the incorporation of the Colleges of Further Education in Northern Ireland. It is a limited company with charitable status. The Board of Directors represents the Association's memberships and comprises Directors of Institutions and Chairs of Governors.

The ANIC Equality Policy and Research Unit was introduced in March 2002 to assist colleges in meeting the provisions of Section 75 and other equality legislation, and in aiding colleges to comply with this process through a co-ordinated approach.

PROJECT AIMS:

The aims of the AGREE programme were as follows:-

- to ensure that equity and respect for difference are placed at the heart of the college's structures, systems and cultures;
- to go beyond complying with legislation by ensuring organisational commitment to mainstreaming the principles and practices of equity, diversity and interdependence through a process of organisational change;

- to develop/implement “an inclusive and innovative change programme” which will look at how the FE sector might more fully engage with s 75 considerations; and to model approaches which will allow for the mainstreaming of same over time; and
- to assist colleges to implement the seven steps of organisational change:
 - 1) Invitation.
 - 2) To establish critical dialogue.
 - 3) To growing leadership commitment and understanding.
 - 4) To identify the issues.
 - 5) Growing commitment and understanding across the wider organisation.
 - 6) Experimenting and modelling of new working practices.
 - 7) Implementing new models of practice into mainstream structures and relationships.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The AGREE programme had the following objectives which were met:-

Step 1:

To establish a Project Working Group (to agree a plan of work for Year 1).

Step 2:

To establish a Development Group which is representative of all current college structures (x24 Members involved in real dialogue about issues of conflict and division).

To establish a Community Education Forum (x16 Members involved in dialogue).

Step 3:

To bring both the formal and informal leadership into new conversations around the principles of fairness and valuing difference (x24 Members of Development Group, x16 Members of Equality Forum, x16 Community Education Forum Members, x16 Board of Directors, x16 Governors, x16 Trade Union Members, x16 Student Executives, x4 Working Group Members).

To recruit (over x6 days) and train a cohort of tutor/facilitators to undertake the preparation, strategic planning, deliver and evaluation of appropriate training course in relation to s 75 (1) & (2) (x16 College representatives).

To develop and deliver an accredited OCN training course on “Equality & Good Relations” – suggested modules: Equality Legislation, Understanding Equity, Diversity and Interdependence, Anti-sectarianism, Anti-racism, Strategic Planning and Programme Design, Delivery and Evaluation.

Step 4:

To carry out an audit of programmes and activities (relating to issues of community relations, peace building and ED & I across the FE & H sector over x5 days).

To carry out a number of baseline scoping studies and action research into ‘organisational culture’.

To produce accompanying materials.

Step 5:

To engage with the various inter-college groups and structures and deliver a programme of dialogue.

To assist in the development of a training strategy for the colleges (senior staff, student representatives and others from the FE sector) to meet requirements under Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998.

To develop plans to implement a framework of organisational change based on the inclusive principles of equity, diversity and interdependence.

Step 6:

To experiment with, and model, new working practices, policies, structures and support mechanisms.

Step 7:

To implement new models of practice into mainstream structures and relationships.

A key objective was to provide mechanisms and methodologies which will allow community relations/considerations to become a self-renewing/sustaining feature of further education in NI.

PROJECT OUTCOMES:

Outlined below are the outcomes of the programme:

- The establishment of new structures within colleges to deal with equality specifically, e.g. College Equality Working Groups.
- The recruitment and development of Equality Trainers.
- Development and delivery of OCN accredited programme “Equality and Good Relations Trainers Programme” to college staff. This programme was further developed by Trademark and delivered to other public sector bodies.
- The delivery of general awareness training.
- The identification of equality issues within individual colleges.
- The development of training materials.
- Sharing and development of good practice and equality initiatives through the establishment of equality structures.
- Cultural diversity and good relations are now included as elements of student induction and in some student curriculums.
- Growing confidence, knowledge and experience within further education to allow for the continuation of steps taken through the AGREE Programme.

Throughout the life of the programme, colleges were provided with opportunities to build capacity, and to challenge and overcome the politeness and denial that characterises individual and organisational approaches to the fundamental divisions that exist within this society, and the increasing demands faced in dealing with an endemic and increasingly active racism.

Through the various strands of the programme this project has directly intervened in the political and cultural life of the colleges, in an attempt to bring the development of positive community relationships from the periphery to the mainstream of organisational policy and practice.

A cumulative total of 2797 participants were involved in the various activities during the three year programme. Activities included:

- Equality and good relations awareness training.
- Training & support for college equality working groups.
- Research interviews.

- Student workshops/ training.
- Residential.
- Consultation regarding relevant college equality issues.
- Anti-harassment training.
- Staff surveys.
- Policy development.

Cultural Diversity Projects

In addition to the AGREE Programme in 2003, the Department for Employment and Learning provided financial support totalling £150,000 (£50,000 per pilot) for three Cultural Diversity pilot projects, which were completed in March 2005. The purpose of supporting the pilots was primarily to promote “Cultural Diversity / Good Relations” in the Northern Ireland further education (FE) sector, by providing opportunities for students and staff from differing identities, backgrounds and traditions to develop and enhance relationships of trust and understanding, and promote mutual respect in every aspect of college life. The four colleges involved were Armagh College, Belfast Institute, North West Institute and Upper Bann Institute.

Next Steps - Dissemination Programme

Following completion of the pilots, the Department has decided to provide financial support to the six new area based Colleges to facilitate the dissemination and roll out of Cultural Diversity/Good Relations best practice identified by:

- the Education and Training Inspectorate, in their report on the above Cultural Diversity Pilot Initiatives; and
- MORI Ireland/ Deloitte, in their “Chill Factor” FE research project, commissioned by ANIC.

A total of £300,000 has been made available for this purpose between November 2006 -07.

Whilst each dissemination programme is specific to the local context, generic activities include:

- the collation and analysis of data on potential and actual learners from minority ethnic groups;

- the development and introduction of codes of good practice for staff and students in relation to cultural diversity;
- the engagement of students and representatives from groups reflecting a wide range of cultures and traditions in the development of whole-college policies on good relations;
- the introduction of induction programmes for students and staff, focused on cultural diversity;
- the completion of a full curriculum audit to identify where formal cultural diversity activities are integrated effectively into the curriculum, and to incorporate issues of cultural diversity and equal opportunity into quality assurance and course review processes; and
- the review of marketing and promotional materials, including prospectuses, to ensure that they portray, and are effective in recruiting, a diverse group of students.

ANIC is also currently undertaking research, funded by the Department for Employment and Learning, into racism in further education. Findings were due in October 2007. In addition, ANIC are developing a race equality plan in partnership with colleges and in conjunction with the Equality Commission.

The Royal Hospitals

The Royal Hospitals has developed and implemented a programme of work to promote good relations. The programme operates along four strands, with the theme of 'Action in Partnership' running through each.

Strand 1: Employees

The Royal Hospitals made the commitment to the promotion of good relations in its annual management plan. The work is overseen by the Royal Equality Steering Group, chaired by the Chief Executive. A Good Relations Working Group comprising of management and trade unions was established to take the issue forward. It was agreed that a good relations audit of the organisation would be carried out. Advice was sought from the Futureways Unit at the University of Ulster and the Community Relations Council. An

audit was carried out and a series of staff and trade union dialogue groups were held. The focus was on good relations in the workplace. A range of work was carried out as a result of this joint project. This work has included:

1. The development and implementation of a “Working Well Together” policy by management and trade unions. This policy recognises that all staff must accept that as individuals they have differences and they can create the possibility of Working Well Together in a harmonious environment that is characterised by fair treatment. This is essential to the well-being of all employees, patients and service users. It states that a harmonious environment free from conflict is something for which all staff have responsibility. It highlights the importance of respect, dignity and positive interpersonal behaviour and the role of trade unions in developing this in partnership. This policy is used as a basis for good relations in the workplace along with the Joint Declaration of Protection.
2. The establishment of an Equal Opportunities Joint Forum, where staff and trade union representatives discuss issues impacting on equal opportunities and good relations and devise new policies.
3. A Staff Diversity Group where staff and trade union representatives address issues of racial harassment occurring inside and outside the Trust and promote sources of support through the Royal magazine, intranet and other media.
4. Staff training on equal opportunities (compulsory for staff every three years), good relations and working well together. This training is evaluated for effectiveness.
5. The launch of a Good Relations Statement in March 2005 by the Eastern Area Best Practice Forum, of which the Royal Hospitals is a member.

Strand 2: Ethnic Minority Groups

The Royal Hospitals conducted a 3 year project aimed at improving health and developing awareness of the Irish Traveller Community among Royal Hospitals staff. The project included an accredited course for eight Traveller women on health issues and services. A Traveller Health Needs assessment was carried out to assess the health needs of the Traveller Community and a staff survey was conducted to identify training and information needs. These surveys identified a need to facilitate dialogue about services between Travellers and hospital staff outside health crisis situations. A series of 10

visits were planned and carried out to key service areas to allow a two-way exchange of information between Travellers and hospital staff. Visits were structured to show the “journey” patients and staff go on when someone attends the service. The visits aimed to improve understanding and promote good relations. Feedback was obtained from Traveller participants through semi-structured interviews and was very positive. One participant said: “We finally got to see what goes on behind the closed doors and why.” Hospital staff have also undertaken further training on Traveller Culture. Feedback on this strand was obtained via surveys and was very positive. Formal evaluation of the programme is planned to report in 2007.

Royal Hospitals’ staff from ethnic minority backgrounds have contributed to initiatives promoting good relations in partnership with trade unions and community groups. This has included giving talks at events in the Department of Health, the Eastern Health & Social Services Board and Belfast City Council. More locally, staff have given talks in local schools, community centres and women’s groups. Local communities have taken an active role in tackling racism in the West Belfast area and held a conference on tackling racism. Royal Hospitals ran a workshop for the local community entitled “Overseas Staff at the Royal – Facts and Fiction” to dispel myths about overseas staff. This workshop was very well received and has led to further partnership work on racism with local communities, including a Belfast wide anti-racism conference. Royal Hospitals’ staff participated in training on cultural diversity in partnership with ethnic minority sector organisations, which has been mainstreamed within its “Learning for Excellence” corporate training brochure.

In 2005-2006, over 230 employees attended training specifically on cultural diversity within The Royal Hospitals, while 1587 employees attended training on a range of diversity and equality issues during the same period. 99% of participants evaluated the training as either good or very good.

Strand 3: Communities

A number of projects going on within the Royal Hospitals have had good relations elements built into them. These included a cross-community playtherapy project involving staff, children and parents from two childcare centres and two schools (one Protestant and one Catholic) located in South and West Belfast. Staff from the two centres came together on the Royal site for an eight week training course on how to develop skills in therapeutic play. Visits to the Royal Belfast Hospital for Sick Children were included in the project for the childcare staff and parents. Good relations was a theme

built into the project by the joint community – hospital steering group as despite providing similar services, these childcare staff had never worked or trained together before.

Evaluation of Programme

Measures were established to develop an evaluation framework for the project elements.

Project Element	Baseline	Mid-Point	End
Staff training course	Baseline Survey Staff meetings Assessment of training & development needs Site visits to centres	Mid-point survey Weekly feedback on benefits of equipment “lending library”	Post-project evaluation survey Interviews with childcare centre managers
Parents training course	Baseline Survey Informal meetings	Evaluation surveys	Evaluation surveys Interviews with childcare centre managers
Hospital Visits	Baseline Survey	Evaluation surveys	Evaluation survey
School Sessions	Baseline interviews with teachers in both schools Identification of participants by teachers	Records kept of child’s progress by teachers Weekly feedback from teachers	Post project evaluation interviews with teachers

Measures for evaluating the good relations aspects of the project were built into the overall evaluation. Baseline, mid-point and post-project surveys and interviews were carried out. Over two-thirds of participants stated in evaluation that doing the course with staff from another community centre was beneficial. All participants rated the visits to the Children’s Hospital as beneficial; over half the participants had never visited the hospital before.

This project was highly commended as good practice in Corporate Social Responsibility by the Belfast Telegraph Business Awards in April 2005. It was also commended by Business in the Community in their Healthy Communities Awards. A video presentation of this project was made to senior staff within the Royal Hospitals highlighting the benefits to a range of groups.

The Royal Hospitals organised two information days which took place in May

2005 in the Sandy Row and Donegall Road areas. The days were planned in partnership with Belfast City Council Community Development Workers and South Belfast Highway to Health. The aim of the events was to introduce services and employment opportunities at the Royal Hospitals to communities who may not have been aware of them. The Royal Hospitals aims to increase employment of members of the Protestant community in a range of departments. Royal Jubilee Maternity Service, Royal Belfast Hospital for Sick Children Play Department, Health Promotion and the Human Resources Department held information workshops.

Current job vacancies were advertised along with application forms. Both information days were evaluated using questionnaires. 59% of participants at both sessions said they would be interested in employment at the Royal Hospitals (this figure was 80% at the Donegall Road event). Respondents were asked if the information day had influenced their outlook on the Royal Hospitals and its services. 100% of respondents at both events replied “Yes”. Respondents were asked if their view of the Royal Hospitals was more positive, more negative or had not changed. 86% of participants at both events stated that their view of the Royal Hospitals was more positive, 7% had no change and 3% stated more negative. 65% of respondents said they would be interested in participating in future consultations on services and issues at the Royal Hospitals.

Strand 4: Regional

The Royal Hospitals has benefited from being part of the City Bridges Trade Union Good Relations project. This has facilitated partnerships between The Royal and Letterkenny General Hospital with exchange visits of staff side and management side employees to discuss good relations issues. This involved Royal Hospitals staff speaking at a conference on Good Relations in the Workplace hosted by City Bridges.

The Royal has also had working relationships with Beaumont Hospital, Dublin, Mayo General Hospital and Bradford Royal Infirmary, where good relations has been a theme. The Royal Hospitals is a member of the Eastern Area Best Practice Sub-Group on Good Relations and meets with partners to discuss the issue including Community Relations Council, Counteract and Trademark. A seminar on good relations was hosted by the Eastern Health and Social Services Board in which the Royal Hospitals participated.

Newry and Mourne District Council

Council Context

Newry and Mourne District Council is the fourth largest Council in Northern Ireland with a population in excess of 90,000 people.

It has three quite distinct areas: Newry City, South Armagh and the Mournes. Each of these areas has quite distinct cultures and identities.

Given the considerable geographic spread of the communities and the land mass of the Mourne Mountains, there has been a tendency for communities within the district to develop separately from one another adding the perception of remoteness felt by some of the communities in the district.

The district as a whole is recognised as having developed significantly in economic and social terms in the past fifteen years, although as Noble indices indicate, there are still considerable pockets of severe multiple deprivation within the area.

Community Relations

Community relations in Newry and Mourne District has evolved over a considerable period of time. Newry and Mourne District Council participated fully within the District Council Community Relations Programme and a core programme in the evolutionary process of good relations has been the Relationships in Equity, Diversity and Interdependence initiative (REDI).

REDI

REDI (Relationships in Equity Diversity and Interdependence) was a pilot initiative which began in 1998. It was facilitated by two external partners, Future Ways, based at the University of Ulster, and Counteract, the anti-intimidation group set up by the Irish Congress of Trade Unions.

REDI centered upon mainstreaming community relations principles and had internal and external dimensions. It was about naming and dealing with the challenges that a local Council faces operating within a politically contested society, and focused upon how the Council acted as:

- a civic leader;
- an employer; and

- a deliverer of services.

In essence REDI was about learning the best ways for working and living together in the same place with different people. REDI integrated the two themes of community relations, and organisational change and learning through dealing with the issues of:

- **Equity** – making sure people from all parts of the community are treated fairly.
- **Diversity** – respecting and understanding of differences between people.
- **Interdependence** – recognising how decisions we take affect others, and how others' actions impact on us as people and as an organisation.

A scoping study resulted in the establishment of the following:

- REDI Development Group
 - Consisting of employees from all levels, elected representatives, trade unions, and management, all on an equal footing.
 - An informal space.
- Trade Union Working Group
 - Providing a direct voice in the process and legitimised their role as communication channels between the workforce and the Development Group.
- REDI Leadership Group
 - 12 employees - undertook 6-day training programme.
 - To increase knowledge and skills for those who were advocates of REDI.
 - Creating 'champions' who could influence the informal networks and relationships that shape the organisation.
- REDI Elected Representatives Group
 - All Councillors meeting on a quarterly basis to discuss issues relating to their role as civic leaders.
 - Facilitated by Dr Duncan Morrow.
 - No media presence allowed Councillors to engage fully in honest and frank dialogue.
- Community Relationships Forum
 - External dimension.
 - Facilitating community dialogue / discussion.
 - Brought together unionist, nationalist and republican stakeholders.

Outputs / Successes of REDI

- Underpinned by the full support of the Clerk and Chief Executive
To move Community Relations 'to the centre'.
- A Declaration of Principles
 - Agreed, supported and endorsed by the employees, elected representatives, trade unions and management within Newry and Mourne District Council.
- Creation of the Council's Equality Unit located within the Administration Department
 - Brought together Best Value, Community Relations, Equality, PR and Communication.
 - Places these issues strategically at the heart of service delivery, decision making and policy development.
- Anti-sectarian / Anti-harassment Training for all employees
 - Dignity at Work Policy.
 - Harassment Advisors.
- Training for Supervisors and Managers
- Diversity Training for all employees
- Greater consultation with employees and increased opportunities for employees, especially those in the minority group, to have a 'voice'
 - Employee Survey.
 - Open Spaces – participative consultation.
 - Equality Consultation process on policies.
 - Helping the Council be seen as one which 'listens and values' people's views.
- Greater input by employees into new policies and procedures
 - Participants in the REDI Development Group had the opportunity to think as 'leaders' not 'lowly workers'.
 - Building trust and helping employees understand they are valued members of Council whose input and contribution is valued.
- New thinking in terms of policy development and implementation
 - Family Friendly Policies.
 - Creation of a Corporate Press Office.

- New voluntary Contributions Application Process with proofing mechanism to create a strategically targeted and focused system.
- Increased communication between employees and management.
- The Council was ready and prepared to embrace new legislative requirements such as Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998.

Towards the future

REDI had allowed space for a level of critical dialogue to develop and contributed towards building relationships in the workplace through defining a sense of ownership of the decision-making process across the organisation. Building on the success of REDI, the ongoing challenge for Newry and Mourne District Council as a civic leader was how it treats those who feel marginalized or excluded from the centre.

The Council acknowledged it needed to maintain momentum and commitment to the process whilst recognising the Council itself, is a transient structure with Councillors presenting themselves to the voters every four years. In this context, the dilemma for the political representatives was negotiating the party political function and their civic leadership role.

It was important to further integrate the principles of community relations through influencing decision makers in how they develop policy and deliver services. Therefore, the Council's policy should be both strategic and proactive in identifying and providing practical solutions to emerging problems.

Community Relations Audit

In moving forward, the Council commissioned an independent review of the Council's Community Relations Programme.

A Community Relations Audit was undertaken in 2003 to examine the work undertaken within REDI, the emerging policy context and future implications for local government. The audit, undertaken in consultation with the community and Council, was the evolutionary pathway of definitively moving from the community relations to the good relations context.

The Community Relations Audit re-defined the Council's Community Relations Programme in the Newry and Mourne area as:

‘enabling the continued development of an inclusive district through the building of good relations and trust thereby enabling mutual understanding and respect for the diverse cultures and heritages of the district’.

In addition, the audit recommended Council should reconsider the allocation of staff resources, to reflect there are two distinct elements, internal and external, of the Community Relations programme in Newry and Mourne. It recommended the Council consider that the internal and external programmes be implemented by two separate staff members of equal grading, rather than the existing structure of having a Community Relations Officer and an Assistant.

This resulted in a restructuring of the Good Relations Section to have an Internal Good Relations Officer and External Good Relations Officer to assist with the mainstreaming of good relations both within and outside of Council. The Officers continued to be located at the heart of Council activity within the Equality Unit of the Administration Department.

The Good Relations Section operates primarily within the statutory duty of Section 75 (2) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998. Progressing the good relations duty has required taking into consideration new policies and frameworks established by central government such as the ‘Racial Equality Strategy’ and ‘A Shared Future’. In addition, the Good Relations Section is preparing itself for the new Challenge Programme through the Community Relations Council, as opposed to the Community Relations Unit in OFMDFM, and the pending Review of Public Administration.

Good Relations Strategic Plan

Newry and Mourne District Council’s Good Relations Strategic Plan has four aims:

- To encourage greater understanding within the community in Newry and Mourne.
- To enable the Council make decisions and deliver services recognizing the impact of its actions.
- To encourage the development of civic capacity.
- To continually improve the capacity of the Good Relations team to provide a quality service.

Key elements of the Council's programme of work include:

1. The Good Relations Forum

Newry and Mourne District Council is committed to facilitating and co-ordinating community discussion and dialogue. The Newry Good Relationships Forum, co-ordinated by the External Good Relations Officer, is widely regarded as a model of good practice both in Northern Ireland and also in Great Britain.

The aim of the Good Relations Forum is to positively contribute to good relations in Newry between people of different political, religious and ethnic background and improving relationships between Newry and other parts of the district of Newry and Mourne. This forum provides 'quiet' space for citizens of the Newry area to discuss, debate and challenge perceptions so enabling participants to improve understanding both their own and other participant's views on issues impacting upon the area.

The Forum, facilitated by Mediation Northern Ireland and Council Officers, involves a cross section of District Councillors, Officials of Newry and Mourne District Council and citizens of the Newry area.

During 2005, members of the Good Relations Forum participated in the three cities programme which included Newry, Belfast and Amsterdam. A field study trip to Amsterdam enabled members to see how others have addressed their issues of challenge. This helped to develop members capacity to consider local issues within a wider context and, through the sharing good practice, members have gained an ability to turn hindsight into foresight. This culminated in June 2006 with the 'Challenge of Change Convention', which was a three-day convention about diversity in a society still struggling with division. This was organised by Newry and Mourne District Council and Belfast City Council in association with Louth County Council, and facilitated by mediation Northern Ireland.

2 The Elected Members Forum

This is co-ordinated by the Internal Good Relations Officer. Working in partnership with the Community Relations Council, it is facilitated by Dr Duncan Morrow and operates under Chatham House rules.

The aim of the Forum is to provide the elected representatives (Councillors) with an opportunity to engage in a facilitated discussion about good relations based issues outside of the Chamber with no press present. This allows for

meaningful engagement between the elected members, and also provides an opportunity to familiarise Members with current good relations legislation, policies and frameworks in terms of Newry and Mourne such as 'A Shared Future' and the 'Racial Equality Strategy'.

3. Good Relations Grant Programme

The Good Relations Section has created a targeted and focused Good Relations Grant Scheme which has a clear evaluation process to identify benefits and outcomes of projects funded through the Good Relations budget.

The Good Relations Small Grants Scheme is administered through the External Good Relations Officer and is available for community groups throughout the District. It provides the community with the opportunity to receive funding for innovative Good Relations projects, which are single identity, cross community and cultural diversity.

Newry and Mourne District Council have also amended their Voluntary Contributions assessment process, and a project's impact in terms of promoting good relations is one of the ten criteria used when assessing applications seeking funding. In addition, members of the Equality Unit sit on the Assessment Team which evaluates all funding applications.

4. Work with ethnic minorities

Newry and Mourne District Council has been proactive in hosting information evenings across the Council area. These information evenings, attended by elected members and representatives of local service providers, provide an opportunity for members of our BME community to meet decision-makers. The meet and greet sessions have included meeting with representatives of, and providing financial assistance for, the Newry Polish Resource Centre.

In addition the Council has produced a directory of local services including a breakdown of Council services in six different languages. An Anti-Racism project has also been undertaken in partnership with the SELB Youth Service with young people from the Newry area. The Council's Well Being Action Partnership have also secured funding for Policy and Project workers in the specific field of ethnic minorities.

5. Youth based activities

School Information Pack

During 2003/2004 the Council produced a Teachers' Information Pack for Schools. This introduced young people to the Council, and the issues of citizenship, culture and diversity. The accompanying Work Pack was designed in conjunction with teachers, and the Council continues to also run events to complement the Pack to reinforce the meaning of diversity for the schoolchildren.

The Pack received an Opportunity Now Award in 2005 under the Good Relations category. The Pack, which is in loose-leaf format for updating, includes information on local history, culture, diversity, citizenship and the local environment. Each primary school in the Newry and Mourne area received a number of Packs with backup support service from the Equality Unit. Feedback from teachers has indicated they find it to be a useful tool which complements the young peoples' learning process.

Allsorts Project (2005/2006) and Photographic Youth Project (2006)

Run by the Good Relations Section in conjunction with the Community Safety Partnership and Youth Service, involving the Bosco Youth Club and members of the Travelling Community, the Allsorts Project explored issues and personal experiences of prejudice and discrimination. The culmination of the project was the publication of a book by the young people. It is envisaged this initiative will be replicated across the Council area in the future.

The Photographic Youth Project was a youth initiative through the Good Relations Programme where twenty young people from across the Council area were asked to take photographs of issues of importance affecting them. The young people then presented this to Councillors.

Local Democracy Week

In recognition of its civic leadership function, Newry and Mourne District Council takes an active role in promoting Local Democracy Week. This enables opportunities for meaningful engagement and valuable discussion between Councillors and young people through various projects such as the 'I'm a Councillor Get Me out of Here' project which was run in 2006.

Youth Forum

At present, a Youth Forum is being developed in partnership with the SELB Youth Service for the whole of the District. Through the partnership approach participants are provided with the opportunity to engage in issues which are important to them in terms of their community and the services provided therein.

In addition to the activities above, the Good Relations Section continues to provide advice, support and training opportunities for employees, individuals, groups and organisations. Sharing of best practice within the community takes place through the External Good Relations Officer. This is through partnership working on various groups for example, Community Safety Partnership, Drugs and Alcohol Partnership.

Influencing policy and enabling informed decision-making remains a key cornerstone, and the Council's Good Relations Officers participate on numerous committees such as the St Patrick's Day Committee, Ulster Scots Committee, and projects delivered through Newry Museum, the Irish Language Section, Community Safety Partnership, Neighbourhood Renewal Partnership, Local Strategy Partnership and Community Services Section (Community Support Plan).

While Newry and Mourne District Council has provided examples of programmes of work, it should be acknowledged the programme is always work in progress. The Council believes that working to maintain sustainable relationships is the key principle underpinning civic society and initiatives centred around structured dialogue processes such as household panels, community forums and Councillor forums are pathways to this.

Examples of Good Practice

Outlined below are examples of some measures taken by a range of public authorities to promote good relations, in the context of their own particular remit and functions.

Discussing contentious issues

In July 2001 concerns were raised over the flying of flags across Ballymena Borough. Following approval from Ballymena Borough Council, Counteract, a mediation organisation set up to address sectarianism and conflict issues, was engaged to work with the Council in attempting to resolve this contentious and difficult issue. A Pilot Scheme was set up in the Fisherwick and Harryville areas in order to give residents an opportunity to discuss the medium to long term vision for the overall improvement of their areas, in addition to correct and influence external views of the Borough's image generally.

Development of a local area Good Relations Strategy

Ballymena Borough Council, through its Good Relations Unit, facilitated the production of a Good Relations Strategy for the Dunclug Estate. The strategy addressed priority issues such as the display of flags and emblems and the image of the estate, and the relationships between different communities (including minority ethnic communities) and different community associations.

This initiative was developed out of a consultation process initiated in Dunclug by Ballymena Local Strategic Partnership. Three sub-groups were developed, including a Crime and Community Safety Sub-Group, which agreed in 2006 to conduct a survey, commissioned by the council, among a sample of residents within the estate in order to seek their views on a range of issues related to community relations in the area. The initiative had the full support of the Dunclug and District Residents' Association together with Dunclug Partnership and Ballymena Community Safety Partnership.

Inter-Ethnic Support Group and Forum

As part of its Ethnic Minorities Project, launched in 2002, Ballymena Borough Council has facilitated an Inter-Ethnic Support Group and Forum aimed at organising a wide range of support services for its increasing minority ethnic population. The Council's aim is to empower people who are currently marginalised and bring an awareness of all cultural traditions into the mainstream of the Council's deliberations on the design and delivery of all its activities.

Ethnic Minorities Support Project

Ballymoney Borough Council is implementing an Ethnic Minorities Support Project which is funded by OFMDFM Racial Equality Unit. The stated aim of the project is "to develop the capacity and increase the equality of opportunity of all ethnic minority communities in Ballymoney Borough". The project employs an Ethnic Minorities Support Worker to audit the needs of various minority communities and to develop capacity and build relationships with participant communities. The project works in partnership with other stakeholders, including the Council, to develop information on services available in the local area and to ensure that these services can be more easily accessed. It works with ethnic minority communities and the wider community, to promote cultural diversity and awareness, and supports needs within the Borough.

'Youth in Community' project

Corrymeela Community's 'Youth in Community' project is a cutting edge programme of personal and social development enabling young adults (18-25) from highly marginalised areas to develop and facilitate their own modular community relations/good relations programmes. The project focuses on the Section 75 agenda, and is based on the principles of equity, diversity and interdependence. The project begins by focusing on each young adult's personal identity. This 'identity' module is integral and essential to the whole programme.

The project is funded by the Youth Education Social Inclusion Partnership (YESIP), a consortium of twelve partners from the Northern Ireland education sector, as part of the EU Peace II programme for peace and reconciliation.

Building relationships at an interface

The Suffolk and Lenadoon Interface Group, which was funded by a number of sources, including the International Fund for Ireland, Community Relations Council, Belfast City Council, NIHE and Department for Social Development, was established in 1997 in order to build relationships between the two interface communities of Suffolk and Lenadoon in Belfast. They developed and implemented an agreed plan linked into key strategies, such as *A Shared Future* and the Neighbourhood Renewal Strategy, aimed at developing shared activities, shared spaces and shared services within the two communities. The Group received an award from the British Urban Regeneration Association in 2003 for best practice in community regeneration.

Collaboration and sharing good practice

An education conference brought together senior personnel from the Community Relations Branch of the Department of Education, the five Education and Library Boards and the University of Ulster, with teachers from across Northern Ireland in a shared commitment to enhancing the effectiveness of Community Relations Education. The two-day event involved workshops, speakers, drama sessions, discussion groups and recommendations on the way forward. In evaluating the course participants said they had been “jolted out of their comfort zone, re-energised and had enjoyed the opportunity to share in the dissemination of good practice.”

Collaboration and sharing good practice

A two day ‘Sharing Good Practice: Race, Equality and Diversity Regional Conference’ was run in partnership with six other councils, under the Regional Community Relations Officer Forum (Ballymoney, Limavady, Coleraine, Moyle, Londonderry and Magherafelt). The Conference focused on two inter-related themes; the first day examined the roles, responsibilities and capacity of the statutory and business sectors to work within a diverse society and address the issue of accessibility; the second day focused on sharing models of good practice. Workshops included education for diversity, community sector models which work well, diversity in communities, civic leadership, making the business case, migrant workers myth-busting and community safety.

Cultural awareness raising

Belfast City Council have organised a range of cultural events aimed at encouraging understanding of and respect for different cultural expressions and needs. They have also funded a range of community relations cultural delivery projects, including the Irish Football Association's anti-racism and anti-sectarianism initiative.

Development of a Good Relations Plan

Belfast City Council, as part of an initiative under *A Shared Future*, and in partnership with a number of public authorities (including NIHE, the Department for Social Development and the Health Trusts) has developed a Good Relations Plan for Belfast, with the aim of making Belfast a 'shared city'.

Working in partnership with the local community

Craigavon and Banbridge HSS Trust launched a new mural at Russell Drive, Lurgan, one of the Trust's facilities, in June 2006. The mural, which depicts Lurgan Workhouse, is the result of a good relations initiative. The project involved partnership working between Mourneview and Grey Estate Community Association, Craigavon & Banbridge Community HSS Trust and Play Resource Centre, Belfast, and marked an agreement over the flying of flags, resulting in a reduction in the use of paramilitary flags and emblems in the Russell Drive area of Lurgan, and the removal of paramilitary murals from Trust property in the area. Plans for the future include the Trust funding of a mural in the interface area.

Reducing Tensions

In partnership with organisations from the public and voluntary sectors, Craigavon Borough Council developed projects looking at cultural and identity issues within new areas. In particular, it worked with community groups during July and August 2005 aimed at reducing tension during this period. The Council awarded funding to the PLACE Initiative and Mourneview and Grey Estates Community Association for cultural activities leading up to the lighting of the bonfires in July. The groups liaised with various statutory bodies such as Council, NIHE and PSNI

and also with key influencers to ensure the events passed off peacefully. Particularly in the Portadown area, the group were able to affect change around illegal dumping, size and positioning of the bonfires and remove contentious slogans. They were also able to negotiate the timescale on the flying of flags in the area.

Cross border, cross community projects

Since its inception in October 2003, the British Council's NcompasS programme has supported in excess of 2,500 young people and those who work with them in developing cross border, cross community exchanges. Activities ranged from Joint and Innovative Projects (52 projects) involving partners North and South, to Job Shadowing/Study Visits (3), and Student Placements (26 participants). Many of the groups which took part in NcompasS activities on a cross border, cross community basis did so for the first time. They appreciated the opportunity to learn about people and communities from different traditions. Participants' comments included: 'It opened my eyes to see how different people worked and it was interesting to explore misconceptions about each other', and 'the impact of the exchange on participants was very positive...the experience has increased their awareness of barriers to accepting others'.

Statement of Commitment

In March 2005, the Eastern Area Best Practice Equality Forum (which comprises the Eastern Health and Social Services Board, Eastern Health and Social Services Council and Health and Social Services Trusts within the Eastern Board Area), launched a Statement of Commitment to Good Relations. The Forum followed this up with a scoping exercise to identify existing policies, procedures and good practice relating to good relations across the member organisations. The Forum also engaged with community relations / good relations specialists such as the Community Relations Council and Trademark to explore how to develop a good relations strategy. In view of the pending re-organisation of the HPSS under the Review of Public Administration, it was decided to hold a workshop to again raise the profile of good relations, to highlight the effects of sectarianism and racism and to include the Hate Crimes legislation. The workshop took place in June 2006, and included presentations of current examples of good practice initiatives which promote and support good relations within health and social care, and

also partnership working with other statutory organisations, given by the Northern Ireland Ambulance Service and Down & Lisburn Trust.

The Good Relations statement adopted by each Eastern Board Trust has been printed on to a freestanding banner and is displayed throughout each organisation at reception areas, at staff training sessions and public consultations events (the statement is given as an example of a vision statement at para. 3.28 above).

Attitude survey

Conducted under the auspices of the ANIMATE Project, the Craigavon & Banbridge Community HSS Trust undertook a piece of research to assess attitudes and levels of prejudice of staff working in the public sector, including health and social services. Whilst the majority of Trust staff did not express prejudice against migrant workers, a sizeable minority of staff did articulate prejudicial and racist attitudes. The findings of this research will be used to inform future training interventions.

Good Relations Audit

The Higher Education Equality Consortium (HEEC) consists of representatives from the University of Ulster, Queen's University Belfast, St Mary's University College, Stranmillis University College and the Open University. In 2005, the HEEC appointed a research assistant to conduct an extensive good relations audit in each university/college. Following extensive research into good relations, community relations, inter-group communication, diversity questionnaires and diversity culture audits (research methodology), wide-ranging consultation, and a pilot survey, the audit was conducted between September 2005 and December 2006.

The audit investigated the state of relations between those of different religious belief, political opinion and racial background. In particular, it focused on six key aspects of good relations within the university context: perceptions of current relations; perceptions of university/college environment; social interaction; diversity programmes; teaching and learning; and views on good relations.

The results of each audit were presented in individual reports for each consortium member, for general publication and dissemination. The recommendations from the audit will be used to inform general equality and good relations practices and developing good relations strategies at each member institution.

New Housing Development for Travellers

In December 2003, the NI Housing Executive took over responsibility for managing the Travellers site at Ballyarnett, and have been meeting regularly with Travellers and the Derry Travellers Support Group to progress plans to develop ten properties and a transit site. Work has now commenced and once the site is cleared, North & West Housing Association can begin construction.

The ten houses are for settled Travellers and the transit site will meet the needs of the nomadic Travellers. Six hard stand units with pods (self contained shower, W.C. and laundry unit) have been provided and six Travellers have moved their mobile homes to the hard stands. This is an innovative project and the first within Derry to meet the specific needs of Travellers.

Commenting on the proposals Margaret Boyle, the Director of the Derry Travellers Support Team at Ballyarnett said: “We are delighted to have facilitated consultation between the Travellers families living in Ballyarnett and the Housing Executive... .We believe this project will be a great success particularly as Travellers have been consulted throughout the process and will continue to have an input until completion of the scheme. Since the Housing Executive took over responsibility for the Ballyarnett site relations between us, the Travellers and the NIHE have been excellent. We hope to continue to develop this relationship and to work in partnership with the Housing Executive and North & West Housing Association well into the future and recommend this partnership is viewed as a model of good practice for other agencies.”

Outreach project for young people

The South Belfast District Command Unit of the Police Service observed that due to the increase in ethnic minorities in the Donegall Pass area, an increase in hate crime was observed with 37% of all race crime recorded in this area between April 2004 and March 2005. In response to this, the Community Policing Team developed an initiative aimed at influencing the socialization of young people in the area, to encourage a better understanding of diversity and different cultures contributing in the long term to the relationships between diverse groups in the local community. The initiative was developed in partnership with the Belfast Education and Library Board, Outward Bound NI, South Belfast Area

Project and the Chinese Welfare Association.

Initially twenty young people were brought together, ten from socially and economically deprived areas of the sector and ten from the Chinese community. They underwent a five day residential course at Ullswater Outward Bound Centre. The emphasis on the course was the development of relationships, exploration of each others culture, identity and experiences and the tackling of their own perceptions and prejudices. Favourable comment was made by the participants on completion of the course, including “Chinese people have been racially attacked for nothing and we have been through the same thing” and “It made me want to continue with this project so we can learn from and share with each other more of who we are.”

As expected outcomes of the project, the project partners anticipate that knowledge and understanding will be created within the communities that share this area and racial attacks will reduce. To date racial attacks have declined by 45%, although this may not be as a direct result of this project. The outcomes are long term given the number of young people that can be catered for on this annual course. The benefits will be arrived at through time as the influence of those attending filters to their contemporaries.

Annex 2

Schedule 9(4)

Schedule 9(4) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 details the requirements of an Equality Scheme:

- (1) A scheme shall show how the public authority proposes to fulfil the duties imposed by Section 75 in relation to the relevant functions.
- (2) A scheme shall state, in particular, the authority's arrangements -
 - (a) for assessing its compliance with the duties under Section 75 and for consulting on matters to which a duty under that section is likely to be relevant (including details of the persons to be consulted);
 - (b) for assessing and consulting on the likely impact of policies adopted or proposed to be adopted by the authority on the promotion of equality of opportunity;
 - (c) for monitoring any adverse impact of policies adopted by the authority on the promotion of equality of opportunity;
 - (d) for publishing the results of such assessments as are mentioned in paragraph (b) and such monitoring as is mentioned in paragraph (c);
 - (e) for training staff;
 - (f) for ensuring, and assessing, public access to information and to services provided by the authority.

Annex 3

Further Information

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Northern Ireland Community Relations Council (CRC).

The Community Relations Council (CRC) is an independent company and registered charity established by government to develop and strengthen community relations in Northern Ireland. Its strategic aim is to support development of a peaceful, inclusive, stable and fair society founded on the achievement of reconciliation, co-operation, respect, mutual trust and good relations. It aims to do this by:

- Identifying and developing new and effective approaches to peace-building and reconciliation in partnership with government, organisations and people.
- Assisting communities and institutions in working through and beyond the legacies of the Troubles.
- Promoting the adoption of good relations policy and practice at local, community and institutional level.
- Promoting community relations based on interdependence, equity and respect for diversity.

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